

**To Identify the Key Determinants for Successful Performance in
Franchising: A Study of Pakistan's Fast Food Industry**

Farhan Sharif

Thesis Submitted in Fulfilment for the Degree of

Doctor of Business Administration

The University of the West of Scotland London

2021

Acknowledgement

Undertaking this DBA has been a truly life changing experience for me. It has taken immense dedication and hard work. Despite the struggles it has all been worthwhile however, I could not have accomplished any of this on my own.

I would like to thank my supervisor for offering his considerable experience and knowledge to guide me through the course of my thesis. I value his cheerful enthusiasm and continuous encouragement and will cherish his mentorship.

Finally I would like to express my gratitude towards my friends and my family who during my entire journey of writing this thesis were always by my side, supporting me and had faith in me and enabled me to realise and comprehend my potential.

Abstract

In this contemporary world of globalization, businesses look for the ways to expand their business internationally and attain competitive advantage from their global presence. In this regard, franchising is a well-known business arrangement, yet underexploited, that attains an extensive portion of business, outside the local boundaries. This study sought to empirically investigate the key determinants of successful franchises entering into the Pakistani fast food market. The key success factors are sought from both the franchisee and customer perspectives through a combination of research methodologies i.e., quantitative and qualitative research methodology. In other words, a mixed method approach.

This study used questionnaires as the source of collecting data from a sample size of 385 respondents through an online survey method and then analysed them using the SPSS statistical software, to quantify the results and interpret them. In addition, this study also collected data by conducting semi-structured interviews with the franchisees and managers of fast food franchises in Pakistan and by conducting focus group discussion with customers to attain varying perspectives about key success factors of the fast food franchises operating in Pakistan. The combination of both research methods enriched study with different perspectives of both customers and franchisees and provides overarching results for the current study.

The findings of the study yielded some useful information to the prospective customers and franchisors who want to gain access to the Pakistani fast food market in upcoming years. Online survey strategy is used for carrying out both research methodologies because of the existing pandemic situation by COVID-19 that did not allow for field survey. However, the limitation of online survey strategy is, the delayed response from respective respondents; but this element was adequately handled by the researcher through a continuous reminder of emails and reminder posts on relevant social media platforms where the questionnaire was uploaded. As reflected from the findings of the study, product mix, convenience, price of products, atmosphere, business concept and managerial competence, brand equity and brand image were the key determinants of successful fast food franchises in Pakistan. Such findings can be used by fast food franchisors who want to establish successful businesses in Pakistan and other same regions in South Asian market. The study findings have practical implications for marketers, practitioners and future researchers who want to consider the factors affecting the revenue growth of the company because directed interventions may be needed to execute

sustainable strategies by franchisors. This study may act as a catalyst for emerging and essential activity in Pakistan and other developing countries.

The study has contributed a lot of knowledge on how to operate a successful fast food chain franchise in Pakistan. Through analysis of data collected, areas of improvement as well as recommendations have clearly sufficed, advancing the need for this study. It also expresses the need for future research to be conducted in this particular area of business to bring out new and better ways of doing franchising in the fast food industries, not only in Pakistan, but around the globe. The study also touched upon the impact of Covid in the fast food franchise industry in Pakistan which will serve as a basis for future research. The success of any franchise operation, besides fast food, may be gladly boosted by this study.

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	14
1.0 Introduction.....	14
1.1 Background of the Study.....	18
1.2 The Research Problem	25
1.2.1 Background of the Problem	27
1.2.2 The Impact of COVID-19 on Franchising Sector	32
1.3 The Impact of COVID-19 on Pakistan Economy	35
1.4 Key Determinants and Franchising System in Food Sector.....	36
1.5 The Application of Value Chain Business Model in Key Success Factors.....	38
1.6 Aim of the Study.....	40
1.7 The Objectives of the Study.....	40
1.8 Research Questions	41
1.9 Methodology	43
1.9.1 Methodological Approach.....	43
1.10 Ethical Review	44
1.10.1 Data Consent.....	45
1.10.2 Confidentiality	45
1.11 Structure of the Thesis	45
1.12 Conclusion	46
Chapter 2: Literature Review.....	47
2.0 Introduction.....	47
2.1 The Pakistani Business Environment.....	47
2.1.1 Economy of Pakistan.....	47
2.1.2 Business Economic Environment of Pakistan.....	49
2.1.3 The Economic, Political and Cultural Features of Pakistan.....	52
2.1.4 Pakistani Economical Impact within the Restaurant Sector	55
2.2 Key Determinants for Success Performance	58
2.2.1 Key Success Factors.....	58
2.2.2 Key Success Factors: Significance, Identification	59
2.2.3 Key Success Factors and Sustainable Competitive Advantage.....	60
2.3 Franchising.....	63
2.3.1 The Franchising System.....	64
2.3.2 Theories of Franchising	66

2.3.2.1 Theory of Scarcity of Resources	66
2.3.2.2 Agency Theory	67
2.3.2.3 Integrated View	68
2.3.3 Advantages and Disadvantages	68
2.3.4 Risks with Franchising	70
2.3.5 Internationalization of Franchising	71
2.3.5.1 Administration	71
2.3.6 Risk Management in the Host Country	72
2.3.7 Fast food Franchising and Key Success Factors	72
2.3.8 Key Success Factors-Franchisor Perspective	73
2.3.9 Key Success Factors-Franchisee Perspective	74
2.3.10 Critical Success Factors / Key Success Factors	77
2.4 Product Mix	79
2.5 Convenience	79
2.6 Employee Competence	81
2.7 Price	82
2.8 Atmosphere	82
2.9 Managerial Experience	83
2.10 Concept	84
2.11 Franchising Brand Building	85
2.12 Barriers in Franchising	87
2.13 Expand the Exposition	88
2.13.1 Price:	88
2.13.2 Variety of food:	89
2.13.3 Brand loyalty:	89
2.13.4 Customer satisfaction and brand loyalty:	90
2.13.5 Corporate Social Responsibility	90
2.14 Key Success Factors Varies Between the Countries	91
2.15 Gap in the Literature	92
2.16 Conclusion	94
Chapter 3: Research Methodology and Design	96
3.1 Introduction	96
3.2 Research Paradigm	96
3.3 Research Design	100

3.3.1 Population and Sampling	101
3.3.2 Qualitative Sampling Research	103
3.3.3 Sample Size.....	104
3.3.4 Data Collection	105
3.3.4.1 Individual Interviews	105
3.3.4.2 Focus Groups	106
3.3.5 Qualitative Research Data Analysis.....	109
Phase2: 3.4 Quantitative Research.....	114
3.4.1 Validity	114
3.4.2 Reliability.....	114
3.4.3 Survey Population.....	116
3.4.4 The Survey Process.....	117
3.4.5 No Response Bias	118
3.5 Random Sampling Error	118
3.6 Non Sampling Error	118
3.7 Nonresponse Error	118
3.8 Response Error.....	119
3.9 Sample Size.....	119
3.10 Method to Collect Quantitative Data	120
3.11 Questionnaire Design.....	120
3.12 The Formation of Questionnaire	125
3.13 Quantitative Research Analysis	126
3.14 Hypothesis.....	127
3.15 Hypothesis Testing.....	127
3.16 Chi Square.....	128
3.17 Correlation Determination	128
3.18 Conceptual Framework	130
3.19 Conclusion	132
Chapter 4: Findings and Analysis	133
Chapter 4a: Analysis-Qualitative Data	133
4.1 Introduction.....	133
4.1.1 Thematic Analytical Process.....	133
4.2 Study Participants	134

4.3 Interview Analysis for the Key Determinants of Successful Performance in the Franchising Sector	135
4.4 Focus Group Analysis for the Role of COVID-19 in Fast Food Franchising in Pakistan	147
Chapter 4b: Quantitative Analysis	151
4.5 The Response Rate.....	151
4.6 Reliability Tests	152
4.7 Demographic Statistics	157
4.8 Descriptive Statistics.....	165
4.9 Testing of Hypothesis-Correlation Testing.....	168
4.10 Regression Analysis.....	178
4.11 The Impact of Demographic Variables on Customers.....	181
4.12 Conclusion	185
Chapter 5- Findings and Discussion.....	186
5.0 Overview.....	186
5.1 Finding Through Qualitative Approach.....	187
5.2 Findings Through Quantitative Approach	197
5.3 Answer to the Research Question	202
5.4 Conclusions on the Objectives for the Research.....	203
5.4.1 <i>Objective 1: To find out the key success factors of the food franchising system in Pakistan.</i>	203
5.4.2 <i>Objective 2: To find out the importance of these key success factors in Pakistan's franchising system.</i>	203
5.4.3 <i>Objective 3: The impact of these success factors in Pakistan's franchising system.</i>	204
5.4 The Reaction of Pakistan Franchising Stakeholder to COVID-19	205
5.4.1 The Primary Measures were Emergency Care and Safety.....	205
5.4.2 The relationship between all the relevant parties is increasingly turning close	206
5.4.3 It was important, but it is unavoidable	207
5.4.4 Creating Connection between Franchisors and Franchisee.....	208
5.5 Conclusion	208
Chapter 6- Conclusion, Contribution and Recommendations.....	210
6.0 Introduction.....	210
6.1 Conclusion	210
6.2 Knowledge Contribution.....	211
6.3 Significance of the Study	212
6.4 Implications of the theory and practice of the franchising industry.....	213

6.5 Recommendations	214
6.6 Need for Further Research	215
References	216
APPENDIXES	229

List of Figures

Figure 1 FATBURGER Branch in Pakistan	27
Figure 2 Top five countries ranked in terms of franchising.....	33
Figure 3 The level of influence of COVID-19 on sectors	34
Figure 4 Pizza Hut Branch in Pakistan	35
Figure 5 KFC Branch in Pakistan	37
Figure 6 Michael Porter’s Value Chain	38
Figure 7 Competitive Strategy	60
Figure 8 Porter’s Generic Strategies	62
Figure 9 The Franchising Model.....	65
Figure 10 The Research Process	99
Figure 11 Research Design	100
Figure 12 Methodology Stages	103
Figure 13 The design process of a questionnaire.....	122
Figure 14 The Conceptual Framework	131
Figure 15 Thematic Analysis	134
Figure 16 Graph showing the gender of respondents	158
Figure 17 Graph showing the Ages of respondents	159
Figure 18 Graph Showing Names of Pakistan’s Fast Foods.....	161
Figure 19 Graph Showing Frequency of Visits to Pakistan’s fast Foods	163
Figure 20 Graph Showing positions of Customers who Visit Pakistan’s fast Foods	165
Figure 21 Graph showing frequency of Gender Visits	183
Figure 22 Graph showing frequency of Age-Group Visits.....	184

List of Abbreviations

CSF Critical Success Factors

FGD Focus Group Discussion

FSR Full Service Restaurant

QSR Quick Service Restaurant

List of Tables

Table 1 Characterisations of Pakistani Society Framing the Analysis of Brand Behaviour ...	54
Table 2 A summary of research methodologies and questions.....	99
Table 3 Design of semi structured questions from the managers and franchisees	106
Table 4 The Rationale for the questions and their study objectives	108
Table 5 Data Collection and Analysis Methods and Qualitative Research Question.....	110
Table 6 Findings from Analysis.....	113
Table 7 Table Showing the Statical Method of Testing the Hypothesis.....	129
Table 8 Case-processing summary	152
Table 9 Reliability Test.....	153
Table 10 Item total statistics	154
Table 11 Item statistics	156
Table 12 Gender frequency analysis.....	157
Table 13 Age Frequency analysis	158
Table 14 Name of the Fast Food Frequently Visited by Customers.....	160
Table 15 Frequency to visit the fast food franchise	162
Table 16 Positions of the customers	164
Table 17 Table showing the Descriptive statistics of the mean score of each variable with maximum and minimum values for each variable	166
Table 18 Correlation between success and product features	169
Table 19 Convenience and Success Correlation	170
Table 20 Prices and Success Correlation	171
Table 21 The correlation between success and the competence of employee(s).....	172

Table 22 Correlation between success and atmosphere.....	173
Table 23 Correlation between success and brand image	174
Table 24 Table showing the Coordinates of Variables and their values.....	175
Table 25 Table showing the grand Summary of the results of the hypothesis Testing	178
Table 26 Regression analysis.....	179
Table 27 ANOVA.....	180
Table 28 Showing the Success of the Dependable Variable Success.....	181
Table 29 Cross tabulation for gender and frequency of visits	182
Table 30 Cross tabulation for age and frequency of visit	184
Table 31 Comparison of literature hypothesised and research findings	202

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.0 Introduction

The study conducted by Alon (2004) stated that the increasing proliferation of globalization has profoundly emerged the global trend towards a single unified and interdependent economy, where there are common needs across the society. With increased integration between the nations, the research states that there is a huge homogeneity in the consumer behavior (Shapiro, 2005) A group of researchers conducted studies on the viewpoint of customers as the focal point for the emergence of standardized marketing strategies and suggested that the countries needed to tailor them based on the standardized characteristics of the product (Sharma & Christie, 2010.) On the other hand, some scholars are of the perspective that customer needs are varied and depend on the diversified characteristics; therefore, marketers must promote their products depending on the country characteristics (Sedera, Gable & Chan, 2004) Based on these contrasting viewpoints, where the standardized marketing strategies are on one hand and the tailored and varied marketing strategies are based on the country characteristics, the consequent strategy lead to a hybrid approach (Sashi and Kauppur, 2002). However, it is further noted that in certain instances, standardising certain elements of the marketing plan across countries may be useful by accepting local market characteristics and localising its aspects.

According to Vignali (2001), when the enterprises seek for international strategies, it is crucial for them to tailor marketing plans for different parts of the world. In this scenario, franchising is described as a type of business organisation that is designed to expand into global markets and enables for the adoption of a hybrid marketing strategy based on nation characteristics. (Johannesson, 2010) As argued by Sashi and Karuppur, (2002), franchising adopts the standardized elements with localization of some attributes particular to the country. This type of establishing business allows the business to tailor each country's specific requirements.

The franchise system is described as the type of business relationship where the franchisor provides a right of running the business by utilizing the trademark of the franchisor and allows franchisee to carry out business under specific terms and conditions specified in the agreement (Hoffman and Preble, 2004). Under this agreement, the franchisor is accountable to

offer training and guidance to the organization for the running a business under same brand name. This is furthermore illustrated by Luangsuwimol & Kleiner (2004) where it states that franchise system is the process of distributing and marketing the products and services by utilizing the established business framework. For this reason, the franchisee (the person who buys the trademark to run a business) has the greater chance to progress in the market with the established structure. Ramírez-Hurtado et al. (2011) explained franchising business as, “ franchisors developing products, services ideas and offer them to the franchisee for marketing them in the particular geographical territories”. In this context, the franchisee is required to pay the starting fee and then accordingly pay a “royalty” to the franchisor. Although, hybrid marketing strategy is provided by the franchisor to run the business, some elements are left open to the franchisee to determine the local needs and promote the products and services that match the local needs of customers, for instance, local marketing approaches, recruiting workers and day to day activities like selling procedure etc. (Sashi and Karuppur, 2002).

Franchising is determined as one of the most favourable means of getting involved in the business and in the range of activities. As mentioned by Johannesson (2010), the changing demographic characteristics of customers, franchising is considered as the essential strategies for those firms that want to expand their business in the international market. Nevertheless, franchising is used in every type of industries (Felício et al., 2014b, Michael and Combs, 2008), and in particular retail and service industries like food (Gillis et al., 2014, Gorovaia and Windsperger, 2013) is one of the popular areas where the nature of the product and services could not be separated from manufacturing and the consumption process. In this particular situation, organisations are required to disseminate their chains by establishing the outlets near their consumers (Kandampully, 2006)

Initially, franchising started with “Singer Company” during the 19th century in the United States of America. However, with the passage of time, other organisations like McDonalds, Burger King, Coca Cola and Pizza Hut started utilizing this marketing strategy to expand their businesses in the international market (Eser, 2012). Presently, various businesses in multiple industries are using this concept (Hoffman and Preble, 2003), which has received a profound attention from a wide array of researchers and academicians, marketers and policy makers (Madanoglu et al., 2011). The scholars provide their viewpoints by stating that franchise helps in establishing new opportunities for employment and develop the local and economic status of the country (Kandampully, 2006), thus, it continues to enhance the significance in various countries like the United States of America., United Kingdom,

Germany, France and many other countries including Pakistan, India and Bangladesh. The rationale is provided by scholars (e.g., Combs et al., 2011a; Cochet et al., 2008a) that those companies that are formed under franchising systems could progressively get the benefit of experts and adapt the characteristics of the local market to expand their business operations in lesser time. Even to some extent, it allows organisations to enter into the markets that are unfamiliar to them.

Franchising entails a major part of the distribution framework around the world. More than 7,000 companies are indulged in franchising (Doherty, 2007), spread around 85 countries and have over 500,000 retail regions. Information revealed by the International Franchise Association Educational Foundation and cited by Combs et al., (2004) that around one third of retail outlets are now run under franchise system, spanned across various nations. In particular, the restaurant franchising system, which is estimated as exceeding \$70 billion, accounted for nearly 40% of franchise system. Another study conducted by Roberts-Lombard (2009) stated that by the year 2020, 50% of all franchise retail outlets will belong to the food and restaurant chains. Nevertheless, franchising is the unique type of business activity that includes the symbiotic and differentiated legal presence in the world of business ventures. Although in the relationship between the franchiser and the franchisee, it seems a distinctive association because both the units look separate from each other. However, they are so closely attached to each other that it engenders the concept of partnership and or strategic alliance between the companies. According to Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) the franchise system has three elements: interdependency between the entities, symbolic and individual units and organisations.

The researchers recognized two major categories of the franchising system: product-trade name franchising and business format franchising. In the first category, there is a contractual series of distributing products that is established by the franchisor and the second category involves franchisor providing license to the franchisee to imitate the business idea of franchisor in another region. Product trade-name franchising is described by Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) as that which is raised when the product gained familiarity and it requires a nation-wide or global-wide marketing of business. This is particularly the situation when there is a progressive development in the technological aspect and or success of the products and services raises demand for the production and distribution in more than one geographical region. Product trade-name franchising and business format franchising are distinctive from each other based on the legal perspective and functional activities of the businesses. According

to Manev et al., (2005) business format franchising has the opportunity to sell the business ownership to the franchisees, whereas, in the context of trade product name franchising, the products are sold through the franchisee. However, in both aspects, the core motive of franchising is the franchisors' wish to expand their businesses and distribute the products or trademark services.

This has been indicated by scholars that whatever category of franchising system is adopted by franchisor, the agreement is dependent on the mutual consent of both the parties (Doherty, 2007) Similarly, partners' decision and objectives are dependent on each other, which are designed to attain the common goals and objectives in franchising system. Moreover, the interdependency in franchising system is described by (Manev et al., 2005) According to the authors, there are three categories of interdependence: business, legal and agreement. All these forms accommodate based on independence. The research indicates that there are enormous benefits for entering into the contract of franchising system. Amongst these benefits are brand awareness, public identification, lowered risk due to established business format in contrast to independent business unit and the training and development provided by the franchisor. However, researchers criticize it as the franchisee has various responsibilities that enforce him/her to work in the boundaries set by the franchisor. This is important to mention here based on the past studies that if the franchise system is succeeded, it not only provides benefits to the franchisee but also to the consumers as well because in that case the consumers can have easy access to the global brands with localized strategy. For this reason, franchisees are immensely motivated to alter their strategy based on the tastes and preferences of consumers. Similarly, potential franchisees are also considered as the customers of the franchising firms.

The variations in services are found in the agreement signed between the franchisor and franchisee (Amberg, Fischl & Wiener, 2005). This means that based on the value of the franchising system, franchisors provide their services such as they may help franchisees for initiating their services by providing them funds to finance their business, locating areas for opening franchise, training and lease provision. Some scholars also state that when the franchise is established based on the continuing process; the franchisors' may furnish franchisee with the focal data processing techniques and procedures, control inventory, retail enterprise assessment, newsletter and meetings (Wingrove and Urban,2017). All these services have the sole purpose to facilitate, monitor and control the franchisee's productivity and reduce the issues that is likely to make problems in the long term relationships. However, it is optional

for the franchisor to set the higher price for royalty fee or base fee for providing extra services in monitoring and controlling activities.

The scholars conceptualize the relationship between the franchisor and franchisee and divide it into two distinct stages (Frazer and Winzar, 2003). The primary stage is the introduction stage, where the franchisor and franchisee share their mutual interdependency and encouragement to continue the relationship and foster the steps towards profits and succession. The second stage is determined by the growth and embarking business functioning. This is the phase where the franchisor is providing support to the fresh and new franchisee and so the association continue to grow and develop; however, if the franchisor does not offer adequate training and development to the franchisee, the problems can be raised. Once the relationship of trust and understanding is developed, the maturity stage is achieved in the relationship between franchise and franchisor, which demonstrates that the franchisee has adequately developed an exact image of the competence and expertise of the franchisor. Finally, the last stage of decline is observed if i) the business is not performing well and the agreement is likely to be cancelled; ii) the business is thriving for progression and the association between the two parties is strengthened.

1.1 Background of the Study

According to Vignali (2001), when the enterprises seek for international strategies, it is crucial for them to tailor marketing strategies to the various regions in the world. In this context, franchising is defined as a type of business organisation that is designed to expand into global markets and allows for the implementation of a hybrid business model based on the characteristics of the country (Johannesson, 2010).

As argued by Sashi and Karuppur, (2002), franchising adopts the standardized elements with localization of some attributes particular to the country. This type of establishing business allows the business to tailor each country's specific requirements. The franchise system is described as the type of business relationship where the franchisor provides a right of running the business by utilizing the trademark of the franchisor and allows franchisee to carry out business under specific terms and conditions specified in the agreement (Hoffman and Preble, 2004). Under this agreement, the franchisor is accountable to offer training and guidance to the organization for the running a business under same brand name. This is furthermore illustrated by Luangsuvimol & Kleiner (2004) that the franchise system is the process of distributing and marketing the products /services by utilizing the established business framework. For this

reason, the franchisee (the person who buys the trademark to run a business) has the greater chance to progress in the market with the established structure.

Ramírez-Hurtado et al. (2011) explained franchising business as, “franchisors develop products/service ideas and offer them to the franchisee for marketing them in the particular geographical territories”. In this context, the franchisee is required to pay the starting fee and then accordingly pay a “royalty fee” to the franchisor. Although, hybrid marketing strategy is provided by the franchisor to run the business, but some elements are left open to the franchisee to determine the local needs and promote the products/services that match the local needs of customers, for instance, local marketing approaches, recruiting workers and day to day activities like selling procedure etc. (Sashi and Karuppur, 2002).

Franchising is determined as one of the most favourable means of getting involved in the business and in the range of activities. As mentioned by Johannesson (2010), the changing demographic characteristics of customers, franchising is considered as the essential strategies for those firms that want to expand their businesses in the international market. Nevertheless, franchising is used in every type of industries (Felício et al., 2014b, Michael and Combs, 2008), and in particular, retail and service industries like food (Gillis et al., 2014, Gorovaia and Windsperger, 2013) is one of the popular areas where the nature of the product/services could not be separated from manufacturing and consumption process.

In this particular situation, organisations are required to disseminate their chains by establishing the outlets near their consumers (Kandampully, 2006) Initially, franchising started with the “ Singer company” during the 19th century in the United States of America;- however, with the passage of time, other organisations like McDonalds, Burger king, Coca Cola and Pizza Hut started utilizing this marketing strategy to expand their business in the international market (Eser, 2012). Presently, various businesses in multiple industries are using this concept (Hoffman and Preble, 2003), which has received a profound attention from the wide array of researchers and academicians, marketers and policy makers (Madanoglu et al., 2011). The scholars provide their viewpoint by stating that franchise helps in establishing new opportunities for employment and develop local and economic status of the country (Kandampully, 9 2006), Thus, franchising continues to enhance this significance in various countries such as the USA, the UK, Germany, France and many other countries including Pakistan, India and Bangladesh.

The rationale is provided by scholars (e.g., Combs et al., 2011a; Cochet et al., 2008a) that those companies that are formed under franchising system can progressively get the benefits of experts and adapt the characteristics of local markets to expand their business operations in lesser time. Even to the extent, it allows organisations to enter into the markets that are unfamiliar to them.

Franchising entails a major part of the distribution framework around the world. More than 7000 companies are indulged in franchising (Doherty, 2007), spread around 85 countries and have over 500,000 retail regions. Information revealed by the International Franchise Association Educational Foundation and cited by Combs et al., (2004) stated that around one third of retail outlets are now run under franchise systems, spanned across various nations. In particular, restaurant franchising systems estimated as exceeding \$70 billion, accounted for nearly 40% of franchise system. Another study conducted by Roberts-Lombard (2009) stated that by the year 2020, 50% of all franchise retail outlets will belong to food and restaurant chains.

Nevertheless, franchising is the unique type of business activity that includes the symbiotic and differentiated legal presence in the world of business ventures. Although, in the relationship between franchiser and franchisee, it seems a distinctive association because both the units look separate from each other; however, they are closely attached to each other and that rises the concept of partnership and or strategic alliance between the companies. According to Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) the franchise system has three elements: “interdependency between the entities, symbolic and individual units/organisations”. The researchers recognized two major categories of franchising systems: “product-trade name franchising and business format franchising”. In the first category, there is a contractual series of distributing products that is established by the franchisor and the second category involves franchisor providing license to the franchisee to imitate the business idea of franchisor in another region.

Product trade-name franchising is described by Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) that it is raised when the product gained familiarity and it requires a nation-wide or global-wide marketing of business. This is particularly the situation when there is a progressive development in the technological aspect and or success of the products or services raises demand for the production and distribution in more than one geographical region. Product trade-name franchising and business format franchising are distinctive from each other based on the legal perspective and functional 10 activities of the businesses.

According to Manev et al., (2005) business format franchising has the opportunity to sell the business ownership to the franchises, whereas, in the context of trade product name franchising, the products are sold through a franchisee. However, in both aspects, the core motive of franchising is when franchisors' wish to expand their businesses and distribute the products or trademark services. This has been indicated by scholars that whatever category of franchising system is adopted by franchisor, the agreement is dependent on the mutual consent of both parties (Doherty, 2007) Similarly, partners' decisions and objectives are dependent on each other, which are designed to attain the common goals and objectives in the franchising system.

The interdependency in the franchising system is described by (Manev et al., 2005). According to the authors, there are three categories of interdependence: business, legal and agreement. All these forms are based on the independence of each other. Their research indicates that there are enormous benefits for entering into the contract of the franchising system. Amongst these benefits some are brand awareness, public identification, lowered risk due to established business format in contrast to independent business units and the training and development provided by the franchisor. However, researchers criticize it as the franchisee has various responsibilities that enforce him or her to work within the boundaries set by the franchisor. This is important to mention here based on the past studies that if the franchise system is successful, it does not only provide benefits to the franchisee, but also to the consumers as well. This is because in that case, the consumers can have easy access to the global brands with localized strategy. For this reason, franchisees are immensely motivated to alter their strategies based on the tastes and preferences of consumers.

Similarly, potential franchisees are also considered as the customers of the franchising firms. The variations in services are found in the agreement signed between the franchisor and franchisee (Amberg, Fischl & Wiener, 2005) This means that based on the value of the franchising system, franchisors provide their services such as they may help franchisees in initiating their services by providing them funds to finance their businesses, locating areas for opening franchises, training and lease provision. Some scholars also state that when the franchise is established based on the continuing process, the franchisors' may furnish franchisee with the focal data processing techniques and procedures, control inventory, retail enterprise assessment, newsletter and meetings. All these services have the sole purpose to facilitate, monitor and control the franchisee's productivity and reduce the issues that are likely to engender problems in the long-term relationships. However, it is optional for the franchisor

to set the higher price for royalty fees or base fees for providing extra services in monitoring and controlling activities.

The scholars conceptualize the relationship between the franchisor and franchisee and divide it into two distinct stages (Frazer and Winzar, 2003) The primary stage is the introduction stage, where the franchisor and the franchisee share their mutual interdependency and encouragement to continue the relationship and foster the steps towards profits and success. The second stage is determined by the growth and embarking business functioning. This is the phase where the franchisor is providing support to the fresh and new franchisee and so the association continue to grow and develop; however, if the franchisor does not offer adequate training and development to the franchisee, problems can be raised. Once the relationship of trust and understanding is developed, the maturity stage is achieved in the relationship between franchise and franchisor, which demonstrates that the franchisee has adequately developed an exact image of the competence and expertise of the franchisor.

Finally, the last stage of decline is observed if the business is not performing well and the agreement is likely to be cancelled ii) the business is thriving for progression and the association between the two parties is strengthened. A large number of studies have been conducted to evaluate the reasons why organisations choose the franchise systems of business for distributing their products nationwide and globally. However, the literature lacks the empirical evidence for the success factors that contribute to the progression of franchising in other localities. According to Frazer and Winzar (2003) the success of franchising as an organisational framework and its positive influence on the business industry demonstrates its progression and significance for the economic and social aspects.

Past research have been conducted to compare the failure and success rates of the multiple franchised and non-franchised firms (Frazer and Winzer, 2005; Manev et al., 2005); however, to understand the operational variables of franchise organization, it is essential for the business entrepreneur to identify and understand the factors contributing to the franchising system's success or failure. Furthermore, the influence of choice in selecting type of franchise, communication process, power, level of support provided by the franchisor and the level of satisfaction franchisee has due to franchising system are some of the notable elements that determine the success rate of the franchise organization.

The scholars (Frazer and Winzar, 2003) state their perspective that there are two eminent factors that have substantial impacts on the progression of the franchise system: “selection criteria for franchise and franchisee entrepreneurial ability”. The choice of selecting franchisee has been one of the crucial decisions made by the franchisor in the anticipation of successful operational activities. This is, however, argued by scholars that once quality is controlled and enhanced by the franchisor by utilizing a thorough screening process, and testing franchisee performance for the continuation of franchise system, the franchisor can reduce the monitoring and the controlling costs to a large extent. The literature suggests that for the franchisor, the choice of selecting the franchisee is most critical step for determining the long term success of the franchise system (Goulding, 2002; Lim and Frazer, 2004); however, there is no uniform selection process determined by the franchisor for the selection of a franchisee, but it depends on the entrepreneurial abilities of both parties that help them to decide on taking those steps that have substantial roles in the subsequent progression of the franchise unit. Here, according to Kandampully (2006) entrepreneurial ability of the franchisee is identified as linked to the success and failure of the franchise unit. It is an undeniable fact that this demanding and challenging landscape calls for the businessperson to possess the attributes of entrepreneurship in order to survive in this business market that requires continuous changes and innovative ideas to compete with market rivalries.

Particularly in the context of franchising business, the franchisor must possess the attributes of entrepreneurship because they compete either at national or global levels that involve the business environment, which is exponentially highly competitive and requires changes as time progresses (Sedera, Gable & Chan, 2004) However, some scholars present their viewpoint that the franchisee activities are usually limited as they cannot pursue entrepreneurial activity because by doing so, their perspectives can raise conflicts with the franchisors’ goals. Although, this viewpoint is not supported by Sedera, Gable & Chan (2004) who stated that franchisees have profound personal investments in their franchise firms for which they tend to reflect the entrepreneurial attributes so that they can develop their fame in the relevant market and influence the parent and larger organization, which they represent. In essence, this is further argued that franchising does not essentially offer the franchisee the huge degree of control, but entrepreneurial ability is required due to increasing changes observed in demographics as the geographical location is changed. For instance, taking an example of the South African economy for the fast-food market for franchising system, research indicates that the country observed 160% increase in sales revenue generated due to fast food industry between 2006 and

2015 because nearly 22% of the fast-food industry is led by franchising system of various global chains such as McDonalds, Subway etc.

The research on the increase in South African fast-food industry due to franchising system indicates that there are certain elements that are responsible for this growth in South Africa. These include increase in brand awareness, health knowledge, quality of the products, satisfaction with the services etc. (Mackay et al. 2013, p. 68; Roberts-Lombard 2009, p. 236). According to Hua and Dalbor (2013, p. 724), franchising can be better explained by using extant theory that states that both franchisors and franchisee opt for the franchising business because they want to enhance the productivity as the time moves on. Consequent upon this, the firm's experiences increase in sales revenue.

Similarly, another study conducted by Michael and Combs (2008, p. 76) stated that franchising had the core focus on the agency cost because the franchisor has the liability to ascertain that high quality is maintained by the franchisee across their franchise unit that ultimately presents the image of franchisor. According to Nijmeijer et al., (2013), franchising is proliferated across countries and widely adopted as a business framework because in this regard, the entire liability to arrange, advertise, build a brand, control quality, product and services mix of the units are the obligations of the franchisor who ensures that growth, development and long-term market sustainability is maintained. Although, the significance of such an agreement for the franchising system and the attained benefits are ascertained, multiple scholars have evaluated and recognized the factors that impact the productivity and revenue of both the franchisor and franchisee (e.g., Kacker et al., 2013, p. 25). For instance, factors like the location of the franchise unit, ease of access, quality of the products and services offered, quality of the atmosphere, image of the franchise, perceived customer value (So et al., 2013, p. 33) are all linked to the enhanced performance of the franchise unit.

Another study conducted by Urbana and Kongo (2015, p. 2) revealed that usually successful franchise units are customer-centric and follow strategic and tactical solutions that surrounds their current and potential customers. The choice of selecting store location is widely discussed by the previous scholars in the context of franchise system. According to Jaravaza and Chitando (2013, p. 303), customer decision to buy from a store is dependent on the ease of access, location, quality of retail, customer services, prices, ambiance, promotions and brand selection criteria. However, it is arguably correct that the process of franchise growth is so complex that

it cannot be attributed to the single factor to illustrate the outcome of the franchise process. In the prospect of the restaurant and the food chain industry, the franchise system has gained immense popularity and expanded the global presence that fueled the sales revenue generated from the food chains working under a franchise system.

According to Schlosser (2001), urbanization and mobility are immensely increased and have enforced people to commute to and from the workplace only. Similarly, large number of women joined the workplace that results in less time accessible for them to make meals at home. This led to the solutions using ready-to-eat food, which is demonstrated as the primary reason for progression in the restaurant and the food industry within the franchising system. The increase in fast foods, with simple menus and quick services leads to the standardization of products and related services that are comparatively convenient to franchises. Another study conducted by Doherty (2007) also observed that a wide array of fast-food organisations are parts of franchising because in the context of the fast-food industry, the franchisee is immensely attracted with the concept of adopting already established brands, instead of developing their own fast-food units due to the challenging demographic characteristics like customer tastes and preferences for service quality.

1.2 The Research Problem

In the previous decade, investigating the influential elements of the business organisations that affected their performances had been the focal area of discussion for various scholars in management and social sciences. This is a true fact, based on the empirical analysis that various potential entrepreneurs are now exponentially running franchise units instead of running their own businesses.

It is a fact based on the empirical analysis that in Pakistan, various potential entrepreneurs are now exponentially running franchise units instead of running their own businesses. The fact that they can easily make profit under the protection provided by the franchisor, franchising business system is significantly expanded. A recent survey by Samsudin et al (2018) showed that the emergence of franchises in the past two decade showcased the immense transformation in Pakistan's multi-tier domestic market, even to the extent that international franchises saw a growing trend in Pakistan that depicted a deepening in the consumption-led economic development in the country. It is also estimated, from recent studies that the interest of Pakistani

entrepreneurs in global companies was increased by the progress of brand operators in Pakistan and the voracious desire for food in upscale market for branded markets show that franchising business has a bright future in this particular sector in Pakistan (Chun and Nyam-Ochir, 2020). The fact that they can easily make profits under the protection provided by franchisor, the franchising business system is significantly expanded. According to Doherty (2007) the franchisee can get the benefit of a well-organised and established brand with low risk of failure chances. This is even to the extent that, some businesses choose the strategy used by the franchise system to enhance their overall ability to compete in the market (Combs et al., 2004c). For this purpose, it is crucial to pay attention to the productivity, failure and survival of the franchising units (Barthelemy, 2008) 15 Although, many scholars demonstrate the success and growth rates in the franchising system, there is a need to demonstrate a critical analysis on the failure rates of the franchising system (Stanworth et al.,2004).

According to Marnburg et al., (2004), the reason of franchise-failure is attributed to their distinct performances and behaviour at different regions and the understanding of the factors that influence their productivity are likely to improve their probability of survival amongst the other franchises (Michael and Combs, 2008). Nevertheless, various scholars have demonstrated the performance of small and medium businesses, but there are limited studies that pay attention to the franchisee productivity. Research studies on the outcome of franchising and the key success factors that influence their performances are rarely carried out by previous scholars (Doherty, 2007) The studies predominantly focused on the efforts inclined towards the franchise productivity and the reasons for selecting franchising instead of an individual business firm (Michael and Combs,2008).

Based on the role of franchising's economic progression, the lack of research based on the influential factors that determine the success and failure rates of the franchising system seem to create a gap in the literature (Doherty, 2007) The scholars state that if the entrepreneur/ considers the franchising business system as the important part in the business journey, but does not gather adequate information about the factors influencing their performance, it then represents the likelihood of franchise failure in the market. According to Sharma & Christie (2010) knowledge about the factors that influence the franchisee performance could help the franchisor as well because in this way they can improve the overall system and adopt policies that support franchisee and the chain of the franchise system. Furthermore, previous studies call for extensive research to understand the influential factors of the franchise system and

understand the franchisee's consequences. Hence, to fill in the gap in the literature, and also the need to conduct more studies on franchisee's consequences along with the requirements to understand the factors that are key determinants for the success or failure of the franchising system, the present study focuses on the franchising system, the influential factors and the franchisee's performance and consequences.

1.2.1 Background of the Problem

The term hospitality industry is used to denote the food service, offer lodging, travel and leisure conventions on the large scale (Ottenbacher et al., 2009; O'Gorman, 2009). In particular, it focusses on the restaurants. These are determined as the food service providers that have the broad scope in the hospitality industry in this excessively competitive global environment where restaurants, food chains and related hospitality businesses practice high levels of product differentiation in their future prospect to retain and enhance their market positionings along with attaining customer loyalty and increased market shares. The competition is now changed from being confined to providing unique products to offering "superior services with quality and innovative products".

Figure 1 FATBURGER Branch in Pakistan

Source: (Bawany, 2022)

As argued by Pizam and Shani, (2009), this superior services in the hospitality industry involve a range of activities, experiences and factors that enable people to feel "at home" even if they

are actually away from their home and provide them tremendous and superior experiences that act as influential factors and persuade them to repeat their purchase activities. Even some researchers call this service “idealized mother” (Sherman, 2007) because providing superior services in the hospitality industry go even beyond what mothers offer at home. The experiences can involve a range of activities from friendly interaction to comfy ambience where people have easy access to their meals and accommodation along with greater focus on their entertainment and fun. In addition to various services in hospitality industry, the provision of food is the most essential aspect that needs to be focused on within this hypercompetitive environment.

Food courts or restaurants are found at every place from hotels to tourism destinations, to airports and railway stations to hyper malls. Large number of restaurants exist “stand alone” except other hospitality services offered with them like accommodation. According to the researchers, the restaurant industry is divided into two major branches, 1. QSR (Quick Service Restaurants) and 2. FSR (Full-Service Restaurants) . (Mueller and Kleiner, 2004). FSR include buffets and family services, as well as fine dining and ethnic cuisines such as Mexican, Italian, and Chinese. (Agnelo and Vladimir, 2007). On the other hand, fast food falls in the category of food that is provided to the customers that might include on or off the premises. They are furthermore illustrated by Sharma & Christie (2010) that fast food chains involve individual or food chains that are indulged in the provision of food related to sandwiches, pizzas, grills, fish and fries etc. This study has limited the scope of restaurants to fast food chains working as the franchise system. The reason is that the restaurant industry has expanded in the previous two decades due to significant expansion in the tourism sector and making a unified global economy. This is substantially fuelled by the change in lifestyle, urbanization and mobility of people due to work purpose. The busy life schedule and dual working families are two eminent factors that increased the progression of fast food, ready-made food.

Since the twenty first century is linked with franchising (Lashley and Morrison, 2000; Atkins and Bowler, 2001), the fast-food giants like McDonalds, KFC , Burger King, and Pizza Hut with simple menus, quality services lend the standardisation of product that is now conveniently franchised by businesspersons and or entrepreneurs and expand their operations through the franchising system (Quinn and Alexander, 2002). This is also observed by Quinn and Alexander (2002) that the fast-food concept with franchising system is more viable as compared to independent fast-food units. This is because there is a high potential of positive cash flow in short time as compared to the independent business outlets. Moreover, the

exclusion of unrequired start-up costs and the increased chances of market identification seem to increase the survival rate of fast-food unit formed under the franchise system (Mendelsohn, 2004).

Despite the perception of a relatively simple progression, changing demographic characteristics of customers (income, change in lifestyle, change in taste , preferences) have changed the paradigm from standardized product and services to customized products and services based on hybrid marketing strategy to satisfy the needs of customers. This is determined by the customers as the factors contributing towards the success or failure of the franchised system (Gillbert et al.,2004). From the customers' viewpoint, businesses are meant to satisfy the customer's demand. This seems impossible to grow the business irrespective of satisfying the needs of the customers (Anderson and Fornell, 2000) because if the customer is satisfied, he or she will become loyal customers who repeats his or her purchasing behaviour.

In light of the above discussion, it is evident that the satisfied customer is crucial for the long-term existence of the firm and has critical influence on the progression of the business. As in the context of present discussion on the fast-food franchise system, a happy customer with a high level of satisfaction remains loyal with the specific outlet, whereas, if the customer is dissatisfied with the service quality given by a particular outlet, he or she will avoid all the existing outlets with the same name and will generate unfavorable publicity and induce people to seek alternative outlets. (Gillbert et al., 2004). If a franchise fast food or restaurant wishes to thrive and compete successfully in the market, it must deliver consistent and high-quality products and services to clients from many cultures and countries.

Although, the customer viewpoint of services may vary across different cultures and at the time of globalizing organisations, the businesses need to consider the cultural distances and utilize the adaptive elements to lodge the varied cultural needs and tastes. Well-developed nations such as the United States, the United Kingdom, France, and many other developed countries have established well-defined market spaces for franchising as compared to the under-developed or emerging nations such as Kenya, Pakistan, Bangladesh etc. For instance, in Kenya, franchised restaurants like KFC entered the market in the 1980s but it closed down all its operations by the end of the year 2011 due to unsuccessful business sales due to the entrance of Nando's in 1998 from Zimbabwe. However, the Nando's' plan to achieve a minimum of 7 units by the end of 2007 was never accomplished and it withdrew all its operations by 2007. In

the meantime, all the Nando's outlets were taken over by Galitos, the Italian ice cream and frozen food company (Waithaka, 2007).

Moving ahead, another franchise pizza, Debonair Pizza and Steers, a subsidiary of "Famous Brands Limited of South Africa" captured Kenya's market in 1998, and reached six outlets by 1999; however, it closed down its outlets by 2008 due to loss in sales. Similarly, Wimpy closed down all its outlets in Kenya in 2013 due to lossmaking events. All these events show that in the emerging economy, like Kenya, either the franchisor or the franchisee neglected certain factors that led them to close down their franchise outlets within a few years of their inception. There are various other examples in the global market, such as the Malaysian franchise market in the food industry is vulnerable because they assume that this market is consumed by consumers directly and is directly related to their health and safety, which requires extra efforts towards value provision.

Another study conducted by Samsudin et al., (2018), stated that the number of franchises is increasing in Malaysia since 2000 and has reached about 23100 franchise units in fast food sector in 6years only i.e., by 2016. Franchising is observed as the means to expand business trade in the global markets. Research has shown that the franchise industry is anticipated to grow by 5% every year due to its good prospects in the global market. For instance, taking an example of Eleven Malaysia, which is determined as the nation's largest convenience store saw an upsurge in its net revenue for the financial year 2018 and the net sales rose from 2.4% to RM 51.32 from RM 50.1 million. This is linked with their high marketing revenue and innovative product categories catering for a large customer base. According to Monge (2017), in the context of franchising for establishing economic progression, it is essential for the franchisor to establish value and offer innovative products in order to develop trustful, valuable relationships with the customers. It is not a deniable fact that customers are exceedingly sensitive in the context of food and beverage industry because as mentioned by Noor et al. (2018), they directly consume them. The author further concluded that the customer's belief is easily influenced by the brand name and market image.

In this particular industry, customers identify products based on the distinction between the prevailing brand names in the market; thus, it is essential for the franchisee and franchisor both to differentiate their products based on their brand images in the relevant market (Zhang,2015). The brand name of the specific products is profound because it is likely to influence the

customer decision to buy a particular product. Based on the study conducted by Sowunmi et al. (2014), customers have the propensity to evaluate the particular elements of the products and services offered depending on their taste preferences and values. This is essential for every business who wants to thrive in this challenging market that they not only provide products but they fulfil the customer preferences and ascertain that the customer's desire is met.

The most significant element in the food market is the quality of the food that determines the success and failure of the particular outlet. According to Rahatullah (2014), trust and commitment are two important elements that are considered as the key success factors in the food chain market because it helps the business to attain competitive edge and ensure future growth in the market. In businesses, association between the buyer and the seller is established on trust and mutual commitment that need continuous development. In the context of the food chain market, trust is an essential element because it nurtures the overall success of the business outlet in the relevant market. Likewise, as mentioned by Monge (2017) service quality is one of the essential factors in the food chain market for the successful franchise business across the world. Service quality is the important ingredient (Monge,2017) that makes a difference between successful and unsuccessful franchise businesses. Some scholars say that it is the most powerful weapon possessed by the service industry to compete in the hyper competitive business environment (Rahatullah, 2014),

In an overview of the Pakistani Market for Food Chain Franchise, Pakistan has been selected for this study due to the steady development of franchising chains in the commercial and social industry of the country for the past few years. A number of reasons make it essential to focus on the Pakistani market and conduct research by focusing on the franchise sector. Firstly, Pakistan is not significantly explored in the franchising literature (Sharma & Christie, 2010) Secondly, the franchising sector has been the key sector for strengthening the economic condition of the country as it contributes a major portion to the Gross Domestic Production of the country. Most of all, they can help the economy achieve a milestone for the enhancement of the society by offering them quality services, distinctive products with value innovation and contribute to the expansion of the business sector.

There are various successful franchise outlets that have captured the market to a large extent and represent the country as the attractive destination for expanding global businesses.

However, the literature does not exhibit the reasons for the success of this emergence in Pakistan and the key determinants that foster their growth in Pakistan (Sunbiz, 2019). More so, Pakistan does not possess a franchise federation, which can be utilized for collecting data; however, the information presented by the Chamber of Commerce and other industrial data shows that the franchising system in Pakistan has attained a profound exposure in the international market and in a varied range of global franchise chains including businesses from automotive, fashion, hotels, real estate, shoes and telecommunications. Amongst the list of leading global franchise outlets operating in the commercial sector are Levi's, Mango, Mothercare, Next, Zara, C & K and Clarks. Similarly, in the food and restaurant sector, notable franchises are Burger King, Domino Pizza, Dunkin Donuts, McDonalds, KFC, Nando's, Johnny Rockets, Hardees, and Subway. It is interesting to state based on the prevailing market situation of Pakistan that the franchising system is paving its way through global food franchise chains since the 1990s (Augment, 2017). Pizza Hut is the primary fast-food chain that entered the Pakistani market in 1993 and it rapidly captured a large market share in the country. Subsequent to this, multiple other food chains followed their way and entered the Pakistani market such as KFC in 1997 and McDonalds and Subway in 1998, Dunkin Donuts in 1999; and thus, this trend kept going on till now.

In 2013, Pakistan Food Association, based on the market data projected that the annual sales revenue of global franchise food chains had reached 150 million dollars and was expected to grow if the trend continued. The existence of global franchises shows that Pakistan has a lot of potential for the progression and development of franchise industry. Moreover, this also indicates the investment opportunities for the domestic entrepreneurs to make investment in international franchises. Accordingly, the Pakistani market has 21 expanded various progressive franchise chains in the food market that raised incredible growth in the past few years.

1.2.2 The Impact of COVID-19 on Franchising Sector

Franchising is regarded by Qu et al (2018) as the commercial and social model that has various social and economic influences like employment opportunities, enhancement of entrepreneurship and economic development of the country. However, there is a direct influence observed by Bahauddin, Wei and Mantihal (2020) who stated that COVID-19 has affected income, jobs and the attainment of social goals in emerging economies like India,

Pakistan, Vietnam etc. A survey by the World Franchise Council in 2017 concluded that the economic influence of the franchising in South Korea, India, Pakistan and Taiwan are ranked as top countries that have a wide number of franchising brands. India and Pakistan have the largest number of fast food franchises with an overall GDP offering 16% of the whole sector. Pakistan is employing around 2 million people in the franchising sector, out of which 1.2 million are of fast food franchises and is ranked second in global franchising sector.

Figure 2 Top five countries ranked in terms of franchising

Source: Bahauddin, Wei and Mantihal (2020)

In regard to foreign franchisers, the above mentioned five economies offer favourable regions in terms of their size of population, per capita income, rate of urbanization and income sharing. Argued by Chia et al (2020), emerging economies like Pakistan use franchising as the instrument for enhancing their economic and entrepreneurial growth, employment opportunities and worldwide integration in the arena of business. The recent pandemic challenges have negatively influenced the economic and entrepreneurial context of the emerging nations. One of the key effects of this pandemic crisis is the removal of investment from those countries that are regarded as high risk environment and are at the greatest risk. Those countries that are dependent on exports of manufacturing goods like China, Pakistan and India are experiencing decreased demand. In addition, tourism is another key sector that is seen as an important source of revenue for various developing nations that are now paralysed due to the crisis caused by the epidemic.

The impact of COVID-19 on the service retail sectors is intense as compared to other market segments, out of which food services, fashion and construction are some of the notable segments, adversely affected by the pandemic crisis. The food franchising sector is greatly

affected by the adverse effects of the pandemic crisis with outcomes for the business practices and reliability of the franchising system. Such crisis results in additional challenges to the dynamic relationship between the franchisee and franchisor.

Although, there are various sectors that are related to the services and the retail sector, the franchising sector includes a wider spectrum of business practices and is influenced by the crisis to varying degrees. An empirical research by Chia et al (2020) showed that fast food franchisors are profoundly affected by the corona virus led by retail sector.

Figure 3 The level of influence of COVID-19 on sectors

Source: Chia et al (2020)

The fast food franchising sector in Pakistan surveyed the fast food sector to acquire knowledge about the influence of the pandemic on their businesses. More than 90% of the non-food retail stores were closed and food franchises were expected to earn only 60% of last year revenue. The country is evidenced to face a massive decrease in the fast food sector and food service businesses. Deliveries are the prime source of income for such companies with fast food franchises closed in the majority of rural areas due to health issues and those that are opened only offer takeaways.

1.3 The Impact of COVID-19 on Pakistan Economy

In February 2020, when Pakistan confirmed the first case of COVID-19, the estimations about the growth of Pakistan's GDP in 2020 were around 2.5%, indicating weak expansion of the country. The epidemic crisis in Pakistan resulted in the demand and supply crisis and had intense negative influence on the Pakistan's GDP, leading to unemployment and income loss. Exceeding 40% of the Pakistan's workers are working in the informal market. Eventually, the impact of such quarantine seemed devastating for the economic growth (Chia et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the emerging country like Pakistan is attributed by considerable social inequality. A large part of the country live in the slum areas of the cities' outskirts where along with poor health care condition and sanitation, overcrowding is another element that it is almost impossible to implement government policy of "social distancing". A study conducted by Shrestha et al (2020) concluded that majority of Pakistani population was unable to reach clean water i.e., 17% of the total population and around 45% of the sewage produced in the country is preserved by higher authorities.

Figure 4 Pizza Hut Branch in Pakistan

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of Pizza Hut restaurant. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Source: (Pizza Hut Centaurus Mall, Islamabad Branch - Phone Number, Branch Code & Address, 2022)

From all these discussions, it seems evident that hygiene is the key issue in the majority of the areas of Pakistan against which a strict lockdown situation could facilitate people to prevent the spread of disease. Similar to other developing countries like Latin America, the Pakistani health care system ability to enact with the epidemic crisis is extremely limited and as the pandemic placed extra pressure on the existing health care system, the government of Pakistan had to mitigate the influence of COVID-19 on the economy by adopting various measures. The primary provisions included direct and indirect tax measures, steps related to employment and to stimulate economy.

1.4 Key Determinants and Franchising System in Food Sector

The idea of “success factors” were first introduced by Daniel (1961) ; however, since it is proposed, various researchers have refined the topic and described it in different forms (Qu et al., 2018). For instance, according to Müller (2015).” critical success factors” mean that the organization has a limited number of areas that results in satisfaction and provides competitive advantage to the firm. Other researchers argue that these are those attributes, variables that if the organization manages them adequately, will have a profound influence on the overall productivity of the organisation in the specific market. Different researchers provide their viewpoints on the significance of the critical success factors for the progression of the organization; however, Nijmeijer, Fabbricotti & Huijsman (2014) linked the critical success factors to the relationship between the organization and the environment within which it operates.

According to other scholars, the sources of the critical success factors are based on industry, environmental conditions, regional locations, strategic conditions or other temporary factors. This shows that the underlying notion is to recognize the variables that are used to monitor and enhance the areas of business organization.

Figure 5 KFC Branch in Pakistan

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of KFC restaurant. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Source: (Covid-19: KFC tells customers to hold off on the ‘Finger Lickin’ for now, 2022)

From foregoing discussions, it is evident that franchising has become one of the essential channels in marketing for retailers and emerging sectors of commerce, which consists of restaurants, fast food and even the non-food sector including the miscellaneous sector. Usually, the research on franchising is carried out on western countries like the USA, the UK and Sweden; however, in practice a number of developing economies in the Asian market have adopted franchising as the source of growth strategy for their business sectors. Small, medium and even large organisations in retail businesses use franchising as the means of operations and development into the global markets for a number of years. For instance, fast food outlets like McDonalds, Burger King, KFC, Pizza Hut are franchised in their global operations.

According to Chiou, Hsieh, & Yang (2004) proposed their opinions regarding the fast food chain working under the franchising system. They stated that franchises use critical success factors as the source to facilitate managers of franchisees for the identification of those factors that help them in grabbing attention of customers. This ensures the long term market survival of the company.

Critical success factors may vary from country to country and even from market to market. According to Müller (2015) regional location has a significant impact on the overall performance of the organization and influences the critical success factors. There are other studies conducted on this notion, for instance; Michael and Combs (2008) stated that CSFs provide competitive edge to the particular organization and help managers to determine those factors that identify the market situation.

1.5 The Application of Value Chain Business Model in Key Success Factors

According to the previous discussion, the competitive advantage of a company is heavily influenced by success indicators. It did not, however, go into detail about how everything happens. The scholars answer to this question that when an organization considers the notion of “value and value addition”, it can attain success factors. Because the final good is provided in stages or chains in the fast-food market, it is critical that value is created at each stage.

Figure 6 Michael Porter’s Value Chain

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Researchgate.net. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

Source: Researchgate.net

This is the reason that this section highlights the concept of value creation from the perspective of Porter’s Value Chain approach and uses it as a theoretical notion and describes how success factors influence organizational sustainable competitive advantage. Figure 2.3 illustrates Michael Porter’s Value Chain. The figure explains the various stages of the production process. Porter (1985) best describes the concept of evaluating the value chain to determine the value as important success criteria. This concept is most commonly used in evaluating production through distribution, with a great focus on delivery time and quality that is commensurate with the price. According to Hoffman and Preble (2004), the value of a good is essential to progressive sales promotion because value is essential for consumer decision making. Using

this particular approach, it is indicated that organisations must commit themselves to creating value for their customers. Recent research conducted by Esteves (2004) indicate that the concept of the value chain is more customer- centric in this contemporary world of dynamic business. The concept of the value chain spans in every business sector. For instance, Eser (2012) used the value chain to examine the code of conduct covering the employment situations in Kenya in the agricultural sector. The literature examined how online business can improve their value creation process in apparel industry, whereas Esteves (2004) examined the applications in the hospitality industry and evaluated the value chain process.

Another study by Aliouche & Schlenrich (2011) proposed the model of value chain for the hospitality industry's sustainable competitive advantage. The scholars present their opinion that management must consider the "value chain model" as an essential element in their internal logistic, manufacturing, external supply chain, sales and marketing or services provided after the sale. The success criteria for internal organisational elements are likely to differ from those for manufacturing, marketing, sales, or after-sales services. This distinction in the various stages require the organization to identify the most important factor as there might be some factors that are not relevant for the organizational success. In the context of the fast-food sector, food quality, ~~nu~~ variety, ambience and facilities are referred to as success factors in the production phase. In the franchising sector of the fast food or restaurant sector, these factors have profound influence on the overall success of the organization.

The value chain model was created to evaluate and analyse the value chain's successful aspects and recognize the factors that might be associated with an increase in the customer service satisfaction. Argued by Eser (2012) the organization constitutes internal and external activities that influence the way it operates in the market. The internal factors of the organization are categorized as operational factors and the external environmental factors like political, economic, socio- cultural and environmental situations are determined as market factors.

In the hospitality sector and the application of value creation model, Esteves (2004) concluded that if there is production inefficiency that are linked with poor training of employees, this may result in poor quality of services. There are other tied consequences that may be attained like wastage of material resources, increase in operational expenses. When market inefficiencies are taken into account, the price of licenses and insurance rises, resulting in a significant business cost. Based on these findings, it is evident that critical success factors are those factors that influence the pricing of products and services offered in the food industry. According to Eser (2012) if pricing is influenced, it has a profound influence on the organizational competitiveness and the overall profitability.

The significance of value and the level of satisfaction are significantly linked with each other and both are claimed to affect the choice of customers in their decision-making process, whether to continue with the product or not. For the satisfied customers, value is the first and foremost step considered by the organisations. This is argued by previous authors like Esteves (2004) that if customers are happy with “value added services” of the organization, they have the ability to link themselves with a brand, thus leading to the elements of brand equity and brand awareness. Esteves (2004) stated that the organisations are immensely required to assess their external environment in order to attain value creation for their businesses and make strategic decisions and competitive market positioning. In the fast-food franchised sector, the production and service delivery process involve various steps that involves the critical factors and identification and prioritization are essential in the attainment of the key performance outcomes. This study uses sustainable competitive advantage as the key performance indicator for identifying critical success factors.

1.6 Aim of the Study

The research aims at critically finding out the factors that contribute to the success of franchising in the fast-food industry of countries, and with a particular focus on Pakistan.

1.7 The Objectives of the Study

The present study investigates franchising in the food industry in Pakistan. The study also develops and analyses the theoretical models of predictors that help to determine the impact of the key factors that are responsible for the quality of the franchisor-franchisees relationships. These factors determine the franchisees’ behaviour as regards whether to stay or leave the franchising contract. Moreover, the franchisee’s satisfaction with operating the franchising chain, the influence of the brand name on the quality of the association and the franchisees’ attitude towards franchisor’s support are also determined as the consequence of finding out the key success factors of the franchising chain. Sandberg and Alvesson, (2011) utilize Neglect spotting and Application spotting to identify gaps and develop research topics for this study.

The objectives of the study, therefore, are:

1. To find out the key success factors of the food franchising system in Pakistan
2. To evaluate the importance of these key success factors in Pakistan’s franchising system from the customer perspective.

3. To critically analyse the impact of these success factors that affect the franchise performance in Pakistan.
4. To identify the possible strategies for developing the Food Franchising Industry in Pakistan

1.8 Research Questions

As discussed in the previous sections, the study about the key success factors and the franchisee's consequences is limited. This includes the investigation of the franchisees' satisfaction and the reasons they exist in the market. It is a fact that franchisees provide significant wealth to their retail outlets and have higher expectations than those who have independent businesses. According to Daudpota (2013) franchisees strive for the better performance and exhibit higher productivity. They attain franchising because they want to enhance their abilities to compete. It must, therefore, positively influence their productivity. Entering into the system of franchising and following activity under well-established brand does not reflect the success of the franchising; nor does it guarantee its long term market survival. For this reason, it is important to understand those factors that influence the firm's survival and development, which are determined as essential attributes for franchisees who utilize their resources in the business venture.

While franchising is growing popularity across the globe, research on this kind of organization is limited due to its infancy. The bulk of international franchising research was undertaken in the 1990s, and the topic continues to get minimal empirical and conceptual attention. Numerous studies show that research on international franchising has been limited to concerns including as obstacles, motivating factors, constraints, and management attitudes. On the other hand, research in international business and franchising has recently begun to identify a variety of diverse types of abilities necessary to franchise globally. Despite the fact that franchising is becoming more common as a worldwide business model, there is presently little research on how to improve the performance of this kind of organization. This might be due to the rapid development of this sort of company model. The bulk of international franchising research was undertaken in the 1990s, and the topic continues to get minimal empirical and conceptual attention. The attitude of management and the difficulties they are entrusted with handling On the other hand, research in international business and franchising has recently begun to identify a variety of diverse types of abilities necessary to franchise globally. While franchising is becoming more popular, little research has been conducted to discover what factors, other than a company's competencies, are important in other countries, notably Pakistan. An evaluation

of franchisors' organizational characteristics and international plans, as well as their skills, may aid users in understanding what variables contribute to the success of international franchising. In order to accomplish so, these questions are researched, analyzed, and answered:

Research question 1: What are the key determinants that affect franchisee's performance in Pakistan?

Research question 2: What are the key determinants of a successful performance of international food franchising according to the existing literature?

Research question 3: What measures do franchisors apply in Pakistan fast food franchising system to manage and improve their critical success factors?

Research question 4: What are customer perspectives about a successful franchised fast food chain in Pakistan?

Research question 5: What are the possible strategies for developing the Food Franchising Industry in Pakistan?

The cooperation and the relationship between the franchising partners have profound roles in the progression of the franchising system (Alon, 2006) Determining franchising as the form of relational exchange (Nijmeijer, Fabbriotti & Huijsman, 2014) the association between the partners is crucial to illustrate the progression of the organization and the stronger the relationship between the franchisee and franchisor, the improved productivity of the franchising is observed. Findings from previous studies in the franchising system demonstrate that although much attention has been given to the relationship between the franchisor and the franchisee. Further research must be conducted to understand the factors that affect the franchisee in particular. This understanding helps to improve the relationship between both parties and neglect problematic relationships between the franchisee and franchisor along with the likelihood of failure of the franchising outlet. Based on the existing literature, therefore, it seems that the success of franchising an outlet seems to depend on the strength of the relationship between the franchisor and franchisee.

In the franchising contract, there are a number of factors that have influence on the association between the parties involved in the agreement and become a crucial challenge for the performance of franchise. Moreover, in the mutual association between the franchisor and franchisee, the partners are exclusively dependent on each other and performance to attain their overall goals and objectives. Hence, when studying the impactful factors in the franchising performance, one must always examine the associated factors of both the franchisor and franchisee, in addition to the relationship between them.

The franchisor has the responsibility to offer a number of services to the franchisee that involves training, offering raw materials, advertisement support and managerial training. The literature implies the significance of the franchisor's efforts and the consequences of the franchisee because the franchisor believes that the progression of the franchising outlet is profoundly dependent on the services offered by the franchisor. According to Nijmeijer, Fabbriotti & Huijsman (2014) the starting and the ongoing support and training from the franchisor have a profound impact on the decision of the franchisee to enter into the franchising system. This means that the higher the assistance is offered to the franchisee, the greater the probability of success in the market. Due to the critical role of the franchisor's services, the franchisee is also motivated to look for the opportunity that facilitates and motivates them to work with efficient franchisors that are likely to offer more effective services to them and they can follow their suggestions. In the traditional aspect, if franchisor provides adequate support to the franchisee, it will lead to the better influence on the franchisee and the likelihood of dissatisfaction can be reduced. According to Alon (2006) if the franchisee is offered with effective services through which ineffective services are eliminated, it will have a positive influence on the overall productivity of the organization.

1.9 Methodology

This research adopts a mixed method approach. Both quantitative and qualitative methods are used in the thesis. Data is collected and statistically analysed in the quantitative approach. The qualitative approach assumes a series of interviews and empirical data form publications. Hypotheses guiding the study have been developed and tested statistically.

1.9.1 Methodological Approach

The descriptive portion of this study is concerned with the collection of quantitative data, while the exploratory portion is concerned with the collection of qualitative data. We conducted exploratory and descriptive research. We conducted qualitative research using in-depth interviews to discover how restaurant franchisors and franchisees define, identify, and evaluate success. We also used exploratory research to clarify the nature of the problem: the key determinants for a restaurant franchise system entering the Pakistani market from the perspective of the customers. We used focus group discussions for this.

The qualitative method was chosen because it is exploratory in nature, and many researchers have hailed qualitative research as a catalyst for turning their ideas into reality.

In the exploratory design for the specific issue, the participants' feelings and understandings are directly measured. To create his or her meaning, it highlights the researcher's full comprehension of the circumstance or the perspectives of the participants. The flexible approach of qualitative approaches, rather than quantitative research patterns, can be used to gauge this type of information. The subjective aspect of qualitative research, on the other hand, limits the researcher's study because people's opinions and experiences differ, and sample sizes are tiny in compared to quantitative research, making it difficult to generalise over a broad population. To remedy the qualitative research's inadequacies, we use the survey method to measure and confirm the major aspects of what was left out of the previous qualitative segment of the study via focus groups; this is the method by which the triangulation process is carried out.

According to Burns & Grove (2001), quantitative research is a systematic, objective, and formal technique for gathering mathematical facts and figures to support reality. It's usually done to "test theory" by revealing the nature of variables and examining the relationships between them. According to Aliaga & Gunderson (2002), a quantitative method is one in which data is evaluated using a statistical approach. It is used to construct and test tested hypotheses, and it emphasises on explaining, forecasting, and describing. This style of research can manage a large amount of data and produce reliable results. A quantitative study uses a large sample size to get objective conclusions that can be extrapolated to the entire population.

As a result, a "Triangulation design" approach has been utilised for evaluation, which combines quantitative and qualitative techniques.

1.10 Ethical Review

The guidelines and policies for business research have been provided by the University of the West of Scotland. These criteria are followed throughout the study to ensure that the research standards are met and that there are no ethical concerns.

1.10.1 Data Consent

The nature of the project should be specified, as should the research's goal and, if any, the advantages that will accrue to the researcher. This was done in writing in an introductory letter and orally as part of the interview and questionnaire introductions..

1.10.2 Confidentiality

It is critical for researchers to protect the respondents' privacy and confidentiality. Respondents' and companies' anonymity should be preserved. This was communicated to the respondents both in writing and verbally during the introduction to the interview sessions. The data has only been used for academic purposes, and the participants' privacy is protected.

1.11 Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is divided into five (5) Chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction

This is the main opening chapter for the thesis. It discusses the aim and objectives of the research, the background to the research, research questions, methodology and structure of the thesis are all discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The main and relevant literature used in the thesis are reviewed in this chapter. It discusses main elements of the literature relating to the research topic which is franchising and its related subtopics.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology and Design

This chapter describes and discusses the main methodology used for the research. It includes both qualitative and quantitative discussions and how they relate to the research topic.

Chapter 4: Findings and Analysis

This is the main findings and analysis chapter for the research. The chapter uses both correlation and regression analyses to interpret and discuss the findings from the research fieldwork.

Chapter 5: Discussion of Findings

The research comes to a close in this chapter. It addresses the results reached based on the research's aims, as well as the research's main contributions to knowledge, literature, and practise, and gives suggestions.

Chapter 6: Conclusion, Contribution and Recommendations

In this chapter the major findings are discussed in this chapter, as are the study's limitations and recommended areas for further research.

1.12 Conclusion

This opening chapter of the thesis has discussed the main elements of the thesis. The aims, objectives, research questions and methodology for the thesis have been extensively discussed. The main background to the study as well as the research problems have all been discussed in sufficient details. The chapter also discusses the structure of the thesis and ends with a conclusion.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

The preceding chapter offered an introduction to the research, the problem statement, the study objectives, and the justification for selecting the research topic. The key and significant literature on Pakistan's business environment is presented in this chapter and its franchising sector in the fast-food market. The review begins with the succinct history of Pakistan and moves on to the economic condition and business situation of the country. Other related concepts like infrastructure required for developing business organization and macro environmental framework with respect to Pakistan is also discussed to understand the overall business environment of the country. Finally, the franchising in fast food industry is discussed with respect to key arguments presented by previous scholars and researchers.

2.1 The Pakistani Business Environment

2.1.1 Economy of Pakistan

Pakistan was established in the year 1947 after the partition of India. Since then, the country has been relatively unstable due to sectarian and terrorism attacks; however, since the country won a new presidential government under Prime Minister, Imran Khan, the economic and political condition of the country is improving. The initiation of new housing schemes, job opportunities and economic reforms are some of the notable areas that helped the country to improve its economic development (Uddin et al., 2018).

Pakistan's overall economic freedom score with regard to business and international funding is 54.8, which makes the country as the 135th freest economy around the world. However, research shows that the entire score is declined by 0.2% due to the decrease in the country's fiscal health points. With regard to the Asia Pacific countries, Pakistan is ranked as 32nd amongst the 42 countries. This shows that the country's overall score is quite below the regional index average. This is also argued by scholars that the Pakistani economy is mostly less free since the country-created index in 1995. However, the country's GDP growth is led by cotton exports for the past five years i.e., 2015 till 2018 (Uddin et al., 2018), which is determined as a positive sign for the overall country's success and economic development. On the other side, the economic freedom of Pakistan is hindered by insufficient insecurity of property rights and the inadequate facilities provided by the government of Pakistan to ~~the~~ anti-corruption and laws

for several financial freedoms like money laundering. Nevertheless, the major impediment lies in the Pakistani consumer buying power due to barriers in trade and high tariffs. Despite, all the above-mentioned circumstances prevailing, since 2013, Pakistan has attained a steady growth and development due to the credit facility agreement with the IMF. Moreover, in the year 2019, the economic growth was expected to fall to 3.3% from 5.5% in 2018 a net 0.7% points lower than the IMF previously estimated. The scholars argue that this occurred due to measures carried out by the authorities to enact the country's macroeconomic imbalances. However, this is also argued that in the upcoming future, growth is anticipated to slow down for 2.4% from the year 2020 till 2022. This is due to the reason that the country is working to sustain a strong monetary and fiscal stance. But with this progression, the IMF estimates an increase in GDP growth rate of Pakistan only in one year i.e., 2021

Researchers argue that the internationalization of the Pakistani market or its functioning in global markets is suitable for the franchising sector due to the likelihood of flexibility in franchising arrangements. This is the reason why those businesses that look overseas for assisted expansion in Pakistan, usually go for the franchising option and choose it as the best way to operate in the country. Franchising contract is flexible, which helps to contribute to the implied engagement of risks and uncertainties that is usually found in the global market. In the context of Pakistan's economy, franchisees have the increased chance to react quickly and adapt the changes to the local environment and manage the challenges that can be raised from the regional risks and uncertainties. Although, this seems to increase the cost for monitoring, for a country like Pakistan and its existing economic condition, franchise agreement is suitable for business expansion (Aslam, 2011)

The entrepreneurial spirit in the individual Pakistani is found adequate because the business regulatory environment provides support for the business start-up process. Moreover, the country has a reasonably good geographical location with a major seaport in Karachi that connects the country to many parts of the world. The increasing demand for trade through seaport, another notable seaport is Gwadar port that receives similar attraction for investors. Strategically, the country has a major link road with China, India and Iran and it is hoped that with the road link, seaports, railway lines, the country has a good network with the notable commercial centers around the world. In modern times, Pakistan is working on rehabilitation and expansion of its infrastructure, which includes startmacking on roads and creating a seaport over Gwadar region. With enhanced infrastructure and well-established business environments in Pakistan, it seems to have a potential to make the country a regional business hub for information technology, transportation and food the sector (Siddiqui and Ahmed, 2019).

2.1.2 Business Economic Environment of Pakistan

The Pakistani government has initiated various steps to enable the market for encouraging both local and foreign investment. This is also highlighted by various scholars that; the concepts of democracy and empowerment are persistently implied to overcome the challenges of upcoming unstable economic situation. The recent agenda by the government of Pakistan was designed to stimulate growth, development and protect the employment sector that aims to decrease poverty and improve food security and help the poor. The core elements of government agenda include:

- i) To maintain a stable macro environment and create the environment that enables businesses.
- ii) To develop key infrastructural facilities across the country to strengthen the employment sector and decrease poverty.
- iii) To ensure economic stability through the promotion of equitable regional and social development.
- iv) Invest in a healthy environment that promotes food and nutrition security.
- v) To strengthen the governance as a means of improving the public service delivery.

Following standards formulated in the western countries the like United Kingdom and other countries throughout the world in evaluating economic factors, the World Bank conducted an assessment of Pakistan's economic situation, demonstrating how easy it is to do business in the country. Such micro-economic indicators facilitate the understanding and the enhancing governments to create a friendly business environment by utilizing various regulatory frameworks that promote instead of impeding business. The evaluation shows that quantitative measures are required to start a business in Pakistan so as to attain permits, register property and enforce contracts for small and medium businesses. This is arguably correct in that the country's appealing economic environment necessitates regulations designed to protect investors' rights from exploitation, lower the cost of resolving conflicts, and make property rights understandable. Moreover it aids in determining the predictability of the country's economic connections.

According to Uddin et al., (2018) the Pakistani government fostered the environment for business by decreasing the number of permits required since 2010 and is reduced to half the number it had in 2005 and 2006. Similarly, the housing market is also reformed by shortening

the time it requires to attain a construction permit. This overall situation is designed to strengthen the efficiency of country's infrastructure. Since Pakistan has constituted the new system for fostering business environment, it eventually made things easier for the investors. The regulatory framework for registering business in various ~~parts~~ of the country is almost similar' the only difference lies in the time and cost of the town concerned. Karachi is determined as the easiest place in Pakistan to set up a business. The entire process is efficient in that, the process takes at most 20 days now down from 60 days back in 2010 till 2015. The time required for starting a business depends on the regional location and differs with the difference of 5 to 8 hours. Ideally, in Pakistan the company registration certificate is determined favourable and is treated as a license to initiate a business. On average, it takes 20 to 35 days for starting a business, which is reduced from 60 days back in 2009.

Another critical aspect is obtaining a business permit from the county council committee. The time required varies, depending on the complexity of business nature but usually it takes around 5 to 8 days. The company's registration certificate is determined as sufficient for starting any business because it is considered as the license for starting the business. Another important aspect is business permit, which constitutes a significant portion of the initial investment in a new business and is 30% of the start-up cost. Pakistan is now regarded by business entrepreneurs as one of the ideal countries for starting a business and has the ease of doing business as compared to other Southeast Asian countries like Bangladesh.

One of the factors that attracts franchisors to start their development plans in Pakistan is the ease and low cost of starting a firm. The increased efforts of the government of Pakistan towards transparency, straightforward policies and ease of doing business along with the convenient way of obtaining documents form a good basis for foreign investors to expand their businesses in Pakistan. In particular, the restaurant industry is determined as one of the ideal business sector that fosters international investors to establish their business in different locations of the country. This is important to mention that if the country has clear laws and regulations, it can facilitate the growth of the business sector and encourage investors to execute their business activities.

Pakistan has a large consumer market due to high density of population. This feature makes it the ~~country's~~ great strength. With the increasing population of 200 million people, Pakistan is determined as the world's ninth largest consumer sector country. With the increasing number of people, the diffusion of population is more inclined towards cities. With a progressing economy, a large number of people have enhanced their standards of living and stabilized income, which has given them excessive spending ability. This is argued by Uddin et al.,

(2018), that the increasing population of Pakistan with high standard of living exhibits the ability of Pakistan to maintain profound business growth. Along with the consumer market, Pakistan has a competent hardworking workforce. According to the report generated by CIA World Fact book and cited by Uddin et al., (2018), the total number of Pakistan's workforce is 55.8 million, which makes it the world 9th largest country in the world in terms of labour force.

Another study conducted by Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) stated that as the economy grows in Pakistan, it not only improves the standard of living but it also helps people to have increased access to education and health care opportunities. The hardworking labour force of Pakistan is regarded as a great asset for international investors; however, it is important for them to tap into this huge reserve of talent. Similarly, Pakistan's geographic location is also considered as the great asset to do business because it acts as a corridor that links the Middle East, China, Iran, Afghanistan and other Central Asian countries.

This strategic location of the country makes it a viable option for the international investors. Additionally, the free media in Pakistan makes it one of the viable options because in this way business investors are more likely to tap the domestic market through various promotional campaigns. Although, there are some political pressures exerted on the media industry; however, it is comparatively in a better and strong position as compared to other countries like Nepal, Indonesia and Bangladesh. Due to the presence of private channels, the country has a vast range of channels that shows programs ranging from politics to entertainment and food. In the rural areas of Pakistan, radio still serves as integral part of the media for communicating information and helping people to stay connected with the outer world.

In a recent report, SBP (2018), argued that Pakistan is widely held as the country that has the ease of doing business. Among the Asia Pacific countries, the World Bank regards Pakistan as the second-best country in terms of "ease of doing business". Pakistan's foreign direct investment laws, tax laws, foreign exchange freedom and banking processes make it non cumbersome for the investors to do business in Pakistan. Another opportunity is highlighted by Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) who stated that USAID serves as a trade initiative for Pakistan on which the country can capitalize on. In order to strengthen then trade arrangement between Pakistan and her neighbouring countries, an electronic trade portal provides the government of Pakistan with a great incentive to increase its exports to overseas. The establishment of the trade portal helps Pakistani exporters and overseas buyers to have access to business information in real time.

Overall, this entire scenario is depicted by Uddin et al.,(2018c) by stating that these initiatives can spur the economic development of the country and create business opportunities for the domestic and foreign investors. Moreover, this electronic trade portal is anticipated to remain user friendly and is expected to strengthen the quality of prevailing businesses and encourage business communities to improve on their exposure in the international market. This is also argued by Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) that with trade portal, the businesses are promoted effectively.

The emerging market of the Halal food industry of Pakistan is exhibited by scholars (Siddiqui and Ahmed, 2019; Saeed, 2013) as the one of the effective opportunities in the industry. Halal means “permissible in Muslim community”. The research indicates that with regard to the international food market, multinational companies like McDonalds, KFC, Hardees are some of the notable organisations that have positioned their businesses in Pakistan and linked their food to Halal food brand. This is further stated by Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) that in Pakistan the Halal food market constitutes a major food market because a large population of the country is Muslims and they are attracted towards Halal food with sanitation rules and strict food hygiene compliance.

Considering the current growth of the country in terms of business and trade, it is not a denying fact that Pakistan has some bright opportunities for the international investors that could encourage them to invest their money in the Pakistani business sector. In addition, there is a fast trend in Pakistan towards franchising business due to the increased business opportunities identified by international investors. The economic stability with ease of business opportunities spur on the commercial sector of the country (Siddiqui and Ahmed, 2019)

2.1.3 The Economic, Political and Cultural Features of Pakistan

In the last sixty years, Pakistan has had twenty-three governments, including fourteen elected or appointed prime ministers, five interim governments, and 33 years of military dictatorship under four different leaders. A politically elected government has an average life period of fewer than two years, excluding military and temporary governments. This instability has directly reflected on the performance of franchised fast foods in Pakistan; KFC, Pizza Hut, Domino's, etc. For security reasons, such operating franchises have either reduced operations or altogether halted everything. Change of government by forceful means always leads to untold damage, and this has been a real deterrent.

In contrast, the economic policy regime has only changed twice in Pakistan's history. The liberal private-sector-led growth model that was implemented in the 1950s and accelerated in the 1960s was reversed by Bhutto in the 1970s, and the socialist economic model was established. The general thrust of economic policy has remained unchanged since the rejection of this model in 1977 and the revival of the liberal model. In contrast, this has promoted the successful performance of franchised fast food in Pakistan.

Pakistan is and has been a predominantly Muslim nation. Furthermore, due to geolocation factors, there has been a general resentment for western culture in Pakistan, whichever the form. This has trickled down to low turnout at these franchise fast food joints, as would have been expected in a country with a dense population.

All major political parties have reached broad agreement on the general principles that should underpin Pakistan's economic direction and also shaped the level of brand image and behaviour in the country namely:

- a) In the allocation of scarce resources, central planning and bureaucratic judgement are poor substitutes for market judgement.
- b) Government functionaries should be discouraged from obtaining licences to open, operate, expand, and close businesses.
- c) Ownership and management of businesses, production, distribution, and trade by the government results in inefficiency, waste, and corruption.
- d) Overregulation, controls, and restrictions on the private sector of all kinds raise the cost of doing business.
- e) Individual and corporate tax rates that are too high are counterproductive because they discourage effort and initiative.
- f) Banks and financial institutions owned and managed by the government that provide cheap and/or directed credit have a negative impact on economic growth.
- g) Administered prices for key commodities are the worst possible way to protect the poor from the onslaught of market forces.
- h) Subsidies on inputs such as fertilisers, seeds, and water incur significant budgetary costs and benefit the wealthy rather than the poor.
- i) Foreign investment and multinational corporations should be encouraged because they are important conduits for technology transfer, managerial skills, and organisational innovation.

All these factors have greatly affected the brand image within the country .

Imran Khan the Prime Minister of Pakistan introduced the Ease-of-doing-business policy offering incentives to investors and making administrative processes easy enabling the international enterprises, local businesses and franchise outlets to start their business in the country with ease. This will increase the brand image of the country in the near future.

Table 1 Characterisations of Pakistani Society Framing the Analysis of Brand Behaviour

FEATURES	CHARACTERISTICS	BRAND BEHAVIOUR
POLITICAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instability in government - Violent change and rule of regimes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discourages successful interaction of such brands with general population - Negative effect on the performance of franchise fast foods in Pakistan.
ECONOMIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A bit more stable - Been two factions, the liberals and the capitalists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has had a fairly better effect on fast food chains. - This is due to stability in economic status and thus the

		ability to purchase amongst the population.
CULTURAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pakistan is dominantly a Muslim nation - General resentment for western culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Negatively affected successful performance of fast food chains.

Source: The Author

2.1.4 Pakistani Economical Impact within the Restaurant Sector

The tourism business in conjunction with hotels and the fast-food chain sector rose from its unstable position from the year 1990s to the huge recovery in 2000s. This is argued by scholars as the successful implementation of the tourism market of Pakistan that is executed by the Pakistani tourism sector, with the cooperation of the Pakistani government. The resurgence of Pakistan's tourist industry has contributed significantly to the country's economy as research indicates that Pakistan registered more than 1 million visitors in the country's hotels, and 15% of the sector employed Pakistani workforce. This shows the upward trend of Pakistan in receiving more tourists and giving full time employment to the citizens. This makes the tourism sector, one of the largest contributors to the socio-economic development of the country. According to Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) the emerging market of tourism in Pakistan has increased the growth of food and restaurants sector by 22% recorded in 2017 from 13.4% in 2010. This boosted investor trust and increased capital inflows to the Pakistani government, boosting the country's economic growth.

The function of tourism in the Pakistani economy is outlined in the country's national tourist policy. It is further argued by Saeed (2013) that Pakistani tourism is dedicated to offer high quality services mainly to the food sector including restaurants and the fast-food sector so that a large number of citizens can enjoy and visitors also have wide opportunities to enjoy alike. Considering the Pakistani tourism sector as the instrument to improve the overall economy and

enhance the quality of life, it is pivotal to encourage investment and share benefits for the food industry. The Pakistani government has recognized tourism as one of the promising sectors that has a lot of potential that drives economic growth towards sustainability until 2030.

The tourism and hospitality industry's specific targets are projected to be met by 2022; to increase the significance of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country with an increase in foreign visitors, thereby improving the quality services of hotels and the food market. The increase in number of visitors requires the country to support the facilities for hotels and restaurants. In this vein, international food franchises are likely to attract foreign visitors because brands from their own nations are more familiar to them. This is the reason that the growth in the tourism sector increases the momentum of the hospitality industry for restaurants and the fast-food franchises in the Pakistani market.

The political turmoil of the year 2004 till 2014 because of terrorist attacks and unstable political situation adversely influenced the tourism sector to a large extent. According to Zaidi (2005), hotels and restaurants, fast food chains declined in growth by 44% because this industry was the most severely impacted by both internal and external influences. The visitors cancelled their reservations for scheduled holidays and that reduced income the private consumption cost. However, since the government of Pakistan initiated different strategies for the tourism sector, the tourism sector improved by 10% in the year 2016. This improved the percentage that shrank due to unstable political situation.

Although, the factors leading the country towards economic downtown were not uniquely attributed to Pakistan, however; the instability due to political situation in the country dampened the foreign investors' confidence. In the near term, this circumstance resulted to a commercial turnover in several sectors of the country; nevertheless, the calm elections that began in 2016 offered foreign investors hope. This is argued by Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) that to improve the overall situation of the country, It was critical to encourage both domestic and international investors to invest in a long-term environment that is predictable, stable, and prosperous. The reason is explained by authors that the unstable political environment is not acceptable for foreign investors because they cannot take risks in the unpredictable environment.

According to Uddin et al. (2018), One of the most popular methods of expanding businesses in the hospitality industry is franchising. Usually, the business organisations who want to expand their businesses favour franchising options, especially when there is a probability of unstable

political and economic situations in the future. This is stated that franchising is considered as one of the best options for expanding businesses because it costs less in the monitoring of foreign outlets and has the difficulty to gain essential information about the local situation of the overseas country. Franchising as the mode of entry in international market is determined as low risk for the overseas investor because the risk can be shared between the franchisor and the franchisee, who is usually a local business person. The administrative aspect and the host country risk management are usually catered for by the local franchisee; thus, it makes it one of the viable options for the foreign business expansion.

Researchers have discovered that a chain of franchised food outlets has a superior ability to cope with the country's economies of scale, which protects them from failure and other financial limitations. Moreover, the experience that franchisor brings to the local environment is also argued by Siddiqui and Ahmed (2019) that it can improve the overall quality services of the local industry. Similarly, the experience brought forward by the franchisee also offers greater capability to monitor and regulate the market. This is also stated by Uddin et al., (2018) that the external environment changes rapidly, and that usually business organisations lack abilities to adapt to the changes quickly. However, in the context of the food sector, it is widely observed that usually the failure is attributed to the internal factors such as weak management, low quality services, low product quality and leadership of the organization as compared to the political and economic environment of the country. In the context of Pakistani business market, especially in the hospitality sector, it seems that the country has made adequate efforts to stabilize the market and have brought immense changes in the improvement of the restaurant market. This is also mirrored in market research, which found that hotels and restaurants that had fallen into negative territory due to the country's political turbulence regained stability after the sector began to grow at a rapid pace.

Pakistan is considered as one of South Asia's most affluent countries and is seen as the business hub for the majority of western countries due to its attractive strategic geographical location and emerging business opportunities. Although, in various instances, the country's economy is impeded with political upheavals and corruption, since the growth is spurred, the overall GDP of the country is recovering and has shown a significant improvement in the past few years. In addition, it is also argued that with the growth potential for business opportunities and enhancement in the country's infrastructure and local governance, Pakistan is seeming to be one of the countries that are appealing for local and international investment. The increased

urbanization and expansion of cities are also additional opportunities for growth in the food sector. It is also argued that, as the leader of Asia Pacific countries, Pakistan can serve as a gateway for global corporations looking to expand their operations in the country. One of the essential features that would motivate investors to take the advantage of growing opportunities in the food market is to create crucial success elements or key success factors for the food franchising system penetrating the Pakistani market.

2.2 Key Determinants for Success Performance

2.2.1 Key Success Factors

The recognition of “key success factors” was primarily proposed by Daniel (1961) and later Rockart (1979) improved and refined the term as “critical success factors” that means “the areas, which, if satisfactory, will ascertain progressive and competitive performance in the organization”. This term was later on adopted by various scholars with “key success factors” and “key determinants for success”. By emphasizing key, Ambastha & Momaya (2004) argued that the “most important areas” or “the focused areas” that are vital for the organizational activities and acts as pertaining factors for future growth. This shows that these factors must be carefully managed to reflect success. According to Box and Miller (2011), key success factors, also known as crucial success factors, are those characteristics that determine organisational success as well as the degree of competition for organisational productivity in the relevant marketplace. Nonetheless, it is the responsibility of the organization's management to concentrate on these critical areas and obtain the resources required to keep the focus until the objective has been achieved. This is, however, argued by Ebben & Johnson (2005) that if the organization misses any key success factor, it will make a huge difference for the company because there will be a difference in the competitiveness of the organization and its marketplace performance. This is the reason that management should offer a persistent focus on those areas that help the company to attain the essential resources and maintain the focus till the progress is attained.

According to Ebben & Johnson (2005), the perfect balance between environmental conditions and business characteristics of the specific organization plays a pivotal role in the competitive performance. Research on competitive performance further explores its nature by stating that “those characteristics, conditions or variables that when properly managed, can have a significant impact on the success of an organization competing in a particular industry.” The

important attainment features are valued as their contribution, which are essential to get the desired outcomes; however, the ultimate success of the outcomes can be achieved only with the comprehensively designed objectives (Winer, 2004). The traditional definition does not explain the level of success. Still, the ultimate goal of success factors is the massive success that leaves a mark on corporate management; hence, the success indicator of the organization helps in the strong positioning in the particular industry.

2.2.2 Key Success Factors: Significance, Identification

The organizational success factors' credibility is very high due to its mass usage in the field of research but in the contemporary era, key success factors research are reliable to support in terms of understanding problems and numerous potential aspects, which strongly affect the outcomes. It is evident from the literature that numerous studies are carried out to understand the practicality of success factors. However, there are still ambiguities about the nature of objective knowledge of success factors as researchers are still not sure about the application of key success determinants to resolve real-world issues. Likewise, the research by Alon (2004), elucidates the importance of knowledge by stating that "knowledge can only be understood if it is located, embodied and linked to experience in the life-world, culture, and power." The examination of success determinants and, as a result, their influence on management problems are contextualised by this coupling of information to real-life settings (Aliouche & Schlenrich, 2011).

According to Hoffman & Preble (2004) the management and identification of critical success factors or key success factors is a practical implementation tool for the categorization of success factors in the organization. In the context of hospitality, key success factors are researched by various scholars like Vignali (2001) who employed mixed method. In stage one, the author conducted a survey and in the second stage, he interviewed restaurant owners to find out what variables were crucial to their success. Another study by Camillo et al. (2008) who used a case study method to categorise key success indicators for self-governing eateries in California. Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) also applied questionnaires and interviews-based method to align crucial success elements and client perceptions in the "budget hotel segment" within China. Aliouche & Schlenrich (2011) employed interviews in depth and focus group discussions with owners and managers of medium and small hotels to categorize the success factors coherently. After the completion of categorization of vital success factors, it is crucial

to examine the intensity of the importance of every factor to the dissimilar procedures exemplified in the production of delivery of services and goods.

2.2.3 Key Success Factors and Sustainable Competitive Advantage

From the given research on the concept of success factors, it is evident that these factors seem to have a basic crux. According to Esteves (2004) key success factors are attained from the organizational internal and external environment and can be related to the products, processes in organisations, people and skills that are critical to establishing an organization's competitive advantage. It shows that key success factors have prime focus on those specialized areas of the organization that allows them to attain a huge competitive edge and they become key priorities in allocating resources and effort. Thus, considering this alignment between success factors and the organizational competitive edge, the thesis makes use of the value chain approach proposed by Porter (1980;1985) in the next section of this chapter.

Formulating competitive advantage of the firm is determined as critical success factors or key success factors for the small or growing business firm. Stated by Vignali (2001), the progressive competitive advantage can be achieved if the business person formulates the competitive advantage that is sustainable for the upcoming future.

Figure 7 Competitive Strategy

Source: Salesreadiness.com

Figure 7 above illustrates the mechanism of a competitive advantage in a business.

This is also true that in the prospect of new business, it is unlikely to attain success easily; however, the existing market competitors defend themselves from the new entrants through sustainable competitive advantage. Given the topic of the study, market entry is the first critical phase in formulating competitive advantage and is persistently important throughout the business life cycle. In the franchising market, successful market penetration need new entrants to formulate an effective strategy that can act as the entry section, permitting the new franchising business to earn revenue and attain market share. A relationship is developed amidst various strategies in order to remain competitive. Strategy based on providing sustainable competitive edge might help the new franchising business with that market entry segment that facilitates the creation of the new franchise in the marketplace.

Rarely, some scholars like Hoffman & Preble (2004) argue that franchising business compete with the exiting business ventures on price factor. The reason is explained as business entrepreneurs usually favor and other competitive approaches rather than competing on price strategy. The research by Aliouche & Schlenrich (2011) stated that opening a fast-food franchise might be an example of the typical entrepreneurial business but competing in this industry requires entrepreneurs to focus on the quality instead of focusing only on prices. According to Vignali (2001) formulating competitive advantage focuses on three crucial features: customer value, improved value of the product/services and inimitable business model. This is important to state here in that the primary factor is customer value because competitive advantage must be able to provide customer value in terms of low price with speedy delivery and quality products or similar other attributes. The improved value of the product and services is observed by the customers. As argued by Aliouche & Schlenrich (2011) this is also important in that whatever the business offers, the most important part is that the business tactics are unlikely to be copied by other market rivalries. This is argued by authors in that those franchising businesses that have difficult business tactics are unlikely to be defeated by market rivalries and are regarded as sustainable competitive advantage as shown in Figure 2.1 above.

Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) furthermore added that competitive advantage can be attained by utilizing Porter generic strategies that consist of cost leadership, differentiation and focus strategy in the franchising sector.

Figure 8 Porter's Generic Strategies

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a diagram of Porter's Generic Strategies. Please contact the author for further information.

Source: Calltheone.com

Figure 2.2 above illustrates Michael Porter's generic approaches that consist of cost - leadership strategy, differentiation, cost focus and differentiation focus.

Accordingly, Aliouche & Schlenrich (2011) also argued that the organisations said to attain sustained competitive advantage that implements "value creating strategy" and which are unlikely to be copied by the market competitors nor are they able to imitate the advantages of the business strategy.

Eser (2012) further posits that the business strategy improves the organizational competitive advantage if it is in accordance with and improve the ongoing process that includes the organisations' ongoing efforts to gain a favourable position in resources that give market positions and, as a result, achieve higher financial productivity in the marketplace. Another study by Esteves (2004) confirmed that the organizational marketing strategy provides competitive advantage to the firm, which comes from either organizational assets or resource legacies like brand equity, organizational brand image and perceived quality. These attributes are acquired by the organization over a period. It is further postulated that a market driven firm has higher abilities to understand, attract and sustain valuable consumers (Esteves, 2004)

In the prospect of franchising business, as these firms operate outside the home country business venture, it is important for them to attain a set of goals that help them achieve critical success factors in a particular time frame. This formulating goal to attain success factors is the primary step in the prospect of the franchising business. This is further stated by Eser

(2012) that the business organization must also perform well in certain primary areas that are unique to the organizational mission and industry in which it functions. Critical success factors or key success factors are thus those key areas that require the organization to perform well in those areas and help them accomplish their mission and long-term goals. Once the business venture is successful in identifying these success factors, they act as the point of reference for the entire organization.

Usually, success factors are general and are unlikely to be measured or observed easily because they appear to be generic and help the firm in attaining competitive advantage and position the company in the marketplace through superior activities and progressive financial performance. The link between organisational success determinants and long-term competitive advantage is clear from previous scholars' discussions on key performance indicators. The strategic dominance of the business venture in the franchising sector is seen as ascertaining that the business maintains higher financial productivity through sustainable competitive advantage in the marketplace (Esteves, 2004). A perfect fit between the organizational competitive edge and the success factors form the strong grounds for the progressive performance. Researchers like Amberg, Fischl & Wiener (2005) conclude that the concept of competitive advantage seems that the organization needs to enhance its market positioning in the particular industry as well as maintain the superior financial productivity. Although, in the prospect of success factors, it is not essential that these factors are unique for the organization but as long as they offer unique value to the customers, they make a distinction for the business when it comes to resource allocation and management. The scholars state that if the business is successfully able to manage its success factors, they result in establishing sustained competitive advantage in the market.

2.3 Franchising

The previous section of the literature review dealt with the detailed explanation of the key success factors and its application in the hospitality sector, especially in the food market. This chapter involves the detailed explanation of franchising, theories and concepts that trigger franchising, its benefits and disadvantages, risks related with franchising and finally key success factors from the franchisor and franchisee's perspectives.

2.3.1 The Franchising System

According to Kremez, Frazer & Thaichon (2019) franchising does not seem to have an established definition because different researchers have different perspectives towards it and thus, define it from their own viewpoints. Stated by Bujisic et al (2014) franchising system means when a franchisor authorises a consumer (franchisee) to sell a product with the same brand identity as the franchisor markets it in his or her own country, this is referred to as a franchising system. Another researcher Nyadzayo et al (2016) defined it as the source of privilege that has contractual nature and is given by one individual/organization to another individual/organization. However, some scholars argue that franchising is basically a source of raising funds for operating business activities, whereas Rahatullah (2014) viewed franchising as the source of distributing goods and services that are used for the business' growth and expansion.

Research has emphasized that franchising is one form of business that has made a long way into different sectors and domains since the 1800s, like the Coca-Cola brand and Singer. The business model of franchising is one model that has been used all over the world across different industries but it has gained considerable attention in fast food restaurant businesses (Norton, 2004). Franchising has been an extremely crucial strategy for the fast-food restaurants to tap into international markets like Burger King and McDonalds that are present in a number of countries worldwide and have been a major success into adopting the model of franchising. In simpler terms, franchising is one business model that enables businesses to expand their chains into other regions, other locations with no restriction on the amount of capital or managerial talent etc. (Duckett & Monaghan, 2011).

Franchising is considered to be the fastest way to expand your business chains, it is also referred to as the alternatives to company-owned units. The second benefit that it provides is to minimize the overall operational risk for the businesses worldwide. In a franchising model, the franchisor is the owner of the business concept and all the associated managerial knowledge that is considered essential to carry on with the business (Alon, 2006). It is the proven concept of the business by the franchisor; the franchisee is able to rent out that concept of the business and pay the franchise fees or rent for a specific period of time (Hoffman & Preble, 2004). There is a well-established franchise agreement that proves as a manual to clearly communicate the roles and responsibilities of all the partners involved in the deal. The franchise agreement can be established for a span of 5 to 30 years and also allows renewals to the parties (Dant, et al, 2008).

Research has emphasized that it is not necessary that the franchising deal will always be a success. There are many other elements that can pose potential risks to the business in a franchise agreement (Rob, 2002). But evidently the success rate of the franchising systems is far greater than other businesses due to the amount of shared competence and the greater economies of scale involved in the entire establishment (Gikonyo, et al, 2015). Factors such as managerial competence, brand image, brand awareness, the ambiance, the atmosphere of the franchise, the product mix and the unique marketing strategies are some of the few factors that are considered to be driving up the success of franchises in general (Mendelsohn, 2005).

Figure 9 The Franchising Model

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a diagram of 'steps to become a franchiser'. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

According to Samsudin et al (2018) franchising is the concept of marketing that is concerned with distributing goods and services and also knows that there are physical boundaries for business categories. According to international franchising system (2004), “franchise is the agreement or a license between the two legal and independent parties that allows a person or a group of people (franchisee) the right to market or service of using trademark or trademark name of another business (franchisor)”. This particular definition is viewed by scholars as most authentic and succinct definition, which is further summarized as “the granting of rights by the franchisor for the franchisee to operate their business system using a common brand and common format for promoting, managing and administrating the business”. This definition is the widely used description for franchising in research studies, thus, the present study also uses the same description of franchising for fast food sector.

Different viewpoints about franchising have encouraged business owners, entrepreneurs and scholars to follow the concept, especially in the wake of globalization. The incentives for using franchising as an entry strategy into overseas markets were examined in the globalization of

franchising studies. Amongst such studies, Rahatullah (2014) evaluated brands across the countries and determined factors that help in choosing franchising or managerial contracts for embarking on global markets. Sowunmi et al (2014) viewed the internationalization of restaurants and examined the factors that influenced the decision-making process of the franchisor and franchisee both. Another study by Dada et al (2012) studied the process of internationalization of retail business and observed the factors that influenced the choice of franchising as the source of market entry. Sowunmi et al (2014) also explored the choice of worldwide franchising and growth in developing markets, whereas Samsudin et al (2018) executed a comparison of two cultures of various franchising networks within the USA, France and Brazil. In the study of the franchising system, Rahatullah (2014) is amongst the few scholars who determined the key success factors and sought for the foreign franchisors in East Asian countries.

2.3.2 Theories of Franchising

The agency theory and resource scarcity theory underpin the majority of franchising studies. (Dada& Watson, 2013b). Resource scarcity theory is explained by Samsudin et al (2018) that franchising is the means to limit resource constraints that impede the growth of the organization in the international market. Those constraints can be related to financial and or managerial constraints. Agency theory, on the other hand, sees franchising as a way to improve the fit between the organization's and the agency's advantages.

2.3.2.1 Theory of Scarcity of Resources

The stream of literature shows that the factors behind franchising are mainly the takeover of capital, which is required for the system to develop. It is furthermore suggested that when the organization is facing hindrance in its growth and development due to the shortage of resources, it opts for franchising process. The resources can be related to financial capital, human capital and managerial skills or market knowledge. When organisations face difficulties in raising financial resources and finding skilful workers in the primary phases of franchising, they seek for someone who could help them inject financial capital and also who could share the consequential risk. Moreover, as argued by Nyadzayo et al (2016) if franchisors are able to find someone who could alleviate the limitations of money and labour requirements in the franchising system, the franchisor would also be determined in a better position to monitor and direct his activities towards the growth of the brand and overall system. Those who seek rapid growth are motivated by a desire to achieve a minimum efficient scale and build the brand name capital necessary for retail-oriented activities. Furthermore, the risk can be transferred

from the organisation to the franchisor.

2.3.2.2 Agency Theory

From the standpoint of resource-based constraints, the firm's growth is arguably more transitory and it is suggested that the franchisor would backslide to fully own organizational chains. However, the emergence of franchising and the persistence of the activity seems to have warned this position (Rahatullah, (2014). Agency theory determines the relationship between the principle and agent through a mutual agreement. Both principles (the person who delegates work) and the agent (the one who takes work) expect that they attain mutually satisfying consequences. However, it is also possible that there is an imbalance from either side of the relationship.

Those managers who are tied with fixed incomes and act as agents are likely to reduce their efforts towards the franchise outlet because they are less likely to observe any career development and or personal development opportunities at work. Even sometimes, they pursue their own interests at the expense of the principle. This situation is most likely observed when the additional incentives of the organization solely belong to the owner of the organization and employees do not attain any incentive for their efforts made towards the organization. Some academics argue that if the owner incurs monitoring costs and determines that the employee is working in the best interests of the organisation, it must be referred to as "moral hazard."

On the contrary, it is possible that the organisation is unable to ascertain that the selected worker is able to perform the task assigned and bring up the subject of "adverse selection".

Franchising is seen as the best way to reduce the likelihood of moral hazards and adverse selection because the franchising system considers the interest of the franchisor as well as the franchisee through the mutual placement of benefits from both the parties. From the viewpoint of agency theory in the franchising system, it is argued by researchers that the franchisor would enhance the value of their system operations by ascertaining efficient regulating expenses to the least possible extent. Franchising also helps in delivering the desired outcomes if employed in its hybrid form. However, Dada & Watson (2013b) suggest that franchising becomes the preferred option over owning a foreign subsidiary when the marginal cost of regulating own units exceeds the marginal cost of franchising contracts. Another study claimed that franchising has the propensity to arrive at the increased goal convergence between the principal and the agent that can be organized in the arrangement of company ownership. The franchisee is encouraged to increase the value of their own activities to the extent that he has an enduring

claim over any revenue that is raised from the operations after fulfilling the royalty fee to the franchisor. This shows that the franchising cost is preferred in those regions where the monitoring cost is relatively higher than the other regions.

2.3.2.3 Integrated View

The above-mentioned theories i.e., resource scarcity theory and agency theory have been illustrated to explain the reasons of franchising. Some scholars argue that they are competing with each other; however, others state their opinions that they are complementary to each other instead of having different perspectives (Sowunmi et al, 2014) Amongst those scholars who support this viewpoint are Samsudin et al (2018) who state their opinion that franchising is the solution to those business owners who are facing incentive issues and have enormous problems about acquiring capital resources for obliging growth. It appears from the above two theories that the resource-based theory is determined to foster the franchising system to develop and emerge during the start up phase. When franchisors realise economies of scale through the franchise network, however, they transition to the agency paradigm since the cost of managing franchise outlets becomes the primary focus. It seems adequate to state that when franchisors want to grow to foreign markets, the viewpoints of resource base seem to govern initially in the process. This integrated perspective seems to offer a complete description on why firms franchise instead of foreign direct investments or establishing subsidiaries.

2.3.3 Advantages and Disadvantages

The study conducted by Rahatullah (2014) recognized the perceived advantages of the franchise option from the perspective of franchise and stated that training facilities could help improve the chance of success in functioning business operations and is directly related to the franchisor support. This is determined as one of the greatest advantages that seems to enhance the chances of success in franchising system. Another essential attribute is a “greater sense of independence”. This perspective is perceived from the viewpoint of entrepreneurship that when a person acquires a feeling of ownership for the organization in comparison to being hired and accountable to others, being a freelancer is considered more advantageous. Consequently, it leads a business owner to choose franchising instead of exploiting employment opportunity. The third notable advantage is working under an umbrella of an “established name”. Working under a well-known and well-established brand name is said to draw more customers to a firm than attempting to break into a new market with a new concept.

Along with the above-mentioned advantages, disadvantages of franchising are also recognized by researchers. It is argued by Vahdati and Nejad (2016) that the contractual requirements of the franchising system seem to exceed the small independent businesses. With a requirement of paying royalty fees and purchase limitations, sometimes business owners do not like to choose franchising in contrast to independent businesses. According to the franchisor, the franchising system is the most favourable business strategy to expand operations in the foreign market; however, from the franchisee perspective, it is not feasible because all the capital required to set up the business are provided by the franchisee. In this regard, it may become difficult for those who have capital constraints. Hence, it is regarded by Rahatullah (2014) that the franchising system grows but risk and cost are distributed across the franchise.

The cost of monitoring is not required to a large extent as it is needed in the franchising system, from the perspective of the franchisor. In the context of franchising, the franchisee is the owner and sometimes he acts as the manager of the firm who has interest in meeting the liabilities of the franchising contract and who has exclusive interest in gaining revenue for himself and for the franchisor.

Although, the above-mentioned disadvantages highlighted the adverse consequences of the franchising system, the advantages outweigh the disadvantages. In the franchising system, the franchisor can attain economies of scale by virtue of its size and can excessively spend on marketing and promotional side of the business. With regard to international franchising, the franchisor has the advantage to spread the risk of environmental uncertainty because the franchisee has a better understanding of the local environment and can thus handle the issues that may be raised due to cultural or economic regulations of the country. Language barriers and specific geographic government policies may be factors that discourage foreign companies from choosing foreign direct investment. Even the franchisor could successfully use the knowledge skills of the franchisee in adopting the marketing strategies and promotional strategies in the foreign market. The franchisee has more knowledge about the taste and buying preferences of local consumers, which could be used by the franchisor and attain competitive advantage. However, the franchisor has the liability to stay vigilant over the quality of products in franchise system. Free riding is one of the emerging practices that is utilized with regard to the franchising system, especially in the case of a franchisee who can take the advantages of brand name irrespective of contributing to its sustainability and viability. Vahdati and Nejad (2016) observed that there may be situations where franchisees tend to increase the revenues of their shops through the reduced dependency on brand such as marketing strategies and

reducing the quality of services and decreasing the entire reputation of franchise.

2.3.4 Risks with Franchising

Same as other business ventures, franchising faces risk factors that are stated by various scholars including Rahatullah (2014) who claimed that the progress rate of the franchising system activities are exceeding those of other competing businesses. This is due to the inherited support structure in franchising, the shared knowledge and the economies of scale that are the outcomes of the association with the franchisor as well as with the identified brand name and the franchisor's marketing contribution. However, some scholars state that the market survival rate of franchising system is lower than the actual image provided by the previous literature if compared with the independent businesses. Noor et al (2018) stated that the image of viability with franchising system has also enforced banks to foster their credit acquisition processes. However, as scholars like Zhang (2015) suggest, the data representing failed franchisees may have misrepresentations because they are usually concealed by the franchisors and prevent them from intense failure in the market.

Vahdati and Nejad (2016) further argued that there were malpractices executed by the franchisor who presents information based on the productivity of franchisees and promote businesses. The studies on the ownership redirection are brought forward by various scholars (Watson et al., 2017; Covin & Wales, 2012) who presented their viewpoints about the public concerns and policy implications of the ownership activity (return of ownership to the franchisor) and investigated the likelihood of malpractices inherent in this prospect. This appears to be related to the success or failure of the franchising system. It is argued that risk is the source of motivation for the franchisees because they are the sole owners of their franchising system; and failure could lead them to the failure of the entire money invested in the business. In contrast, managers of business units are given salaries and as they do invest money, thus, they do not own any risk. There are other inter-linked risks that could cost the franchisee. These include opportunistic behaviour and freerider attitude of the franchisee. In this prospect if the franchisee is not adequately controlled and are vested with free rider behaviour. they may market low quality products and erode the brand reputation, which could harm the entire franchising system. As a result, the franchisor exerts control over the franchisee in order to reduce the risk of opportunism and to pressurise them for contract terms. This is accomplished by safeguarding the brand name and ensuring consistency in how customers perceive it. (Dada

& Watson, 2013a).

2.3.5 Internationalization of Franchising

Franchising has been used as an effective way of expanding businesses, keeping in view to maintain low costs unit-tracking mixed with reasonable access to capital for franchisors (Norton, 1988b; Bachmann et al., 2016) over time. These two elements are viewed as part of the motivation for franchising (Hoover, et al., 2003) by the researchers. Inside the USA, the home of franchising, saturation of domestic market has additionally driven American franchisors to discover the internationalization in their perspectives (Dada & Watson, 2013a). Zhang (2015) argued that despite the 2008 economic downturn, many franchisors operating around the world had continued to grow incrementally. The literature identifies two categories of risks associated with franchising worldwide. These threats are linked to operational performance, that has to do with the worldwide franchise relationship, that come with functioning in a foreign market.

2.3.5.1 Administration

According to the scholars, administrative efficiency is the most important aspect since it determines the extent to which the franchise agreement partnership allows the franchisee and franchisor to align their alternatives (Zhang, 2015). Domestic franchisors are distinguished from global franchisors by their ability to effectively display a foreign franchisee. The difficulties faced throughout the 95-tracking procedure are due to the geographic and cultural differences between the franchisor and franchisee (Dada & Watson, 2013a). Handling issues that arise as a result of the franchisee's distance from the franchisor necessitates not only the most effective potential risks and uncertainties, but also additional increases in the franchisor's monitoring cost. (Dada & Watson, 2013b). Researchers have discovered, however, that internationalisation or operating in global markets has ideal franchising arrangements due to the possible adaptability in a franchise settlement. This adaptability has been seen to contribute to the effective absorption of risks and uncertainties in the global marketplace (Sashi & Karuppur, 2002). A franchisor in a faraway location would take longer to grasp the local situation in contrast to a franchisee that can respond quickly to changes within their local trading environment. According to global franchising research in the restaurant business, growth into foreign countries that are physically near to the host country, such as the United States of America from Canada (Bachmann et al., 2016), is more appealing and deemed

franchising friendly.

The classification of countries based on their political, technical, economic, cultural, and social similarities could make standardising the advertising mix easier. McDonald's learned through their global operations that, while standardisation could save money, to be successful, the product and the price had to be adjusted to the surroundings (Vignali, 2001). The market's social, cultural, and religious values would promote product diversity, while economic variables, as well as costs imposed by competitors, would influence the rate. Countries with sophisticated infrastructure and cultural commonalities, such as the European Union nations, Japan, and neighbouring Asian international locations, are examples of countries that have used franchising to achieve greater success (Autio et al., 2013).

2.3.6 Risk Management in the Host Country

The hazards posed by the macroeconomic environment consisting of authorities' regulations, legal systems, statistics and physical infrastructure and so on increase the uncertainty in establishing the business worldwide (Noor et al., 2018). The government policies on ownership, protection of highbrow belonging rights, and repatriation of income need considerable evaluation. Franchise companies may additionally suffer from imitation due to competitors (Zhang, 2015). The volatility in the foreign exchange market is another element of risk for the franchisor. Franchises, on the other hand, enable businesses to grow internationally without putting their money at risk. This decreases the chances of currency volatility, political instability, and unstable financial circumstances in global economies (Sashi & Karuppur, 2002).

2.3.7 Fast food Franchising and Key Success Factors

Franchising is demonstrated as the engine of growth, especially in the restaurant and fast-food market. Only the United States of America has a strong global presence for more than 40% of the market's goods and services. According to Zhang (2015) the fast-food segment of the restaurant market is the main segment that expanded mainly through franchising, across the countries. The rapid growth of franchising in the United States, as well as its effectiveness in the fast-food business model, has resulted in the instant globalisation of the fast-food industry. McDonalds' fast food is the prominent example that is determined as the leader in the foreign market of franchising in the fast-food sector.

When talking about global franchising, McDonaldization is deemed as the most common trend observed around the world. Other notable examples include KFC, Burger King; Pizza Hut and Subway are amongst the most well-known names in fast-food franchising that entered into Europe from the USA and other parts of the Middle East, such as the Asian countries. The emergence of this growth in franchising fast-food sector is linked with the following factors, i) increase in the mobility of population ii) growth in urban population iii) increase in younger generation iv) increase in the number of working women are some of the notable factors that contributed towards the growth of franchising food.

2.3.8 Key Success Factors-Franchisor Perspective

One of the important major variables impacting the potential to succeed or loss of restaurant franchises, particularly in the fast-food market, is the competitive climate in which they operate. This can be achieved through the physical location of the restaurant, the area's solidity, and the ability of the fast-food chain to differentiate itself from the competition, as well as respond to growth and changes in the environment. It is argued that franchised and chain restaurants are superior to independent restaurants because they can benefit from economies of scale. Size is linked to market survival, according to research, implying that the greater the company, the simpler it is to thrive in the market.

Stated by Nakao et al (2019), for the franchised restaurant to become successful, it must have a good criteria for selecting site. The location of the business is considered as one of the essential factors for success

If there is a poorly selected site for business, it cannot facilitate the successful performance of the products and services in the market. The site selection is based on the following criteria: the density of restaurant in the nearby area, the type of businesses in the region and the disposable income of the target audience in that particular region. It is argued by Nyadzayo et al (2016) that franchised restaurants usually carry out successful market research that help them to choose new locations. On that basis, it is easier for the franchisor that it would approve or reject the site for establishing the restaurant, thereby augmenting the chances of success.

Another research by Covin, & Lumpkin (2011) was conducted to find out “why restaurants fail.” The authors found that amongst the key success factors for franchised restaurant viability and progress, it was important that they had a clear idea of their business model. In the prospect of franchising, brand and business models are already tested by the franchisor,. Thus, they do

not posit any challenges for the franchising restaurant and indeed facilitates the business. Franchised restaurants have very clear concepts that are communicated by the brand identity. People increasingly associate themselves with the specific brand that distinguishes them from any other restaurant. The franchisor keeps check over the brand quality and strength to maintain the franchise visibility. It is important to mention here that a good and clear concept conveys an image to the customers that brings in noticeable differentiation from the competition in the region to attract clientele.

Customers want to get value for their money. A well-recognized brand is linked with a certain range of products and offers them in specific price range. When the restaurant is the part of franchising system, customers have certain ranges of expectations of value whenever they visit it. In that case, if the restaurant fails to meet the customer's expectations for value, the customer is likely to choose another restaurant and will not return. Those franchising restaurants that are failed in providing a clear concept would find it difficult to stay in the market because the customers want to seek for the persistent operation that offers them value for their money. Other key success factors from the perspective of the franchisor include the excellent choice of selecting franchisees and promote good relationships with them. Covin & Lumpkin (2011) suggested that the franchisor could opt for that franchisee that share prime values and are committed to their business. The author also stated that maintaining a constructive and positive relationship with the franchisee is critical because it allows them to pursue their goals by overcoming "ongoing challenges." Excessive stress that drain relations, create resistance to major changes, misinterpreting a franchisor motive for undertaking various choices, franchisor leadership that is overly authoritarian, insensitive, or insufficient support from the franchisee to the franchisor are all common reasons for franchising sector failure, according to Covin and Miller (2014). Additionally, when giving franchises, it must take into account current government policy. These areas are vital for franchised restaurants from the franchisor's perspective; therefore, to ensure the franchising system's success, management should concentrate on these aspects.

2.3.9 Key Success Factors-Franchisee Perspective

From the perspective of the franchisee, strong financial management is regarded as one of the most important success factors for the progression of franchised restaurants. Financial management should be valued to the details by using entire operational activities, from buying right up to service. If the franchising system is not adequately controlled and run by franchisee

and there is least control on avoiding waste materials, pilfering and spoilage, it can collectively bring failure to the organization. Typically, franchisors develop procedural manuals to ensure that the franchisee has adequate control over functional areas, and they are unlikely to yield benefits and would not be able to meet the franchisor's commitment of royalties. (Alon et al, 2016).

MTSWENI et al (2018) identified the key success factors that were likely to contribute to the franchise's success from the franchisee's perspective in a study based on the South African fast-food industry. The authors were able to shed light upon both internal as well as external factors that were critical to the franchisee operating a fast-food outlet in an effective manner.

Internal factors were mostly related to managerial capacity that not only involved employee's expertise but also covered the system and other inventory controls. Then came the skills and competence of the franchisee that will ensure that there are smooth operations within the fast-food outlet. It had been highlighted that for any business to succeed in the future, it is important for the business owner to have adequate command over the business they aim to run. In this case, for a fast-food outlet, it is important for the franchisee to have some past experience in running a restaurant or a fast-food chain previously. It is important for them to have a practical understanding of the main functions and the basic know-how about the business they are entering into to be successful in the future. Moreover, it was pointed out that if adequate control systems are installed, it further helps to ensure to keep a track of the business in a timely manner that can be helpful for the business profitability as it can alert the management about the shortfalls or may even be able to tell them about the losses that can be avoided through effective monitoring.

Lastly, the study identified that the franchisee or the business manager needs to have a certain sense of style and is required to have a certain personality to be able to work for a particular franchise business altogether. If the franchisee is a perfect fit for the fast-food chain and matches up to the inner elements of the restaurant, the business is likely to succeed in the future as well. The study was also able to identify certain external factors from a franchisee perspective like the location of the restaurant and its accessibility.

The study has referred to the Attractiveness element that is rather significant for any Shopping Center, in fact it has been termed as a necessity. Thus, in the case of a fast-food restaurant, the study has highlighted that the location of the fast-food restaurant should be around some family

friendly places where there is a banking facility present or in a food court of a shopping mall or in some entertainment facility like the cinema or a place that has adequate parking to facilitate the parking of the customers' cars. The customers are extremely demanding and they do prefer their convenience to any other factor.

Accessibility is another significant factor that tends to attract customers the most. By accessibility, the authors are reflecting towards the visibility of the fast-food outlet that will bring the brand to the customer's notice and also will attract them to their business altogether. Studies from different sources seem to agree with this fact that the success or the failure of a fast-food restaurant can be both internal as well as external to the business. In a majority of the studies, the likely cause of a restaurant business failing was due to poor and ineffective management that did not let the businesses flourish for a very long time. Business managers or franchisees need to have sufficient experience in their respective fields as it only helps them to develop a practical understanding regarding the nature of the business altogether (Scarborough, et al,2008). Studies have also suggested that when adequate control and monitoring systems are installed, it enables these fast-food restaurants to keep a thorough check upon the progress of the businesses and alerts them in case of dangers or potential threats exposed to the business (Griffin & Ebert, 2006).

In terms of external factors, the location of the restaurant is quite essential for determining the success of the business in the future. There are numerous different models identified that tend to scrutinize the markets in order to pick an ideal location for the business for fast food restaurants and potentially any other retail business altogether, like the location-allocation model (Frasquet, et al, 2001). Another significant tool that is widely used for business is that of the Shopping Centre Attractiveness (SCATTR) scale that comprises of as much as 21 attributes that helps businesses to evaluate a location on the basis of attractiveness from a customer's perspective (Wong, et al, 2001). The more ideally located a fast-food restaurant is, the more likely it is to remain in business for a longer time as customers' tend to prefer those businesses that are within their reach. The ones they believe are taking care of not just their food related needs but also ensuring that they have ample parking spaces, the ambiance is quite friendly and the service is quick to facilitate the customers in a timely manner.

It is a well-known fact and has been well accepted by numerous different scholars that a fast-food outlet that is most ideally managed, thoroughly taken care of in terms of inventory and other managerial controls and is ideally located for it to be easily within the access of the customers, are the ones that last for years. Due to poor management and a lack of attention given

to the planning of the site location only contributes to long term losses for any business; not just restaurants (Zimmerer, et al, 2008). The customers enjoy those places that are set according to their tastes, where they feel welcome by the management and where they can feel at ease and comfort during each of their visits. One bad customer experience can cost a lot to the fast-food franchise and, therefore, it is extremely important to keep all these critical success factors in mind before planning out for the business (Strydom, 2014).

Managerial competency, ambiance, personnel skills, relationship marketing, an unique selling points for clients, staff management and convenience are other critical success aspects from the franchisee's perspective, which will be explored in the following portion of this chapter.

2.3.10 Critical Success Factors / Key Success Factors

Several researchers have identified essential success elements in the hospitality sector, as well as a few proposed models for success in certain industries. A paper on the essential success elements in UK budget hotel operations and UK corporate hotels was released by Ling and Mansori (2018). Mohd Sidik (2014) investigated Irish hotel groups' performance measurement practises. He uncovered some key success aspects when exploring, including better strategy, expenditure management, client loyalty, competition monitoring, first-class product, top provider, personnel performance, body of workers welfare, group of workers improvement, and team of workers control. Service quality, profitability, financial tracking, customer loyalty, and staff control were identified by Monge et al. (2017) as key success factors of their balanced scorecards for overall performance in SMEs. In their paper 'branding: fantasy or reality in the hotel business,' Melnyk et al. (2009) identified region, marketing, brand management, and human resource control as key success factors.' In their research, Nassaji (2015) found some crucial success elements, including customer loyalty, profitability, and efficiency. Customer courtship management, use of technology, competitive advantage generated from centre expertise, and higher service contributions were highlighted as significant success drivers by Nyadzayo et al. (2016). Nyadzayo et al (2016) found a few critical achievement aspects in optimising networks in order to improve the company enterprise, such as personnel management and market positioning, in a case study of a hotel prospective. Physical goods, high-quality service, cost, merchandising, and location are all significant fulfilment components for budget hotels in China, according to Nassaji (2015).

The restaurant sector, as a subset of the larger hotel industry, shares some critical success elements, according to specific writers (Nyadzayo et al., 2016; Nassaji, 2015). Those key

success factors include the following: management of prices, client loyalty, tracking opposition, marketplace positioning, product first-rate, carrier exceptional, teamwork efficiency, customer retention, profitability, sales prices, and location. Nevertheless, because the hospitality industry is larger and thus has different key success factors that have less to do with the restaurant industry, the current study employs key success factors from the overall restaurant sector in the pursuit of fast-food chains.

Only a few studies have looked at restaurants as a whole; others have looked at specific types of restaurants that fall into the broad categories. An example of this instance is when, Xu (2012) looked at Chinese restaurants in the full-service restaurant category, whereas Nassaji (2015) looked into eateries in the casual dining category. Zhang (2015) researched on quick provider restaurants and Vahdati and Nejad (2016) studied fast food restaurants.

Zhang (2015) examined important success elements and vital success inhibitors on Irish restaurants. These were non-public participation, team worker education and welfare, food high quality, carrier high quality, price for money, advertising and marketing, and benchmarked best practises. Vahdati and Nejad (2016) proposed a version with important success elements for independent eating places suggesting private features, resource allocation, clean seen idea, wonderful positioning in the market, convenient vicinity, enough demand turbines, equipped employees, true economic control, meals-high-quality, and provider of first-rate services as among them. Zhang (2015) proposed a version with important fulfilment factors in the 'why restaurants fail'; these include advertising, first-class products, manager's non-public features, staff performance and training, nicely defined concept, place and consumer management. Essential success elements for the food service business, notably restaurants are sales incentive programme, adaptation based on location and service according to Nyadzayo et al (2016).

The review of the literature highlighted a number of essential success elements for the hospitality industry, especially restaurants. However, there may be inconsistency among the identified factors, and less emphasis has been placed on the fast-food market. Based on previous research, the key success factors for fast-food chains are presented in the following section. Numerous authors who have researched restaurants have identified these factors. They take on the client's point of view.

2.4 Product Mix

Research has shown that even an amazing place cannot conquer a bad product blend in terms of making a restaurant an achievement or a failure (Mohd Sidik, 2014). According to Richardson & Aguir (2004) consumer expectations are shifting in the aftermath of healthy food and fast food. Consumers today want fresh vegetables and chemical-free components, among other things. There is a continuous increase in the need for a more diverse menu, including vegetarian options and the usage of either Kosher or Halal meat/ingredients. Successful operations have been discovered to have operators who're conscious of the evolving client needs, at the same time as preserving the central concept of a particular restaurant. McDonalds launched new healthy alternatives in the UK in the form of fruit bags tailored for children to consume as snack packs, pasta salad to cater for their older population as well as corn on the cob alongside the regular chicken meals and burgers (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014). This in turn, aided in the modification of the menu by the replacement of unpopular items amongst the consumers with the addition of “trendy” new alternatives. Most writers highlight product mix as a factor influencing customer choice while visiting a restaurant or fast food chain in the literature cited in table six. As a result of the investigation, the following hypotheses for verification and confirmation are proposed:

Hypothesis 1: A key success factor within the fast-food restaurant from the customer perspective is Product mix. (Full details of hypothesis development are discussed in the methodology chapter in Chapter 4)

2.5 Convenience

According to Nyadzayo et al (2016), a restaurant's physical location is a critical aspect that influences its successful outcome. In their studies, Singh and Masaku (2014) cited that the density of fast meals chains in a place, have an influence on the achievement or failure of a fast-food market. This has a robust relationship with competitive forces in the market, as a fast meals outlet in a densely populated region may also have a huge number of market competitors; therefore, the marketplace proportion for each fast meal might reduce, ultimately causing some fast foods to shutdown. A restaurant's accessibility and visibility are factors that are linked to its convenience and location. A position on the second floor, for example, may not be as successful as one on the ground floor. The reason for this is that many customers may believe they are spending less time at ground level (Parsa, et al., 2005).

Disposable serving, cutlery, and packaging materials have become more popular as a result of technological advancements and changing customer needs. For the consumer, this has improved the efficiency of using restaurant products (Zhang, 2015). According to researchers, convenience is determined as the most influential factor when it comes to the customer's interest in visiting food outlets. This shows that convenience is a contributing factor in making a food restaurant success or failure. Convenience means the restaurant facilitates its customers through its quick services. Other scholars like Mohd Sidik (2014) linked convenience with the location, hours of operational activities and the speed of delivering service; however, it may vary across the food restaurants. Nevertheless, convenience is observed as the influential factor for making a purchase decision. In the fast-food services sector, convenience is usually considered as a competitive advantage aspect since clients in this segment want to receive their orders as soon as they place them, or make payments at the point of sale.

Now it is not necessary that convenience means the same for all across all business domains and different business settings in the retail industry. For some, convenience may refer to the centrality of the facilities or the fast-food restaurant's location that may be considered a crucial element for the success of the business. This central location can mean a lot to the customer and can play a significant role in attracting them to a given trade area. It is considered that every retail location is likely to have its own unique attributes with respect to the demand it gets which is based upon the store outlets present in that location by ensuring that the offerings are in line with the requirements of the market as well (Jaravaza & Chitando, 2013). The centrality of a retail location can comprise of many different aspects like the availability of a banking facility, other outlets or retailers present in the vicinity, entertainment facilities, supermarkets etc. that may offer some potential advantages to the consumer in terms of shopping experience (Wong, et al, 2001). All these added facilities can largely act as a pull factor for the consumers to attract them towards a fast-food franchise as well.

Research has highlighted that consumers tend to prefer those localities where they can find everything matching up to their preferences as they do not normally go to one place for a single thing, it will be a bonus if they find other facilities in the same location. Studies have shown the likelihood of more consumers getting attracted to such locations that are offering clusters or different varieties of retail outlets that are most commonly found within the boundaries of a shopping centre. The consumer traffic is comparatively more at these locations that are not

limited to just fast-food outlets but they have other retail establishments to offer as well; for example, like within a strip mall area where there may be other competitive offerings available for the customer (Shaw, 2009).

Researchers continue to emphasize upon the central location that tends to support the assumption that consumers are likely to prefer the closest available store or fast-food outlet that is present at some high growth areas altogether (Tayman & Pol, 2011). From the previous studies it can be well concluded that convenience is observed as an essential factor in the fast-food market; thus, the following hypothesis is proposed for addressing them as the part of attaining objectives.

Hypothesis 2: Convenience is the key success factor for determining the success of the fast-food restaurant from the customer perspective

2.6 Employee Competence

Another key success factor identified through the studies by Monge et al (2017) and Mohd Sidik (2014) are employees' competences. This key factor can be derived from training labour force in addition to establishing personal relationship with customers and a variety of workers. The food enterprise is a labour-intensive industry and the linkage between customers and personnel is important.

Although, there is an increasing trend observed in limited customer and employee interaction; however, still customers want to be handled by employees of the fast-food businesses with positive attitudes from employees. This relationship between the customer and the employee is critical to the overall success of the business. Customers make their choice based on previous experiences and interactions with employees of fast-food restaurants. From the previous literature, employee competence is determined as important factor for the overall customer experience within the restaurant. Employee competence is mentioned in existing literature as an important element of the quality service in a restaurant. The capacity to relate to consumers in a polite, orderly, and effective manner communicates to the customer a great service experience. (2015 Zhang). It is critical for marketers to consider a brand's customer perception Berry (2000). The following hypothesis is, therefore, developed.

Hypothesis 3: Employee competence is the key success factor for determining the success of fast-food restaurant from the customer perspective

2.7 Price

Usually, customers lack the exact knowledge about the prices of various brands but they usually have generic ideas about the brands; for example, if they are expensive and or cheaper than the competing brands in the market (Monge et al., 2017). The perceived price is demonstrated as one of the essential attributes that affects the consumers' purchase decision as well as determining the reason for considering a specific restaurant. Mueller & Kleiner (2004) suggested that if the customers are not satisfied with the characteristics of the taste, cleanliness and the expenses in their choices and the patterns of eating out, but they are agreeing to spend more on what they perceive it as the quality content; this means that for them, quality is more important than price. However, others like Nijmeijer et al (2013) argued that in various instances, consumers choose those products that are relatively less costly as compared to the market rivalries. This translates that, although price maybe less important than the quality of the product it, however, is still considered as one of the important attributes in determining the choice of customers. Price is established as one of the critical aspects in the restaurant company, although being less important than employee competence in prior studies.

Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed based on the literature review:

Hypothesis 4: Price is a key success factor for determining the success of fast-food restaurant from the customer perspective

2.8 Atmosphere

Because customers do not spend much of their time in the restaurant the atmosphere of the restaurant sometimes seems less important in the prospect of fast-food franchising. Even the majority of the fast-food franchises are based on "Take away" bases where customers collect their orders and leave the premises of the restaurant. Usually, when the customers make choices, the atmosphere seems to have least importance (Noor et al., 2018); yet, cleanliness of the outlet, its physical appearance, colours and branding organization will be those elements that primarily attract the customer's attention towards the restaurant. If the restaurant is successfully able to maintain these elements, they can significantly contribute to earning the brand loyalty of the customers to that specific outlet.

Ottenbacher et al., (2009) found that customers do not accept a poorly maintained environment of fast-food restaurants. Another study by O’Gorman (2009) concluded that such restaurants are classified as sub-standards and do not appeal to customers. On the other hand, those customers that have good ambience are able to attract customer’s attention and constitute high levels customer loyalty as compared to the one that had poor quality for cleanliness. Marketing scholars have recognized that if customers have increased stimuli for the physical environment of the restaurant, their purchase intentions are significantly influenced and, in return, the sales revenues of the outlet increase accordingly. This means that at the point of buying, if the physical stimuli influence their entire decision process, then the activity of establishing and maintaining impactful atmosphere should be one of the top priorities in creating a marketing strategy of the firm (O’Gorman, 2009).

Researchers like Monge et al., (2017) claimed that the impact of the environment in the service industry has a great influence on attracting customers to the restaurant because in such cases, services are produced and consumed at the same time; therefore, this part of the restaurant constitutes an important factor in the viability of the restaurant and its patronage. Noor et al (2018) noted that if the restaurant makes an “atmospheric planning”, it can make a huge difference in the business’s’ long term failure and or success. The literature review shows that although the atmosphere might be less important than the price factor; however, it still has importance in the restaurant industry. In particular, franchising is profoundly influenced by the atmospheric strategy in various circumstances. Thus, the following hypothesis has been developed.

Hypothesis 5: From the customer's perspective, the atmosphere is a vital success factor in determining a fast-food restaurant's success.

2.9 Managerial Experience

Customers are not the only factor in the restaurant industry's success. A stream of the relevant literature suggests that the efforts go a long way before establishing a final product and operating it in the market. In order to operate successfully and stay in the business, there are certain factors that must be ensured by the company and should be given specific consideration. The operational dimension of the restaurant has profound influence on the viability of the restaurant. This is further demonstrated by Ottenbacher et al. (2009) in their study "why businesses fail," in which the authors concluded that the failure and success of restaurants are

influenced more by internal factors than by external factors such as weather, social and political environment. The authors identified that the factors such as the restaurant concentration in a specific locality, the size of the functions and the managerial attributes have significant roles in deciding the restaurant's success or failure.

In addition, other elements include the impact of the owner and manager relationship, knowledge of and the practice of relationship marketing, skills, determination, and passion of the franchisor and the manager to run the business are influential factors that have profound influences on the successful operations of the business in the restaurant market. Nevertheless, organized financial planning is essential in the successful operations of the business. Many restaurants have failed as a result of poor managerial activities, poor financial organisation, and poor record keeping, particularly in accounts, as well as a lack of access to critical data and information. This is argued by Pizam & Shani (2009) that new restaurants increasingly find challenges in organizing market changes and increased growth factors like technological advancements.

Usually, when they do not have adequate experience in following the market turbulence, they face numerous challenges. However, Quinn & Alexander (2002) argued that it is observed in the context of franchising business that they are better able to cope with the market changes and the economies of scale protect them from failure linked with financial limitations, whereas the experience they carry with themselves to the franchise market allows them the ability to read the market conditions and evaluate competition (Rahatullah, 2014). A range of scholars affirmed that the franchises have better coping abilities as compared to the individual business units for evaluating the market conditions due to adequate resources such as tools, instruments, capital resources and labour resources for research and development (Rahatullah, 2014; Roberts-Lombard, 2009). Nevertheless, franchises are in better positions to invest in the resources such as continuous marketing and as a result, they gain market shares.

2.10 Concept

All the successful fast-food franchises have been found to have core emphasis on the clear notion that regulates their activities and provides them with distinction and competitive edge in the market. This is illustrated by scholars (e.g., Roberts-Lombard, 2009) that the restaurant can be easily closed if it does not focus on one area or tries to offer all things to all customers. It means that on such occasions, restaurants implement strategies that are weak and are unable to bring competitive advantages to them. It is important that the brand and the theme of the

restaurant is clear to customers and offer success that is required to build the brand power in the market. Brand power has an essential role in defining customer purchasing choices. The business concept needs to be clear to its customers that even some scholars like Samsudin et al (2018) argue that the concept of the restaurant is even more important than the quality of the food service. A well-defined business strategy is assumed to increase client patronage at specific eateries.

2.11 Franchising Brand Building

Establishing a strong brand equity is essential for franchising, depending on the association between that of a franchisor and franchisee where it is crucial to co-promote brand equity and customer satisfaction. According to Samsudin et al (2018) brand awareness, brand image and brand characteristics are essential for the franchising market as consumers are distinct from each other based on the range of competing brands, consequent upon the decisions that eventually engender profits, sales growth and survival (Sashi & Karuppur, 2002)

The knowledge of brands constitutes two factors which establish the part of the memory that customers hold when they recognize a specific brand, brand awareness and brand image. The conceptualization of brand information through memory is essential, considering that brand awareness constitutes brand recognition and brand recall performance. According to the scholar's brand recognition is related to the customer's ability to approve a previous experience with the product using the brand as the hint, whereas brand recall is referred to as the customer's ability to recall the brand when they are provided with a certain product category. In the fast-food market, brand awareness has a significant role because as stated by Sashi and Karuppur (2002) brand awareness has a positive influence and improves the brand relationship that customers exhibit towards their preferred fast-food products (2002).

Similarly, brand image is the perception of the brand that is exhibited by relationships, which are rooted in the customer's memory. Brand relationships are determined as the additional information that is linked with the brands in the customer's memory and include the meaning of the brand. In the context of the fast-food market, brand image is referred to as the accumulated emotional perceptions, ideas or symbolic behaviour that customers link with restaurants.

Another important element is brand attributes that are referred to as the physical composition of the product such as all the ingredients needed to manufacture the product, whereas non-physical attributes are referred to as price, packaging and the visual appearance of the product.

These attributes are discussed in the previous section with regard to their importance to the fast-food franchising restaurant; however, literature suggests that these brand attributes help in building brand images.

Another essential element linked with the fast-food franchise branding is its products-related attributes such as taste, texture of the products and the quality factors. These attributes help consumers to differentiate the brands in the market. The distinction between the products is conveyed openly by making comparisons with the market rivalries attributes and implicitly stating their competitive advantage. This is true in that the context of the franchising system, both direct and indirect elements of the brand attributes and its market positioning are key to ascertain the continuous consumption of the product (Sedera et al 2004).

By brand awareness the fast-food restaurants are basically reflecting towards the strength of a particular franchise brand that is signifying the quality of the product and services as well. Brand image is without a doubt a significant aspect in a fast-food restaurant businesses and especially when it is carefully and effectively communicated through advertising and through efficient brand-building capabilities. All these factors are collectively responsible for influencing the overall growth in their venues of fast-food businesses altogether (Dick et al, 1996). Influence of a brand can be direct as well as indirect; for example, letting out subtle elements around the fast-food brand that can help customers to associate with it in an effective manner.

In a study carried out in South Africa, it was found out that the customers who are likely to get attracted to fast food restaurants, belonging to low to medium socio-economic classes, are mostly influenced through media advertising such as when they watch the advertisements on Television or come across as a deal over social media etc. Television advertising is still considered to be an effective and a rather more influential medium of establishing greater brand awareness among customers in the fast-food businesses (Van Zyl, et al, 2010).

As previously mentioned, price is an important attribute for the fast-food franchising; it is not a denying fact as stated by Schlosser (2001) that price helps consumers to perceive the quality of the products and this perception leads them to establish the brand in their minds. Research shows that those companies that have made price promotions on high quality products have considerably taken market share away from “similar priced quality tier brands and lower tier brands”. Those fast-food franchising outlets that have low tier brands with price promotion for

their products are unable to take any market share from those higher tier brands in the market that have robust quality and price strategies.

In conclusion, brand awareness, brand image, brand attributes and pricing as well as promotional strategies are essential elements for fast food franchise outlets because these elements help consumers to differentiate between the ranges of competing products, which eventually affect the sales growth of the products. In addition, in accepting the significance of how the customer is related to a product or service of a specific brand through brand awareness, the organization identifies the requirements for the consistent provision of higher quality products in order to enhance the customer loyalty. This results in superior revenue streams and the expense of attaining new consumers will be decreased. As a result, it is also hypothesized in the current study that:

Hypothesis 6: Brand awareness, brand image, brand attributes and promotion and revenue growth have positive relation with each other in the fast-food franchised outlets.

2.12 Barriers in Franchising

The researchers argue that franchising is always progressive as the system includes the elements of risk (Sashi & Karuppur, 2002). Nevertheless, as argued by Schlosser (2001) the progressive rate of franchising is superior as compared to the other competing businesses in the market due to two important elements: shared competence and economies of scale. However, this situation may not be always correct in a way that there are some studies that concluded that the exact performance of franchising is sometimes not revealed by franchisors, and hence the whole truth is uncovered. Those units that are unable to make any profit are usually resold or even re-purchased by the franchisor, re-branded or even sold to a third party.

Various elements could make issues for the franchising system. According to Sedera et al. (2004) a franchising association could be similar to the partnership; however, the relationship is more like employee relationship with an employer. Here, this can make the relationship lose balance and deteriorate the power distribution between the parties, the franchise and the franchisor.

On some occasions, it is observed that franchisees are forced intentionally by the franchisor to make expensive changes at very short notice and this is not essential, in that this step is carried out in the best interest of the franchisee. However, it is usually executed in the interest of the chain. The elements like the country's business rules, economic situations, regulations, taxation

etc. have all proved as the potential barriers for the franchising system. Sedera et al (2004) argued that one of the prime elements for the success of the franchising system is to find a skilful franchisee; however, this may not be very easy for the franchisor because there are various criteria for selecting the franchisee such as, business experience, financial power, local market information that could affect the choice of the franchisee. Hence, to find a successful franchisee is sometimes difficult by the franchisor, creating one of the potential barriers for the franchisor.

A study conducted by Monge et al (2017) revealed that the barriers for a franchising system can be explained by the utilization of various growth stages. The scholars found 3 stages and 10 stages, but five of them are quite important: i) hatchling i.e., creating the business before franchising, ii) nestling is the commitment and devotion with the franchising, iii) fledging is the recruitment of franchisee and instant growth to access economies of scale, iv) adult is the maturity of franchising and v) internationalization is concerned with completely internalizing the business in an international country. Although, the research concludes that it is not essential that all franchise chains manage to move through all these stages, it is possible that chains may get stuck in one of the stages due to potential growth barriers. The barriers like building concepts for the business, attaining customers and providing services, refining format, copying and testing format and acquiring good franchisees are some of the notable elements that could make issues for the growth of the franchise.

2.13 Expand the Exposition

2.13.1 Price:

In order to understand the behaviour of consumers, it is believed that price is a crucial component to consider. It may be described as the amount of money or time the client spent or sacrificed in order to get the goods or services. In order to persuade clients to purchase from a certain brand, it is an effective and convincing technique. According to Pride and Ferrell, the price of a product is a tool that informs buyers about the value of the product. Customers often evaluate the worth of a product or service based on the price that is being given. It is common in the restaurant sector for prices of items on the menu to differ from one establishment to another. Customers may create internal reference pricing in the restaurant business as a result

of the fierce rivalry in the industry. Only a few research have looked at the relationship between pricing and customer satisfaction as well as behavioral intentions to return to a store(Montagu, 2002). The researcher believed that the price was a significant predictor of consumer satisfaction in their study. Customers should do a comparison between their current payment and their expectations, determining if the real compensation is more or lower than what they anticipate to be needed, the authors said. His research revealed that 62% of students feel that the most important factor in deciding whether or not to eat out at a certain restaurant is the price of the food and beverages. In addition to this, the researcher discovered a clear correlation between pricing and consumer happiness. Customers who are certain that they are receiving a superior-quality product or service are more likely to remain loyal over time. It has been suggested that consumer satisfaction is positively influenced by the perceived price. Customer types that are willing to spend a higher price in the restaurant industry are those who believe the product or service provides more value in terms of characteristics. The perceived price, according to several researchers, is an important factor in determining consumer repeat purchasing behaviour (Berry et al., 2010).

2.13.2 Variety of food:

The term "variety of food" may also refer to "variety of menu." It was shown in the majority of research that the variety in cuisine has a significant impact on a patron's opinion of the restaurant environment and has generated a perception that has an impact on customer satisfaction and repeat restaurant patronage. When it comes to the restaurant sector, the accessibility of a diverse range of goods and services is critical since it enhances the possibility of repeat patronage among those who desire diversity. Another researcher demonstrated that sandwiches with various fillings would provide some variation in flavour, however the study on consumption of eight sandwiches with different fillings suggested that it would provide the consumers with the greatest amount of variety in taste (Grünhagen, Dant and Zhu, 2012).

2.13.3 Brand loyalty:

A deeply held commitment to re-purchase or re-patronize a preferred product/service in the future, resulting in repetitive same-brand or same-brand-set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts that have the potential to cause switching behavior, is defined as brand loyalty (also known as customer retention). The study examined brand loyalty using the three aspects of brand loyalty that have been proposed: affective/emotive loyalty,

cognitive/attitudinal or evaluative loyalty, and behavioral loyalty. First and foremost, emotional loyalty is defined as a feeling of adoration or a tendency to conform that is more strongly expressed in favor of a brand than it is in favor of its competitors on the market. The second kind of brand loyalty is cognitive/evaluative brand loyalty, which is a combination of the first two. The third method to brand loyalty is based on a person's behavioral attachment to a certain brand. When it comes to the services sector, the notion of brand loyalty is significantly more relevant, especially for those that offer services with minimal differences and compete in a dynamic environment, such as those in the fast food business. In order to increase market share and revenues, restaurants use defensive marketing methods in order to build brand loyalty among their customers (Nyadzayo, Matanda and Rajaguru, 2018).

2.13.4 Customer satisfaction and brand loyalty:

Customer satisfaction is defined as evaluative assessments made by customers regarding particular products/services and their purchase decisions. Customer satisfaction may be described as an overall evaluation of a product or service based on customer interactions with it. According to Shin et al., (2015) the quality of the product, the service, the pricing, the atmosphere, and the location all impact consumer happiness. In addition to making repeat purchases and becoming loyal consumers, pleased customers are more positive in their recommendation of items to other customers and less price sensitive than dissatisfied customers. Customer satisfaction is very important in any sector, but it is especially important in the restaurant industry. The outcomes of the research revealed that the intention of a visitor to return is associated with their level of satisfaction with the services provided to him or her. According to their findings, consumers' happiness with fast food restaurants is positively connected with their desire to return to the business. Many researchers have agreed with Han and Ryu that increasing customer happiness is necessary in order to increase the number of visits to restaurants, since pleased customers are more likely to return. This is a notion that has been supported by many studies.

2.13.5 Corporate Social Responsibility

CSR is widely regarded as a valuable tool that helps all parties involved in the food and beverage industry, including stakeholders, shareholders, and communities. Customers assess not just the quality of the food and service they get when eating, but also the CSR practices that they see and participate in. In exchange, the favorable experience provides a competitive

advantage. Customer happiness and loyalty are increased as a result of businesses' ethical activities. Integrity and pricing fairness are closely associated with ethical business operations, as is transparency. Many studies have shown a favorable relationship between justice, customer happiness, and loyalty, and current research has discovered that philanthropic corporate social responsibility has a good influence on both consumer satisfaction and loyalty as well as on the bottom line

The concept of ethical responsibility comprises the spectrum of acts that are permitted or prohibited by society. Within the legal limits, it complies with expectations of what customers, workers, the community, and stockholders think to be fair and equitable in the marketplace. As described by the author, customers have judged the value of a good brand in both legal and ethical ways in order to determine its worth. The brand has a significant influence not only on people who purchase it, but also on the whole society in which it is distributed. Customer satisfaction and loyalty have been examined in a number of research in relation to the economic responsibility component of the CSR dimension and in franchising. The CSR component of economics has a favourable impact on the purchasing decisions of customers. The study discovered a favorable relationship between economic accountability and corporate social responsibility (CSR) and consumer happiness and loyalty. The characteristic of economic CSR is significantly connected with consumer happiness and brand loyalty, as seen in the chart below (Perrigot, Oxibar and Déjean, 2013). Previous research has also shown that legal CSR has a good influence on consumer happiness and loyalty as well. Customer satisfaction and loyalty were shown to be positively associated with compliance with consumer security and privacy legislation, presumably because consumers place their trust in businesses that conduct themselves in line with the law.

2.14 Key Success Factors Varies Between the Countries

This is argued by scholars that key success factors may not remain the same in each country as they differ from country to country and even from industry to industry (Monge et al., 2017). According to Schlosser (2001) geographical area is one of the key success factors for the success of the franchising outlet. Various studies have been conducted on this issue and Mueller and Kleiner (2004) found that the execution of key success factors does not vary between the developing and the developed nations, but there are some irrefutable variations between the nations that make considerable differences.

Although, this is true that key success factors even differentiate between country to country

and even varies between business firms in the same industry, the research by Mueller and Kleiner (2004) argued that if the business wants to gain competitive advantage, this can be done by developing the key success factors. There are considerable advantages for the managers to implement the key success factors approach in the business strategy because in this way they can make notable variations between the industries. Nonetheless, key success factors facilitate managers in illustrating which factors must be considered by the managers and to what extent. Similarly, they are what work best as the measurement for the managers to recognize organizational situations. Although, the factors may be different between the countries and markets of the globe, key success factors facilitate businesses to move away from “easy to collect data” and help them to emphasize their attention on the most vital elements that might not be attained otherwise.

2.15 Gap in the Literature

Based on the literature reviewed, an emphasis is placed on the factors impacting the success of franchises, leaving areas that have scope for further research because they are unexplored, under-explored, or outdated.

It closes a knowledge gap in the Pakistani restaurant industry concerning critical success factors. There has been some research that identifies critical success factors or key success factors in the Restaurant Industry in general, such as Parsa et al. (2005), Bergin (2002), Bergin (2003), and so on. However, limited pwe were unable to locate any published research on the prioritisation of critical success factors based on their relevance or importance in influencing restaurant success. However, limited publish research found on the prioritisation of critical success factors based on their relevance or importance in influencing restaurant success.

"Success factors," as defined by Hitt et al. (2002), are "factors that may have a major effect on the organizational product implementation phase." A cost-benefit analysis of time and money demonstrates that achieving organizational goals is the most important part of success. At the end of a project, all phases have been completed, which is considered the pinnacle of success. This is the most often used term among project workers to indicate what went well (Eser,2012). Furthermore, the theory lacks credibility since it makes no mention of "competitiveness," which is essential when there are few players. According to Winer (2004), his notion is

relatively unique and challenging to implement in a corporation since it requires a long-term competitive position as well as major changes in the organization's environment (Remus & Wiener, 2008). To some extent, it assists in conveying the concept and highlighting that it is confined to project implementation. Furthermore, it reveals that Rockart's description of the concept was insufficient and vague.

Other definitions in the literature show that success factors meet these three key characteristics; for example, Eser (2012) defines success factors as events, situations, conditions, or activities that need special attention due to their importance. This is consistent with Alon's (2004) evaluation of success and competitive performance. Other scholars, however, such as Quinn and Alexander (2002), contend that prior definitions are useless in articulating the true general meaning of success and competition.

The term "key success factors" is used in this research in the sense described by Vignali (2001): "the limited number of areas in which gratifying results would secure an organization's successful competitive performance." The thesis utilizes concepts from Quinn and Alexander's (2002) critical definition, particularly "critical forces functioning in a given industry," to augment the definition. Many of the key arguments for utilizing this concept of "success factors" are outlined in the following paragraphs.

- i) The primary reason is because this study does not purport to exhaust all possible elements; rather, it focuses on a "restricted group of factors." In truth, the company will never benefit from all of the success criteria. Furthermore, Hoffman and Preble (2004) contend that catering to a limited number of success variables is better than catering to a large number of success factors. The various and contextually important elements assist in understanding the exact conceptualization of our independent variables.
- ii) The second reason for selecting this definition is because it explains the idea of "competitive performance," which clarifies the dependent variables.
- iii) The third reason is because it contains the specific phrases "organization" and "working in a certain industry," which add significantly to the research's contextualization.

The study's goal is to find a relationship between "essential success aspects" and "competitive performance" for "organizations operating in a certain industry." The preceding chapter discussed the research context, which is centered on franchised restaurants in Pakistan. This definition is a valuable tool for determining the sources of critical success elements while

investigating the additional features that contribute to key success factors (Esteves, 2004; Gates 2010). Quinn and Alexander (2002) advanced the categorizing of success factors by claiming that organizations have unique determinants while being in the same market. As a consequence, he identified the underlying reasons of the aforementioned variances, which are principally driven by temporal considerations, geographic location, strategic conditions, and environmental situations. To support this claim, Gates (2010) claims that success determinants may exist objectively for a long period of time in strategic planning. If the organization's overall environment changes, success criteria may need to be adjusted. In the case of internal conflict, the second possibility for change is to modify the company's environment. This study expands on Alon (2004)'s categorization and grouping of important success factor sources, which are critical for understanding the origins of success and competitive performance.

2.16 Conclusion

In order to recognize the abilities, skills and capabilities needed for the overseas franchising, a comprehensive literature review has been carried out in this chapter (Nijmeijer et al., 2013). The main purpose was to discuss those abilities that have prime importance in the international context irrespective of domestic significance. Different scholars have different opinions on what the capabilities the franchising outlet must have or develop to enhance the profitability of successful overseas operation. Based on the previous studies, it has been identified that price, quality, managerial competence, concept, product features, brand awareness, brand promotion, brand attributes, employee competence are some of the notable factors that play important roles in determining the success of the franchising system. However, it is also important for the franchisor to find out the risk barriers that could hinder the successful operations of franchising outlets in the international market.

Although, internationalization have various benefits, it is also important to note that going outside the boundaries of the home country is a strategic decision which, if not taken properly, the company can become unsuccessful and become a failure. Usually, large MNCs have adequate resources to execute suitable measures required to penetrate new markets; on the other hand, however, small companies do not have adequate resources, which increase complexities for them in the international market. Although, this does not mean that small companies cannot penetrate international markets, the research shows that only a minority of SMEs have actively shown their active attitude in going abroad and entering agreements with foreign partners as the mode of entry in the international market. However, the present study focuses on the large

multi-national organizations and evaluates their key success factors in order to attain the study objectives and address the research questions.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology and Design

3.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, we examined franchise-related literature, including theories, principles, benefits and drawbacks, risk factors, and significant success factors in the Fast Food Industry from both franchisee and franchisor perspectives. In this chapter, the research thoroughly discusses the research design for the thesis. Firstly, the discussion sheds light on the research paradigm and gradually moves to the research design, sampling, and population sizes for both the quantitative and qualitative methods used. Lastly, the chapter highlights the data collection method and the analysis procedure. The chapter also uses a variety of Tables to illustrate important points and sections of the chapter.

3.2 Research Paradigm

Marketing research predominately falls under the umbrella of the positivist paradigm. The epistemological focus of this approach helps to unearth the intensity of the credibility in relation with statements. The use of quantitative research methodologies and logical positivist approaches has a significant relationship because they are based on mathematical terms, which confirms the reliability of reality. On one hand, quantitative methodologies have been critiqued in the last few years due to their stiff nature. There are a large number of research that cited that the phenomenological paradigm has many intrinsic and extrinsic factors, which can help gauge the consumer behaviour as the experience of consumers and their nature is pronouncedly inclined toward subjectivity. For instance, the feelings and thought processes of the consumers, instead of the rigid numerical analysis, are observed to find the hidden realities. For that reason, this approach allows consumers to express their viewpoints, which makes the research more reliable and generalizable.

Moreso, there is a possibility that people have diverse experiences in the same or similar circumstances and events, and this method gives room to all consumers to unveil their thoughts, which surge the level of credibility. The ground reality is that this kind of perception and experience are not captured in the rigid paradigm of quantitative methodologies. Thus, post-modern approaches got the back of a large number of academics and researchers who have supported the extensive use of qualitative methodologies to do in-depth research.

On the other hand, there is a large body of researchers who support quantitative methods as they believe that this method brings systematic coding to advocate the phenomena of a hybrid approach to finding the latest modern trends of the market.

For triangulation, the perfect blend of numerous methodologies is favourable to see the problem with multiple perspectives. To second this statement Guion (2011), cited that researchers can use two or more than two methods to evaluate the research to find the credibility of the data. Furthermore, many researchers assume that the use of both qualitative and quantitative covers the shortcomings of the data and also enriches the research to bring more details, which is not possible with the use of the single method. Thus, there are strong pieces of evidence which show that the combined approach of qualitative and quantitative methodologies can counterbalance the weaknesses of each method. This kind of triangulation improves firmness, which strengthens the overall subjectivity of the research.

In this part of the research, interviews are used as a part of qualitative research. We selected this qualitative methodology to gather the observations of franchisees and managers in the fast food industry. Furthermore, this part predominantly answered the research questions, and qualitative methodology was presumed to be the best method to dig out this kind of information.

It has been observed that the number of franchised fast food chains is few in comparison with local restaurants, so it is significant to understand the geographical context and other related factors such as the thorough description of the situations and events along with the human interaction. This is how the research is developed, and the underlying theory creates multiple dimensions which amalgamate into wide-ranging interpretation through broad themes.

The collected data was analysed and given meaning through different interpretations. The genera of interpretative research share a part in building a theory on the perceptions and experiences rather than analysing the fixed numeric facts. The data is transformed into explanations and verbal descriptions to do the next level analysis through a different lens. The recent trend allows us to take an advantage of both methodologies to effect triangulation. Qualitative research was utilized to see the perceptions and experiences of the managers of the respective franchised fast foods through in-depth interviews in order to find the answers to the research questions. The first phase of the study was crucial as it did not find the prior literature in relation to the geographical context of the study. The research needed detailed answers to see the inspirations of franchised restaurant managers in the particular setting of the research

context. The research selected a qualitative method as the nature of this method is exploratory, and numerous researchers cited that qualitative research as a catalyst to translate their efforts into reality.

The participants' feelings and understandings are explicitly measured in the exploratory design about the particular issue. It strongly emphasizes the researcher's thorough understanding of the situation or the participants' viewpoints to create his or her meaning. This type of information can be gauged through the flexible approach of qualitative methods instead of quantitative research patterns. On the other hand, the subjective nature of the qualitative study limits the researcher's study as the perceptions and experiences are different from each other, and the sample sizes are also small in comparison with quantitative research, which is difficult to generalize on the large population. To address the shortcomings of the qualitative research, we employ the survey method to measure and confirm the primary aspects of what was excluded in the preceding qualitative segment of the study via FGD's; thus the method by which the triangulation process is carried out.

Quantitative research, according to Burns & Grove (2001), is a systematic, objective, and formal procedure of acquiring mathematical facts and figures to support the reality. It is typically conducted to "test theory" by unfolding the nature of variables and scrutinizing connections between different variables. Aliaga & Gunderson (2002) stated that a quantitative method is an approach in which the data could be analyzed through a statistical approach. The study focuses on explaining, predicting, and describing, and it is used to develop and test tested theories. This type of study methodology can handle vast amounts of data, and the results must be consistent. A quantitative study is based on a large sample that provides objective results that is generalized on the larger population. Here is the quick summary of the methods selected to answer different research questions shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 A summary of research methodologies and questions

Research questions	Methods to be used	Data Collection Methods
Q1) To identify, define and evaluate the success of franchisee/managers	Qualitative: interpretive	In-depth interviews
Q2 & Q3) To learn how franchisees/managers define, measure, and evaluate success, as well as what variables they believe contribute to a franchise's success in Pakistan.	Qualitative: interpretive	In-depth interviews
Q4) To find out what makes a franchise successful in the eyes of its customers.	Qualitative: exploratory Quantitative: confirmatory	Focus group discussion Survey questionnaire

Figure 10 The Research Process

3.3 Research Design

This is a particular framework that is needed to generally frame the research and is called research design. It describes the processes required to unearth the information, which is crucial to address the particular issue or research questions (Kent , 2007). It organizes the proposed strategy for measuring, collecting, and analysing data. Furthermore, the research assumed a descriptive and exploratory research design that is based on the steps mentioned below:

Figure 11 Research Design

Source: The Author

In this research, qualitative research is such as FDG used, for the consumers and in-depth interviews for managers or franchisees in order to achieve the objectives of the research. The qualitative method is the study that relies upon small sample sizes and unstructured designs. Exploratory research was used in the first phase of the study to clarify the issues: the important success elements for a restaurant franchise system entering the Pakistani market. The following section discusses the steps taken to explain the research process in the light of different methodologies.

3.3.1 Population and Sampling

The sample is the particular term that defines the entire population that needs to examine multiple characteristics of the population. It is not necessary that the general population always represents the whole population, but the primary reason is to unearth the views of the target population. In this study, the target population refers to items, organisations, and people who have information that meets the research's specific requirements.

Probability designs separate sampling procedures into two categories: non-probability designs and researchers. "In probability sampling design, each element of the population is said to have a non-zero chance of being selected. It is, therefore, possible in these cases to project through computation the results of the whole population. In contrast to non-probability sampling designs, the chances of selecting an element of a particular population are not known; consequently, it is not possible to compute and apply sample results, in a strict sense, to an entire population" (Dillon et al., 1990; Malhotra & Birks, 2007).

Firstly, the sampling process begins with the arrangement of the data that is gathered; this process is usually decided according to the nature of the research questions and objectives. From this point, it narrows down to the particular target population, selecting the frequency rates sampling units and a comprehensive sampling frame. Secondly, the process moves to the methods and the collection of data. Following that, the sampling size should be determined using industry norms or scientific hypotheses. As a result, it is critical to utilize the sampling technique and ultimately, the non-response bias must be identified (Dillon et al., 1990; Malhotra & Birks, 2007).

It is utterly important to explain the nature of the target population accurately in order to carry out the research process, which will be fruitful to address the identified issues. The primary aspect of defining the population in a subtle manner underpins the capability to interpret the objectives of the study accurately and highlight the important aspects of the sample. The target population should be aligned with all the pertinent elements that are explicitly and implicitly connected to the research, including all the research objectives. The researcher must find the appropriate sample which satisfies the needs of the research objectives and questions. Moreover, other characteristics of the research must be defined in order to sharpen up the exclusion and inclusion of the sample. Following the selection of the target population, the

specific frame must be chosen (Dillon et al., 1990; (Malhotra & Birks, 2007; Cooper & Schindler, 2008).

The study's target demographic is franchised restaurant customers on the one hand, and fast-food franchises in Pakistan on the other. McDonalds, KFC, Subway, Hardees, and The Burger King are just a few of Pakistan's many restaurant franchises. These were master franchisees who operated multi-unit restaurants in the Pakistani market. To combat the fierce rivalry, they operate as small chains. "Older franchisors wanting to maximise operational advantages while reducing free-riding behaviours from franchisees" prefer this type of growth (Kaufmann, 1992).

A large body of researchers have posited that risk is the catalyst of change, which makes franchisees to work hard to get the desired results as the failure of the business could lead to the loss of prestige and money. On the other hand, with regard to those franchises which operate under the supervision of managers, their outcomes are entirely different as they do not have senses of ownership (Ketchen et al., 2006).

A single owner owns multi-unit or mini-chain restaurants, which are managed by salaried managers. In comparison to the owners, these managers did not want to participate in the interviews. The findings show that these managers need strong monitoring and evaluation frameworks and a less significant contribution to the decision-making authority for managing the franchise. Moreover, it is explicitly visible that single unit franchised restaurants have many dissimilarities with the multi-unit franchised restaurants.

There were certain constraints in conducting the interviews with the managers, such as the fact that the four franchisees that were responsible for operating the smaller chain restaurants were stationed beyond the research content's business environment. Consequently, it is challenging for the researchers to conduct the interviews; therefore, the research excludes those four franchises from the research. Furthermore, Subway was also excluded from the list as it started in late 2013 and did not fall under the criteria of the target population. The total number of restaurant franchisees in Pakistan were 78, excluding the new entrants and closed down restaurants.

As many as 10,000 franchised restaurant customers exist in Pakistan insinuating that the target demographic for franchised restaurant consumers can be regarded as vast or endless.

Figure 12 Methodology Stages

Source: The Author

3.3.2 Qualitative Sampling Research

Non-probability sampling is commonly used in qualitative research. The choice utilised in probability sampling is not used in non-probability sampling. Rather, these strategies rely heavily on the scholar's own judgement. Non-probability samples may accurately represent the characteristics of a community, but due to their subjective nature, statistically accurate generalizability of the features to the population may be unattainable. Non-probability sampling involves selecting specified components in a non-arbitrary approach, and the expert does not attempt to build a delegate sample, instead relying on multiple forms of checks. A few examples are as follows:

- a) **Judgmental or purposive sampling:** For the research, the participants are chosen in a self-assertive way for their practices, approaches, observations etc.
- b) **Theoretical or conceptual categories:** New individuals may be sought by the researcher to review or question emerging patterns during the interview process.
- c) **Snowballing sampling:** This involves the collection of individuals having similar characteristics or views.

- d) **Convenience sampling:** In this kind of sampling the researcher selects a promptly available participant.
- e) **Quota sampling:** This has two phases and is described as a restricted judgmental sampling. The first is an expansion of control characteristics or quotas of population elements followed by a selection of a sample based on suitability or judgment.

In-depth interviews were conducted for this study in the form of surveys in order to gather data from franchisees and or managers of fast food chains in Pakistan . In Pakistan, due to the fact that many of the franchising outlets are in their initial stages and were numerous, so it was unrealistic to attempt a quantitative study and reach all of them. As far as qualitative studies were concerned, interviews were conducted from the franchisees and or managers in the Pakistani market with the help of an established sampling frame. The research relied on the list of franchises so that their relevant managers and franchisees could be interviewed. These franchisees were sampled using a convenient sample since it was impractical to interview all of them.

For the focus group discussions, the strategy utilized was convenience sampling. This sort of sampling is more often used in marketing research owing to the difficulty of establishing a sampling frame i.e., a list of clients (Creswell, 2003). The purpose of picking a convenience sample is to limit the expense and time involved in the selection. A screening method was utilized to choose the members of the interviews from among those who were willing to take part in the research. The screening method, chosen from McDaniel & Gates (2004), helped in distinguishing individuals who did not have any interest in a comparative research. Three months preceding the time, the focus groups discussions were held.

3.3.3 Sample Size

In deciding the size of the sample to be utilized for the investigation purpose, researchers utilise the subjective strategies of study that usually have recourse to either the use of industrial practice general guidelines, or the budget available. Industrial practice in conducting focus groups, is generally between five and seven groups comprising of six to twelve people in each group. Focus group discussions were carried out to set up the key issues that concerned managers of restaurants. Five discussion groups were held consisting of six to twelve

participants. With respect to the franchisees, a convenient sample of 7 managers from 62 managers of franchisees was taken.

3.3.4 Data Collection

In qualitative data collection, in order to get the desired information, researchers usually make use of focus group discussions, conduct in-depth interviews and also depend on their own personal observations.

3.3.4.1 Individual Interviews

The interview is one of the primary data collection strategies for acquiring information in qualitative research methods (Cooper & Schindler, 2008). This is based on the premise that the participants feel comfortable, probe for detail without making them feel harassed. In order to get the most effective information, the researcher should remain detached and objective and yet be able to convey sympathy and understanding to the interviewee or eagerness to understand and empathize. An unstructured interview mode should be chosen by those who, carry out qualitative research using individual in-depth interviews. There should be no specific questions or order of topics pre-determined and fixed, but rather each interview is tailored to each participant; or a semi structured interview, which would usually start with a few specific questions but then follow or develop following probes from the interviewer (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007).

This study used in-depth interviews to gather information from franchisees of diversified fast food chains. The individual in-depth interviews were carried out using skype via proper schedules; interviewees were provided in advance with general guides via email. For data collection, the study used semi-structured questionnaires. The questionnaires were adjusted during the course of each interview and followed a general pattern. The interviews were conducted at a convenient time prescribed by the franchisees. They were preceded with an introduction by the interviewer. The purpose of the research and confidentiality of the information given was pledged. The interviews lasted between forty five and seventy five minutes and were recorded.

The researcher got the lists of the managers of the franchisees, along with the permission to interview them. The selected managers were contacted and interviews were scheduled. The interviews followed a similar pattern for all the managers.

Table 3 Design of semi structured questions from the managers and franchisees

Research objective	Questions	Questions selected	Final questions
To establish how franchisees define key success factors	3 Questions from franchisee	How would you define success? What is your level of success? What does it mean to you to be successful?	The first and last questions were best suited to the required responses.
How do you know you are successful?	3 Questions from managers	What are the success indicators? b) 'Why do you claim to be successful?' and c) 'How do you measure success?'	All three questions are selected for the interview
What are the key success factors that make fast food franchises successful in Pakistan?	3 Questions from managers	a)How do you reach to the point of success? b)What steps must be taken to ensure the business's success? c) What are the key areas that you, as a franchisor/franchisee, must manage well in order for your business to succeed?	All questions are selected for the interview

3.3.4.2 Focus Groups

FGD's are a type of qualitative research method that is often used in market research to collect data. It entails picking six to twelve conversation participants from a homogeneous group. The group's homogeneity enhances the discussion's flow by allowing individuals to freely share their opinions. The researcher could utilise a discussion guide to direct the conversation and ask probing questions. (Cooper & Schindler, 2008) proposed that a focus group discussion's purpose is for the moderator to predict what will be said next. The dialogue may take place within a meeting room that holds a reciprocal mirror that appears reflective on one side and transparent at the other with either observers and video cameras or audio recorders in a comfortable setting. The content of the FGS conversations is recorded and the results are presented after the data has been analysed.

In keeping with market studies that gathered client feedback, this study also included focus-group talks. As previously stated, focus group talks were the best technique for gathering the data needed for the study. Participants for discussion groups were chosen using a screening questionnaire. The screening questionnaire included investigative inquiries that weeded out those who didn't have the data needed for the study. The focus group discussions took place in any accessible room. Audio recordings of the discussions were collected and then transcribed into text. The analysis was carried out using the text. The members were given refreshments as a token of appreciation at the end of each FGD. The questionnaire was tested in the first focus group discussion, and the final guide was created since it evoked replies that could answer the following study questions: What are the views of Pakistani customers on a successful franchised fast food chain? What are the primary success characteristics that make a franchise successful in the eyes of its customers?

The reasoning for the questions, as well as their relation to the study purpose, are stated in Table 4.

Table 4 The Rationale for the questions and their study objectives

Research objective	Research questions	Relevance to the objective
To ascertain what factors contribute to a franchise's success from the perspective of its customers.	What are your thoughts on the eating out trend in Pakistan?	The responses to this question would serve two purposes: they would serve as an icebreaker/introduction and they would also validate the growing consumer patronage of franchised restaurants. The expected responses were that the trend is either increasing or decreasing.
	Why do people prefer to dine out?	
	Why do you eat at the restaurant that you do?	The responses were anticipated to indicate the reasons why the study participants chose to eat at a fast food restaurant. Convenience, entertainment, peer pressure, pricing, food taste, variety, and so on are all expected reasons.
	What motivates you to return to the restaurant you've already visited?	After the initial visit, the replies were anticipated to identify the reasons why customers make repeat purchases from a certain fast food. Price-related considerations, food quality-related factors, customer service-related factors, restaurant environment-related factors, location-related factors, and others are all possibilities.
	What would make you never go back to a fast food joint you've been to before?	After the initial visit, the replies were supposed to identify the reasons why customers stop making recurring purchases from a certain restaurant. Price inconsistencies, food quality inconsistencies, customer service inconsistencies, restaurant setting inconsistencies, and

Source: The Author

3.3.5 Qualitative Research Data Analysis

In this research, the information is established by means of portraying occasions, circumstances, and interactions either verbally or visually. The content is comprised of interpretations which were derived from sound recordings or recorded interviews and as well as from notes taken during the focus group discussions (McDaniel & Gates, 2004; Cooper & Schindler, 2008). Coding and reflection writing are used to detect similarities and differences after creating a narrative from the acquired data. In this way the observed information is derived and are used for the identification of variables. Literature is considered to be the main source for preparation and carrying out the interviews (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

The following steps are followed in the qualitative research process:

1. Separate thematic content analysis of interviews and focus groups
2. Data visualisation and matrices
3. Data Compression
4. Analysing and describing
5. Drawing and verifying conclusions

Thematic content analysis is when patterns within data can be identified and then combined into themes. (McDaniel & Gates, 2004) suggested that these themes sum up the causes, help to develop more theoretical concepts and connect people. To manage the massive amount of data collection and analysis for the thesis, data displays and matrices are used. Data visualisation was required for the presentation and sharing of the obtained data. Matrices were mostly used for each FG and interview. The matrices make it easier to map data from each interview and focus group, as well as data from different interviews and FGS.

The technique of focusing, reducing, and condensing enormous amounts of data into smaller, more manageable portions is known as data reduction (McDaniel & Gates, 2004).

Exploring and describing data allows us to have a better understanding of it. It entails formulating and validating conclusions (Bernard, 1988). In this study, describing and exploring were done for each FGD and interview, as well as between groups and interviews. The information gathered during focus group conversations strengthened the research process by

revealing profound perspectives and highlighting the underlying reasons of those who choose to eat out. The hypotheses were reorganised and a questionnaire for the study's second phase was created using the emergent themes from the focus group discussions.

Drawing and confirming involved examining the data displayed and critically reducing data to draw conclusions in order to complete the procedure. As he struggled to analyse and interpret the data, the researcher became increasingly determined to include translations (Miles and Huberman, 1994). In order to generate the analytic text, it was essential to return to the original text for clarity. Both the focus group talks and the interviews were subjected to this analysis. Below Table 5 summarises the data visualisation, reduction, and description strategies below:

Table 5 Data Collection and Analysis Methods and Qualitative Research Question

Research objective 1: to find out the key success factors from the franchisee/managers of franchise perspective	
Research issue	Data display, reduction and analysis
What does success mean to you?	Record responses from different In-depth interviews Reduce the data to the most dominant themes Analyse the data from individual interviews as well as the data between the interviews
How do you define success?	Record responses from different In-depth interviews Reduce the data to the most dominant themes Analyse the data from individual interviews as well as the data between the interviews
What are the key areas that you must manage differently as a franchisee in the fast food industry to ensure the success of your business?	Record responses from different In-depth interviews Reduce the data to the most dominant themes Analyse the data from individual interviews as well as the data between the interviews
Research objective 2: to find out how franchisee measure their key success factors	
What does success mean to you?	Record responses from different In-depth interviews Reduce the data to the most dominant themes Analyse the data from individual interviews as well as the data between the interviews
How do you define success?	Record responses from different In-depth interviews Reduce the data to the most dominant themes Analyse the data from individual interviews as well as the data between the interviews
What are the key areas that you must manage differently as a franchisee in the fast food industry to ensure the success of your business?	Record responses from different In-depth interviews Reduce the data to the most dominant themes Analyse the data from individual interviews as well as the data between the interviews
Research objective 3: To establish how key success factors are measures and evaluated by the customers of fast food franchises.	
What are your thoughts on the eating out trend in Pakistan?	Record responses from different focus group discussions Reduce the data to the most dominant themes

Following the data analysis, the data is explored, described, and conclusions drawn. To complete this study for each interview and focus group, an analysis was conducted across the interviews and groups in order to find patterns that emerged from each interview and group discussion; the data was then compared between the interviews and groups (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The majority of customers' key issues are based on the outcomes of FGD's.

Table 6 Findings from Analysis

Descriptions	Questions used to draw meaning and verify conclusions
<p>Within group and Interview</p>	<p>What recurring themes and patterns emerge from this focus group or interview? Are there any findings in the literature that support what has been discovered here? What unusual data was discovered, and how can it be explained? Are the findings related to previous research or theory in any way? Congruent? Confirmatory? If so, how? If not, why not? Are the results convincing? Do they ring true to you? What are the main takeaways from this focus group or interview? What are the most important contributions?</p>
<p>Across-groups and interviews</p>	<p>Which focus group or interview stands out the most, and why? What are the prevalent themes and patterns that this focus group or interview has revealed? What are the parallels and differences between the groups and the interviews, and how can you explain them? What kinds of categories or clusters can be made using FGDs and interviews? Do the FGDs show that replication has taken place? If so, how and where would you do it? If not, why not? What kind of data are found to be divergent, and how can they be explained? Is there any link between the findings and previous research or theory? Congruent? Confirmatory? If so, how do you go about doing it? If not, why not?</p>
<p>Issues that are outside the scope of the study: business and policy conclusions and implications</p>	<p>What are the main conclusions of the entire thesis? Are the findings and conclusions persuading, credible, and reasonable? What conclusions can be drawn from this thesis' findings, and what significance do these conclusions have?</p>

Phase2: 3.4 Quantitative Research

According to Burns and Grove (2001), quantitative research is a formal, objective, and systematic approach of gathering numerical data. It's frequently done to test a theory by labelling variables, looking at correlations between variables, or figuring out cause-and-effect relationships between variables. Validity and dependability are considered to be the most important notions in quantitative approaches (Muijis, 2004; Cooper & Schindler, 2008).

3.4.1 Validity

Validity guarantees that the obtained results are undeniably clear (Muijis, 2004). When disparities in observed measurement scores match or imply genuine differences in the characteristic under observation, a measuring scale is deemed construct valid. Non-random errors are the source of construct validity issues (Dillon et. al., 1990). Validity is determined by the amount of non-random error in the measuring process. To see if the scale is content valid, look at how close the scale components are to the trait or construct being studied (Dillon et. al., 1990).

The degree to which two or more measuring scales meant to measure the same construct correlate is known as convergent validity. A measure's discriminant validity is assessed by examining its correlations with other measures that claim to assess a distinct but related characteristic or construct. Criterion validity refers to the ability of observed measuring scale scores to predict some criteria measure (Dillon et. al., 1990).

The construct validity of this study was determined by using a variety of data collection methods. Multiple sources of evidence have been categorised as 'integration of numerous forms of evidence,' and have been deemed more credible than a single source of data. (Yin, 1994). In the current study, construct validity was obtained through the use of triangulation of techniques.

3.4.2 Reliability

The term "reliability" refers to the degree to which outcomes are error-free; it ensures correctness, precision, and consistency (Muijis, 2004; Cooper & Schindler, 2008). It denotes the consistency or soundness of a valuation. From one measurement to the next, the measurement should be constant or stable. The precision of the measurement scores obtained from a sample should be desired, and they should be repeatable accurately with repeated

measurements. The following is a typical representation of the classic true-score measurement model: $\mathbf{XE}=\mathbf{XS}+\mathbf{XR}$

Systematic causes of error, such as instrument error, are represented by \mathbf{XS} , which records the observed scale score in the same manner each time the test is performed.

\mathbf{XR} denotes random sources of error, such as short-term personal circumstances, which will have a different impact on the observed scale score. Thus, if the independent yet contrastable measures of the same variable agree to each other, it can be stated that the measure is determined reliably and authentically. The degree to which measurements are free of random error and provide consistent and dependable results is referred to as reliability. In this case, it is stated that if \mathbf{XR} equals zero, the measure is actually trustworthy and legitimate. The coefficient of correlation is a method of assessing dependability that assumes values between plus and minus one. In this case, a positive and significant association is indicated by a plus one, whereas a negative and substantial relationship is indicated by a minus one.

Internal consistency is also defined as the item that indicates entire correlation. This is accomplished by locating each construct's correlation and comparing it to the overall score. The attitude and probability scores have a linear connection, according to the internal consistency requirements. As a result of this logic, if an item's score is significantly related to its attitude score, the item meets the criteria for internal consistency.

The Cronbach Alpha test, which evaluates the internal consistency of the measuring equipment used in the study, is one of the useful approaches for calculating coefficient reliability. Furthermore, generalizability is that it can be utilized to the targeted population because it is to a good degree of representation of the population of interest to the scholar.

The questionnaire of the test was pretested to evaluate and measure the reliability and authenticity of the instrument using the Cronbach Alpha test. Consequently, the instruments were adjusted. Each stage of the process was meticulously documented in order to ensure the credibility of the qualitative study's conclusions. The coding procedure and tabulating across the categories from the interviews were used to conduct interviews and focus group discussions. The external validity was demonstrated by the validation of patterns across focus groups and interviews. The escalating level of outcomes were then generalised in this way. The representation of validity and reliability ascertained that the research's findings were reliable and authentic.

The quantitative method, on the other hand, is utilised for descriptive or causal designs. The utilisation of clearly stated material from previously completed research questions or hypotheses is attributed to the descriptive design. This is why descriptive research is referred to as preplanned and structured. Furthermore, they are based on huge sampling of the general population. This is also stated that descriptive studies are cross sectional, meaning that data from the study's sample is collected just once. A longitudinal study, on the other hand, is used when a researcher wants to gather data from a fixed sample more than once, that is, over the course of time. Quasi-experimental and experimental designs are two types of causal designs. These designs manipulate or regulate the variables to create cause-and-effect relationships.

This study employed a descriptive research design, which entails a cross-sectional approach. In this approach, the researchers only took a sample from the study's population at one moment and obtained the opinions of fast food franchise consumers. The descriptive design aimed to name a market attribute, which was accomplished by data collecting and frequency tabulation on the research variables.

The second phase of the research aimed to corroborate the first phase's findings and put the theories that had been generated to the test. This allowed for the triangulation of research approaches as well as the enrichment of study findings. Following this confirmatory phase, the research findings were more objective and generalizable to a larger population.

3.4.3 Survey Population

The majority of marketing analyses are designed to gather data about a certain community's unique characteristics. Cooper and Schindler (2008) define population as the sum of all variables that share a set of characteristics relevant to the study. For the purposes of the marketing research, this would also be referred to as the worldwide. The census is used to determine the population's attributes, which can include a comprehensive record of the population's elements or a sample, which is the use of a sub-group of the population. According to Cooper and Schindler's study, there are a number of advantages to using a sample to take a census while gathering research data (2008). The following are the details:

Limited time to carry out the study

- a) Capital resource constraints, as executing the entire population list would be prohibitively expensive.
- b) Another consideration is population size, because conducting a census would be impractical in consumer studies involving a large population.

- c) Non-sampling error may be acceptable in a census with a small sample size.
- d) It is preferable to use a sample rather than a survey, especially when the measurement requires the destruction or contamination of the elements.

The research survey included all fast food franchise customers in Pakistan. The franchised outlets were situated in the main cities of the country such as Lahore, Islamabad, Peshawar and Karachi. The population of the customers from the fast food franchises was over 20,000, which was determined as the large infinite population and unlikely to reach all the customers to attain data.

3.4.4 The Survey Process

Cooper and Schindler (2008) define the target audience as "the entire set of individuals that the scholars wish to study," whereas the sample is "the sub-group or a subset of the people or elements of the population who have agreed to participate in the study." One of the most significant characteristics of a good sample is that it is representative of the population; that is, findings from the study sample must be extrapolated to the entire population. If the sample is to be an accurate depiction of the population, it must be free of selection bias. Furthermore, a scientific sample of the target population should be taken. This method of sampling is quantitative and is usually based on probability sampling, which means that every person of the population has an equal chance of being picked to create a sample. A sampling frame is a list that includes all of the characteristics of the population being sampled. The data required for the study about the targeted population may be obtained from the entire population, in which case it is known as a census.

The present study utilized a non-probability sampling methods. Especially, the study utilized convenience sampling where it pointed out those customers that are already found in the fast food franchised outlet on all the days of the week, excluding weekends, i.e., Saturdays and Sundays. For this purpose, a list of franchised outlets was visited and the number of questionnaires was filled in from the customers. The choice of the days was dependent on the criteria of that the researcher wanted to attain a broader set of information from the respondents. In this type of sampling, the interviewer is in charge of selecting the sampling units. This process is left with the interviewer because he or she has the idea about the right place and at the right time of collecting information from the sample of the study. Because it is difficult to

create a sampling frame, this type of sampling method is used in marketing research studies. This entails reaching out to all customers and gathering detailed information on each of them. Another important reason for using convenience sampling is a lack of time and capital resources. This study is entirely academic in nature and is not sponsored by any industry. As a result, the researcher has limited resources.

3.4.5 No Response Bias

The total survey error determines the amount of data collected. The total survey error is the difference between the population's totally true mean value and the mean observed value of the variable of interest obtained from the provided sample. Random sampling error and non-sampling error account for the entirety of the total survey error. However, a response rate of more than 50% was achieved to manage and monitor non-response bias, as this tends to reduce overall survey error.

3.5 Random Sampling Error

The study conducted by Bell et al (2018) showed that a random sampling error occurred if the chosen sample does not have perfect presentation of the whole population. In order to direct a random sampling error in the current study, the sample of the study were stratified in dissimilar groups, especially for the consumers and for the franchisees/managers of the franchises.

3.6 Non Sampling Error

According to Mabesele (2009), a non-sampling error is the extent to which the "mean observed value" for a specific sample corresponds with the true mean value for the specific sample for the element of interest. In the current study, extra attention was paid to ensuring that each researcher received a response rate of at least 50%.

3.7 Nonresponse Error

This kind of error happens due to the reason when the respondents selected for the sample of the study adequately respond. In order to augment the rate of response, the researcher of the study enabled one assistant to execute a follow up from the sampled participants and receive the completed questionnaire. This specific method was employed because it helped the researcher to ensure a quick completion rate and increased rate of response. In addition to

questionnaires, interviews from the franchisees were conducted to get a clear picture and also monitor and control the non-response error.

3.8 Response Error

This section is known as the error in data. This occurs due to an inadequate answer provided by the sample participants. In other words, when the sample respondents are not interpreted correctly or may be misreported, thus, they create biasedness. Along with this stage, the researcher conducted data analysis and ensured that outlier replies were clearly indicated from study participants, where possible, or were omitted from the evaluation where clarification was not available.

3.9 Sample Size

The variance of the attribute of interest in the target population, as well as the desired level of confidence and accuracy, determine the sample size in general. The current study's confidence level technique for calculating sample size is based on applying the average error calculation to create a level of confidence around the sample means or proportion. Because the confidence interval contains the "population mean," the level of confidence "Z" reflects how aggressive the student must be. Within the formula the sampling error E is deemed as an exception and is the error that the investigator is ready to accept. Typically, cost inferences are used in research investigations, resulting in a trade-off between accuracy, level of confidence, and costs. According to Alon (2006), the standard deviation from the population can be calculated in the following ways:

- a) It's likely that results from a primary survey dealing with the same topic or concerns will be used to determine the population standard deviation. A prior survey approach is what it's called.
- b) Another approach is to carry out a pilot study. In this specific approach, usually for the large projects, a lot of time and resources are needed for executing a pilot survey, whose findings are then utilized to establish the projections of the population standard deviation.
- c) Using secondary sources could be helpful when a same kind of research is already executed in the past or the scholar can use the secondary data to formulate an estimate of the population standard deviation.
- d) The judgments are also frequently used by scholars like when experience is used to establish the population standard deviation. This is termed as an educated guess.

In this study, the size is estimated from the population following the qualitative stage of the research. The researcher then calculates the variation and calculates a size of the sample that allows for roughly 95 percent of the probability value and 0.05 percent of the accuracy level, indicating a larger than the acceptable gap between the sample means and the study's population. The study used the following formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \sigma^2}{E^2}$$

$$384 = \frac{1.96^2 * 0.5 * 0.5}{0.05^2}$$

In the formula, Z is the required 95 percent confidence interval, which is shown in standard error; .σ is the standard deviation estimate applied to the study's population.

In the study, using this formula, sample size is determined as 385 respondents. Despite ascertaining that the non-response issues do not influence the primary sample size, the size of the sample is augmented by 5 items. The actual size of the sample was 390.

3.10 Method to Collect Quantitative Data

Usually in the quantitative research methodology, survey and experiments are used to gather the required data. Survey methods explain the ways of attaining information from the range of individuals or sample participants. This step is carried out to attain information from the hugely targeted population that has been used to collect the sample from the respondents. Generally, as in the survey method, a questionnaire was used by the researcher. After going through all the possible ways of gathering data, the present study chose the survey method for the qualitative approach. It chose the instrument that could collect the information from a large number of customers. This method is frequently used by the marketing scholars in the past and they have showcased their success with this specific methodology. The survey method employed questionnaires to collect the data from the customers about the success factors of fast food franchises.

3.11 Questionnaire Design

The empirical research shows that the survey method uses questionnaires to attain data. Hence, questionnaires have crucial roles in the whole process of the survey method. It is probable that

all leading elements of the research are well executed and there is a good sampling method and an effective planning is carried out, well trained and well organized interviewers with an adequate level of statistical analysis is executed. However, all these elements would not be effective if the questionnaire is not effectively designed. In other words, if it is poorly carried out in terms of questions' sequencing, inappropriate variables, and inadequate questions, it would be unlikely to address the research questions. In this situation, a poorly designed questionnaire leads the researcher towards misleading information. This is the reason, a large number of scholars argued that a questionnaire design must be taken into consideration that is based on the purpose of the study as illustrated in the research questions and objectives.

As mentioned by Hair et al (2008) in their study about the objectives of questionnaires, they are designed to change the information required into a set of particular investigative questions that the sample of the study is likely to answer. Such questions are required to provide information about the research questions that are helpful for attaining research objectives. The questionnaire should be designed in a way that encourages the respondent to provide their information and take part to complete the survey. Notably, this includes a trade-off or the kind of exchange between the researcher and the sample respondent. Those who agree to accept compensation may be offered a reward by the researcher. This can be a gift or a payment offer. It is also important that a scholar conveys the words of appreciation to the sample respondents as they approach them to attain information owing to the research study and the contribution made by respondents could help a researcher to complete the survey and attain the objectives. This shows empathy and motivation of the researcher towards study respondents. Here are a few elements of a good questionnaire:

- a) A questionnaire also decreases the risk of response error, which can occur as a result of an improper response, recording, or even assessment.
- b) Another essential part of the questionnaire is the structure of the questionnaires. The following steps should be considered for a productive questionnaire structure.
- c) The instructions given in the questionnaire should clearly state about how to approach and question the respondents.
- d) In order to encourage the study participants, the rewards should be adequately communicated to them. This will help them stay motivated throughout the process
- e) Another essential component is the relationship of each question with the research objectives. A lot of scholars might include additional questions or irrelevant questions

that are unlikely to provide information about the research study. This further diverts the attention of a researcher at the time of evaluating the data.

- f) The steps for data analysis must be included in the design stage. The links between the questions and acceptable statistical tests that could provide sufficient responses to the questions, for example. The evaluation measure must be created concurrently with the design.
- g) The specific research's requirements and focus, as derived from data gathered by other researchers or market demands.
- h) The information must be specific at the design phase as it is important to review the issue and the research approach should be addressed as reflected in the research questions and hypothesis.
- i) It is recommended that dummy tables are designed. This helps in cataloguing the data and reflects on how the data will be evaluated.
- j) It is better to identify the target population and have their attributes are clearly stated.

Figure 13 The design process of a questionnaire

Source: Adapted from Malhotra and Birks (2007: 375)

In this study, a questionnaire was designed and administered to the fast food customers as soon as they ordered their food and were waiting to receive them. This helped them to pass their time regardless of their getting bored. The survey was self-administered and used a five-point Likert scale with a range of 1 to 5. (1 strongly disagree, 2, disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree, 5 strongly agree). The method proposed by McDaniel and Gates was used to create the questionnaire (2004). The following is how the questionnaire was divided into groups based on the hypotheses and study objectives:

Product features

- a) Convenience
- b) The competence of employees
- c) Pricing
- d) Atmosphere and ambience
- e) Brand image, brand equity

All the questions were aimed at collecting the responses entailing the above mentioned variables. There were closed-ended response questions included to capture the power of expressing feelings about the problems presented. All of the questions were culled from the interview recordings and secondary data. As mentioned by Cooper and Schindler (2008), questions included in the questionnaire can be grouped based on the following:

- a) Dichotomous is to allow the sample of the population with two alternatives and enable them to choose one amongst them.
- b) Multichotomies is concerned with offering respondents with a range of choices
- c) Open ended needed respondents to provide an error-free reaction to the question in their own words
- d) Checklist is concerned with possible suggestions and alternatives to the sample respondents
- e) Rating requires study participants to rank each element on a comparable or numerical scale.
- f) Ranking necessitates that the participant organise the aforementioned factors in such a way that the content of the individual queries is determined.

It is critical that each question in the questionnaire seeks to obtain essential information; yet, it may be necessary to include some neutral questions to encourage respondents to build rapport

and provide support or interest to research participants in the project. To prevent any query that is likely to address two problems in one, a variety of inquiries are required to obtain the necessary information. This is highly criticized by scholars in a way that the researcher should not employ these questions because they might mislead the respondent. It is important that the researcher enacts the respondent's inability to answer or encourage them to willingly provide the answer (Scott and Spell, 1998).

It is highly suggested that the researcher should avoid those instances where it is assumed that the respondent will provide an accurate answer or a reasonable response to the questions. It is an unrealistic approach because the respondent does not have any prior idea about the study and they need proper instructions on how to fill in the questionnaire. The use of filter questions can assist the researcher in identifying participants who have the required knowledge and screening those who are used to obtain data. The empirical evidence shows that those researchers who gave cues to their respondents are likely to overcome the inability of respondents to respond the questions. Similar to previous studies, this thesis can use the same approach and enact the problems faced by the respondents of the study. It is also likely to happen that the respondents of the study are unable to articulate the response such as they may be unlikely to describe a particular response for the given question. In such case, it is advisable that the researcher enumerates the various alternatives to the respondents so that they can choose the answers that best describe their feelings and or show the ones that best narrate their attitudes or perceptions.

It is critical that the research determines and reduces the effort required by the sample participants to provide the necessary information during the question design phase. The required information must be relevant to the research scenario while also legitimising the study's purpose; otherwise, this must be explained to the sample respondents. There are some topics that may be sensitive such as income of respondents and could give the impression that the study is intruding their personal lives and invasive to their privacies. Such questions are highly recommended to place at the end of the questionnaire, instead of using them at the beginning. In addition, such questions are highly advised to include the information in the form of range, instead of asking them a real amount (Hair, 2015).

3.12 The Formation of Questionnaire

This study used questions from the literature review, provided by multiple scholars in their relevant studies. In addition, after conducting interviews, various questions were also raised that could have been used from the customers in the questionnaires. The first question of the questionnaire was developed to warm up the customers and locate them in the topic of the study. This means it grabs their attention and is likely to develop their interest for the rest of the questionnaires. The remaining questions were developed to address the objectives of the study and answer the research hypotheses guiding the study.

Each objective of the study included 6 to 8 questions and they were arranged on the five-point Likert-scale. The last question was added to rate the fast food franchises in Pakistan. The questions related to the demographics of the respondents, i.e., age and income were included but as advised before, income was placed at the end questionnaire. Lee and Ulgado (1997) conducted a study that dealt with assessing customers of fast food franchises and adopted those questions that could also be used in this study. Such questions are expected to provide similar answers as they were provided in that time. In order to answer questions related to the fast food ambience, these two question were included: “In comparison to competitors in the market, they keep their customers waiting for a longer period of time.” The other question was, “the fast food chain has included fun activity for their kids and children”. In the price category, questions were included like, “the fast food chain offer a competitive prices as compared to market competitors” and “the food and services are provided at bargaining rates and prices justify the quality of the products”, “food offered are good value for my money,” etc., etc.

In the phase 1, customers were identified and were approached for completing the survey questionnaires by utilizing the distinction of the intercept technique i.e., they ordered their meals and were waiting for their order. The customers were not approached in the middle of their meals because this could intrude their privacy and disturb them. They were then instructed to either drop their completed questionnaires at the designated location on their way out or to hand them over the counter to the manager or cashier. Customers' information was gathered over three days of the week, including weekdays and weekends. The whole process was administered with the help of two research assistants who helped the researcher of this study and executed the data collection process.

3.13 Quantitative Research Analysis

Once the researcher collected the data, the next step was to analyse the results. This included a range of steps that are required to make up the whole procedure. The study by Paik and Choi (2007) mentioned that the procedure of data analysis can be summarized and interpreted in the following manner:

- a) To validate and edit data
- b) Data coding and capturing
- c) Hypotheses Testing

Risner (2001) defined validation in the context of data validation and editing as "the act of checking that the interviews were also conducted as indicated." This step ensures an easy and earlier identification of any failure in executing the steps in regard to the main instructions, and also any other issues faced that could have influenced the sample of the respondent's answer. It also ensured that the process of collecting information using questionnaires was executed effectively and properly. Editing entails determining whether or not the interviewer or respondent made any errors. After editing, the questionnaires were ready for coding and entry into the statistical package software. Following the validation and editing of the collected questionnaires, the next step was to ensure that non-response had no effect on the actual sample size. Meanwhile, the sample size was raised by 5 units to ensure that a response rate of 98.8% was attained. Because they were classified as non-response or spoiled response, the extra 5 units were added. A sample of the study was supplied with the questionnaire to those who did not respond, but they did not return it. Spoiled responses, on the other hand, were either incomplete or omitted crucial information.

When the researcher wanted to carry out coding and capturing process of data, the scholar gave the numerical values and or alphanumeric values that exhibited a specific reaction. Alongside, when the researcher executed the coding for the closed ended questions, they were also given with specific codes prior to executing the questionnaire to the field. In this study, the survey was utilized so that the researcher could easily gather data that included mainly closed ended questions, which were coded by the end of the study survey. In order to execute the data capturing process, the primary summation of data was executed by utilizing frequency distribution. This allowed the researcher to create the out-of-range, missing and outliers values for each variable. In the given study, cross tabulation was also used to exhibit combined distributions of the variables. The researcher used SPSS software, which helped to generate descriptive statistics and inferential statistics for the study.

3.14 Hypothesis

Belk (2007) explained a hypothesis as the statement made that needs to be proven. Hypotheses are the statements that are formulated by the researcher about the factors of interest for the study. Another scholar Wingrove and Urban (2017) observe hypothesis as estimations of the associations amid variables that are used by researcher. When testing a hypothesis, the researcher uses statistical procedures to draw conclusions about the population based on the sample's analysis. Usually, a hypothesis is proposed by scholars when they want to carry out research following quantitative research methods. In this study, various hypotheses are proposed that include key success factors that were formulated based on previous studies and deduce variables from interviews conducted with the managers of their franchises.

3.15 Hypothesis Testing

Once the primary data evaluation is carried out, the researcher desires to create if a particular concept is previously supported by the data. The study uses methods to execute the procedure known as hypothesis testing. While evaluating the hypothesis, it is important that the hypothesis is specified and then an appropriate test is applied amid the decision rule formulated showing if it would accept or deny the hypothesis. The study analyses the hypothesis, which is termed as one tail hypothesis.

In a set of hypotheses, assumptions are related to the ranking order amongst the variables. The presumed ranking order is required to be affirmed or denied. This study determined the significance of each hypothesis in the thesis in this setting. The following steps were taken during the testing and evaluation of the hypothesis:

- a) Testing of validity and reliability
- b) The use of Chi square statistical analysis
- c) Determination of correlation of the coefficient

The significance of each independent variable and the hypothesis was assessed in this study. The study used the p value for each t-test to draw conclusions about whether the null hypothesis or the stated hypothesis was accepted. The current study's standard for successfully accepting and rejecting the null hypothesis is based on a level of significance of 5%. If the calculated value of p is less than 5%, the null hypothesis fails to be accepted, and the alternate hypothesis

is accepted. If, on the other hand, the p value is greater than 5%, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis must be rejected.

3.16 Chi Square

Chi square is used in this study because the study assumes that the variables are normally distributed and chi square is best suited for non-parametric test of significance. In such scenario, the nominal data is involved. The test was carried out using the level of significance alpha is equal to 0.05. The test is applied to the given study to find out the categories of gender, income and age with regard to the frequency of visits to the fast food restaurant. The evaluation of tests facilitated the research to answer the questions of the study.

3.17 Correlation Determination

In this investigation, the Pearson correlation coefficient, also known as the correlation coefficient, was employed to determine the magnitude and direction of the association between the variables. This resulted in covariance between the two variables, which helped us determine whether there was a linear relationship between the two variables. For example, consider how age, gender, and income are related to fast food consumption.

Following the previous studies, the assumptions about “r” are mentioned as:

- a) Linear relationship between the variables is observed
- b) The data is traversed by a straight line
- c) A bivariate normal distribution is seen, which means that the data comes from a random sample of the population and the variables are normally distributed in a combined manner.

The coefficient of correlation is used in this study to answer the following questions:

- a) What is the relationship between customer convenience and product price?
- b) What is the relationship between price and convenience?
- c) What is the relationship between price and product?
- d) What is the relationship between the product and employee competence?
- e) What is the relationship between employee competence and the fast food environment?

Table 7 Table Showing the Statical Method of Testing the Hypothesis

Objective of the study	Hypothesis	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Descriptive test	Inferential statistics
What are the key success factors from the customer perspective?	Product mix is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food restaurant from the customer perspective	Product mix	Success in the Pakistan fast food market	Mean Frequencies Standard deviation	Chi square Correlation coefficient (r statistics, F statistics
	Convenience is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food restaurant from the customer perspective	Convenience			
	Employee competence is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food restaurant from the customer perspective	Employee competence			
	Price is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food restaurant from the customer perspective	Price			
	Atmosphere is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food restaurant from the customer perspective	Atmosphere			
	Managerial experience is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food	Managerial experience	Success in Pakistan	Mean Frequencies Standard deviation	

	restaurant from the customer perspective				
	Business concept is the key success factor for determining the success of fast food restaurant from the customer perspective	Business concept	Success in Pakistan	Mean Frequencies Standard deviation	
	Brand awareness, brand image, brand attributes and promotion and revenue growth have positive relation with each other in the fast food franchised outlets.	Brand awareness, brand image, brand attributes and promotion	Revenue sales growth	Mean Frequencies Standard deviation	

3.18 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual Framework in Figure 3.5 below shows a general process of how the success factors for franchising in Pakistani fast food industry. The framework shows the key independent variables to measure the success factors in the fast food industry.

Figure 14 The Conceptual Framework

Independent Variables

1. Convenience
2. Employee Competence
3. Price
4. Atmosphere
5. Brand Image
6. Product Mix

Dependent Variable

1. The determinants of successful performance of franchises in Pakistan.

3.19 Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the research paradigm, design and the philosophical underpinnings of the research methodology used for the thesis. The chapter discussed in good detail the operational interconnectivity of the qualitative and quantitative approaches used in the research. Chi square, the statistical analysis method employed in analysing the findings of the research have all been well discussed. The chapter also discussed the viability of statistical figures arrived at which are usually analysed by the Cronbach Alpha got for the accuracy of figures used in the analysis. The chapter concluded with a Table showing the process of the hypothesis testing carried out for the research.

Chapter 4: Findings and Analysis

Chapter 4a: Analysis-Qualitative Data

4.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, a detailed research methodology was discussed and explained. The steps related to the sampling method and sampling size were explained, determined and concluded from the previous studies. Data collection instruments, methods of collecting data and analysis of results were discussed along with the justifications made by different viewpoints. This section of the chapter (4a) deals with data already collected using qualitative research methods amid interviews. Explanations and evaluations are carried out and summarized using narratives and grounds.

4.1.1 Thematic Analytical Process

The reasons, processes, and problems that emerged during the inquiry are presented using text analysis as an analytical tool. The current study's corpus is made up of texts chosen by managers and junior managers who consented to be interviewed as part of the research project to help discern the theme of the study. The sample texts were chosen based on the fact that they should cover all the research questions and that the respondent thought they exemplified either effective or ineffective enquiries. This was in line with the primary goal of both surveys, which was to determine their individual opinion on the factors affecting the successful operations of franchise food chains in Pakistan. In the end, this goal was not met; no obvious pattern of answers could be discerned, and responses were inconsistent.

Figure 15 Thematic Analysis

4.2 Study Participants

As at the time of conducting this study, a total of 20 fast food franchises were selected in the Pakistani food market. McDonald's, KFC, Hardees, Subway, Burger King are the main franchises that were operating in various cities of Pakistan. The participants of the study were managers of the relevant franchises. However, some of these franchising units employed their own franchisees as managers; however, some chain outlets hired managers to manage their operational activities. All the respondents were coded with relevant IDs allocated to them.

4.3 Interview Analysis for the Key Determinants of Successful Performance in the Franchising Sector

After conducting the interview, it was concluded based on interview recordings that a majority of participants determined the business concept and the brand image as key success factors of their relevant fast food chains. One of the interviewee's responses is summarised below:

(Participant A, aged 35 years)

“Business concept is one of the major elements that needs to be clearly demonstrated to the customers. There are various customers who are now well aware of the different market offerings and compared them easily with regard to prices, attributes and business processes. Although, different customers have different opinions about the business concept depending on their personal experiences, it also depends on how the chain outlet operates its functions. This is the reason I think business concept is more important than any other factor”

Another male respondent of the study, participant C aged 44 years said:

“Although our branding is more focused on farm to fork, if you notice, business concept has given us an edge over the market competitors. In particular to the supply of chicken, and since then we operate with halal license and we are registered with the Pakistani halal board. We realize that it gave us a real boost that may sound very fundamental but for us it gave us the competitive edge”.

Participant E, male and aged 53 years responded with the following answer:

“Exactly and like other things that are also felt by us is that customers feel happier with the foreign based franchise and think that their business concept is better than the local fast foods. This is the reason that enforces them to become loyal customers and influence their repeat

purchase decision. Another reason is that, with the kind of experience they have with the specific franchise makes them a loyal customer. Many of the customers repeat their purchase decisions because they feel that the quality attributes of international fast food are superior and are unlikely to be found in the domestic fast food chains”

At the beginning of interviews, some of the managers revealed that their unit revenue is mainly depended on product characteristics. The following statements are typically given by most of the managers (Participant A, B, D, F), who said that:

“The profitability of their franchise system depends on absolutely the product attribute. Just as those who do not have any special characteristics like any special offering related with their product, they are unlikely to progress well in the market. However, there are additional factors like employee-competence that may persuade customers to select one specific fast food chain, repeatedly. Despite all, it all depends on the product attributes and the quality of the franchise outlet that is preferred by customers and enforces them to buy from the specific chain”

This shows that the franchising system success is not rated only on the business concept, but there are additional elements such as product attributes and the quality of product offered by a specific franchise outlet that motivates customers to repurchase from the same outlet and become a loyal customer. This shows that “employee competency” has a profound role on the customer decision-making process. It was also indicated from one of the interviewee response who regarded that the willingness of the customers to disregard level of discontentment, if there is any probability that the obsession with such element of franchising system would have any adverse influence on the progression of the franchising unit, the managers would not neglect

this element and would give it a considerable focus. In this prospect, participant F aged 54 years stated that:

“Employee competence is seen as instrumental in affecting the customer satisfaction and contentment with the specific franchise and the association between the franchising system and the customer. However, there are some franchising units that have perceived employee competence as the power of the last resort that helps them to resolve issues; however, some perceive it as the weak factor as compared to the price and quality of the products offered by the franchise system. In specific terms, most franchisors and franchisees are not of the opinion that employee competence has any impact on the success of the franchise units”.

The product mix is not perceived as majority of the managers as the influencing factor; however, when they were convinced to exhibit the reasons for not considering it as a meaningful attribute, the majority of the managers answered that it was a measure of success for them, but as they were provided with a specific list of product mix and product lines, therefore they are not much worried about the attributes of the products. Contrary to these responses, 5 of the total respondents replied that the product mix was similar to the marriage where partners had certain expectations of trust, loyalty and high quality characteristics.

This is attributed to the franchising system in a way that customers perceive that they are likely to receive something very different in the form of product mix attributes. In addition, they also alleged communication as the most influential element that affected the relationship between the customer and the franchising system with regard to the product mix and product offerings. This is further explained by one of the respondents, participant I, aged 43 years stated as:

“While the majority of customers are also aware of the franchise offerings to help them feel more valued, communication by a competent employee is one of the major attributes that enable customers to express their desire about specific product attributes and see enhancements in the franchising system. This in turn strengthens customer perception about the specific franchising system, make them contended with the product mix and features of the products offered by them and become a loyal customer with the brand offerings”.

This shows that the fast food chain outlets in Pakistan need to have a well-defined concept with standardized rules and regulations and an enhanced product mix with high quality attributes. This also helps in building brand image, as evident from the interviewee responses who stated that employee competence with smooth and enhanced communication processes are important in steering customers to become brand loyal. These findings are previously revealed by Wingrove and Urban (2017) who posited that business concept and product mix attributes with enhanced employee competence are essential for the fast food franchises to establish loyal customers. Findings from the interview sessions showed that one of the key success factors for the fast food franchising system from the franchisee perspective is managerial experience. The response of one interviewees can be illustrated here as:

“It is very important to know that in Pakistan, there is a high competition in the fast food sector. There are a lot of local brands with low prices that are already targeting low to medium class people. While statistics show that 60% of the population in the country includes low to medium status people, it is very important for the franchising system to understand that they are competing with the local brands and the competition may turn intense if they do not give adequate importance to some of the key success factors.

In my perspective, the most important variable is managerial experience and knowledge of the manager about the local tastes and preferences of domestic customers. If a manager lacks such skills, they are unlikely to target local audience and will keep pushing customers towards local brands.

We have to understand that the cultural preferences, taste preferences and rituals etc. are very important factors that determine the success and failure of the international brand. There are some of the brands that lost market share in the previous decade because they lacked managerial experience in the relevant field. Hence, I believe that knowledge about local taste and managerial experience are two essential factors that have vital roles in determining the success and failure of the franchise in Pakistan”.

From the given response, it is indicated that if a franchise has a strong business concept with an improved product mix and employee competence but lacks sufficient managerial skills like managers of the franchising system do not know about priorities of local customers, their likes and dislikes, they are unlikely to become productive and attain success in the international market. In particular to Pakistan’s economy, the international business entrepreneurs must have a detailed information about the local culture, as mentioned by Khan et al (2013) because there is a distinct difference between Pakistan’s cultural values and western cultural values. In terms of haram and halal food, it is important to understand the local cultural preferences and how they perceive the concept of haram and halal in food outlets.

Another interviewee, participant I, aged 43 years responded with the following answer:

“In Pakistan, the majority of customers anticipate that franchises are comparatively expensive and costly to the local market. However, if we give them exceptional experience through high

quality product attributes and offers them that product mix that targets their preferences, we can make significant profits and lead towards a record revenue. In this context, brand name, promotional techniques and brand attributes are notable variables that have considerable roles in determining success of specific franchise”

In the given response, three other key success factors are highlighted: brand image, brand attributes and promotional techniques such as advertising and marketing strategies. These elements seem to have significant influences on the overall success and or failure of the franchise system. In the literature review, Lee et al. (2008) identified in their study that brand image, brand attributes and brand equity were three essential factors that needed to be given first priority in the contemporary world of business competition.

Participant H, aged 51 years, male manager of the franchising outlet stated:

“Although, we cannot control the brand image directly because it is what is directly inherited from the franchisor and people have already established their assumptions about the brand identity, we can ,however, further enhance brand attributes by giving them a local touch through the agreement of a franchisor. We are bound to follow franchisor instructions and cannot make any decision regardless of getting their permission; therefore, it sometimes becomes arduous for us to convince customers about the offered brand attributes. In this prospect, there is another key factor that has a greater influence on the success or failure of the products offered by the franchising system; that is the pricing of the products.”

From the above mentioned response, another major factor is identified as the key success factor: prices of the fast food products. This implies that prices are given profound importance by the customers when they are deciding upon specific product. Especially, in the context of

Pakistan, customers have low switching costs in the fast food industry because there is a large number of local fast food chains that might offer products with similar attributes, if not exactly same.

At the outset of the interview process, the multitude of franchisees had the core belief that their unit profitability is exclusively related to the marketing strategies and customer services. The following statement shows the typical answers provided by the franchisees of the Pakistani fast food sector. In this regard, participant F, aged 45 years stated:

“Profitability is definitely accelerated by effective marketing strategies. Just wonder those who do not have them. This is the world of the digital market where people have increasingly been changing demand with respect to product attributes, promotional strategies, processes and people involved in the process.”

Some additional factors were also recognized during the course of interview process. For instance, time duration of brand existing in the market is one of the main factors, identified by the franchisee. This factor is linked with brand name in the market. Based on the study by Trkman (2010) the brand name and its overall existence period influence its business activities in a way that if people are already aware about the brand name, it leads them to become loyal customers. Although, franchisee satisfaction and contentment are not determined as rated high in contrast to other factors; however, franchisees believed that if the market region has a high competition, it motivates them to become highly competitive.

This feature is essential because the competitive market elevates creativity and innovation. Undeniably, local market demographic attributes, consumer market demands, local market searching and the likelihood of local communities to bear changes are some of the essential

factors required by every franchisee to become successful in the franchising system. Argued by Hietschold et al (2014) empirical research conducted on franchisees indicates that their willingness to attain the level of satisfaction of customers helped them to attain success. In this study, “passion” for the franchisee in respect of all the dimensions of his or her business is the growing issue identified by their responses during the interviews, although not a greater emphasis was given to this realm by the franchisees during the interviews. However, the response towards local market research and establishing product attributes that meet customer needs exhibits their responses towards passion as the key success determinant and indicated that for them, meeting local customer needs is exclusively important.

Along with the above-mentioned factors, it was also revealed that communication and collaborative skills are equally important for the successful operations of franchising in the market. It means that a franchisee has the power to influence the relationship with the customers and with the franchisor. Those franchisees that are unable to implement an effective communication process do not warrant the progress of their franchising system. According to Müller (2015), the communication process is instrumental in affecting the relationship between the franchisor and franchisee, the franchisee with customers, and the franchisor with customers. However, where the franchisee uses communication and collaborative skills as a last resort to resolve issues, this study did not see it as a significant influential factor in the relationship between the franchisee and the customer, or between the franchisee and the franchisor.

In the particular instance of KFC franchisee in Pakistan, some were of the opinion that the success of their franchising was attributed to their flexibility and meeting cultural values of different regions. For this purpose, organizational culture has an integral value because it reflects their brand and the values that they live by. A good franchisee will work hard to maintain and protect that culture by only awarding personal values that are aligned with the company's strategic objectives. In this study, another interviewee responded to the question:

how do they establish their franchising unit if the market does not have any prior demands for it.?

Participant F, male franchisee aged 40 years answered:

“Those brands are usually preferred by the franchisees that have specific brand equity in the overseas markets. However, in certain situations a new product has a lot of potential to achieve success because the market does not possess intense competition. Although, there are various franchisees who do not favour new products at the cost of established brands because in that case they might face high royalties and weak potential for sales growth. Especially, when the country is a developing nation and people might not have strong purchasing power parity.”

In the existing situation, another important factor, customer purchasing power, was identified as the meaningful variable to influence the sales growth of the franchising system. Understanding consumer behavior and their ability to purchase certain products is crucial for the successful operations of business units. For instance, one of the interviewees explained that when the franchising unit is established in a specific region, it is vital for the franchisor and franchisee to adapt a pricing strategy that enables customers to purchase the products offered by the franchising system. Based on the study by Asemi & Jazi (2010), the purchase decision and the greater impact of the business require both franchising and the franchisee to look deeper into their sales practices and marketing strategies by focusing on the 7Ps of the marketing mix (product, place, price, process, people, promotion, and physical distribution). The relationship between the franchisee and the customers is two-sided, i.e., customers reacting to business tactics and franchisees responding to the customer trends in the specific market. The business side of the franchising system is emphasized on increasing revenue, and the customer side wants to make intelligent purchasing decisions.

Contrary to the previous studies, where the majority of scholars did not find that franchising businesses did not give adequate attention to customer service related to dealing with their complaints, nowadays, customer complaints and their concerns are dealt with immediately. This is, however, true when customers are easily reachable. On the other hand, there are some franchising business units in Pakistan, such as KFC, that have provided their mailboxes at the entrances and exits of their units with a prompt response to customer complaints. KFC has even offered mobile services through text messages, which allows customers to forward their concerns or register their complaints immediately with their orders. This is further illustrated by Gikonyo et al. (2015) who found that those franchising units that have adequately done their customer service can profoundly increase their company's bottom lines. This is why there is a strong positive association between customer service and business progression.

However, this success is not expected to be infinite because there are some franchising units that have utilized their several resources and improved customer service but ended up forfeiting a very large price for it. Thus, the key for companies to establish customer service business operations is that companies use them strategically and effectively in order not to expand their budgets.

One of the studies by Müller (2015) showed that those surveys that drilled down on the question, "Do customer services reward the company with increased sales, profits, and revenue or not?" The authors concluded that 7 out of 10 franchises in the US state that their major revenue cash is spent on customer service. Similarly, consumers also regard those companies who value their customers and provide them with the best customer service as their top priority when availing service and purchasing their products. Customer service is increasing in all the major business sectors. However, in the context of the restaurant sector, customers are willing

to pay 18% more for their services, which is 5% more than the previous 5 year period. Part of this is majorly driven by fast food companies, who have now agreed to spend extensive amounts of money on customer care as before. There are other groups of researchers (e.g., Asemi & Jazi, 2010) who have investigated this question in more depth and with a thorough examination. The scholars revealed and published in the Harvard Business Review in 2019 that those organizations that provide prompt services to their customers are paid off by remembering their customers in good words. Even to the extent that such customers are willing to pay repeatedly for these organizations, 10 times more than those who are unable to serve their customers with personal care. In the context of airlines, a research study revealed that passengers are willing to pay \$10 more for their tickets as compared to those who had weak services (cited by Müller, 2015). Those companies that provided responses in five minutes experienced increased revenue sales because customers were willing to pay even \$20 more as compared to other market rivals. These results are in line with the current interview data collected from the interviewee (a franchisee), who also regarded customer service as now seemingly their top priority and was willing to spend more money on customer service.

As marketing strategies evolve in tandem with the digital world, the competition between companies is heating up. Henceforth, in order to tackle this competition, it is integral for every organization to visualize their marketing strategies in an online world and use digital marketing strategies. One of the interviewees revealed that since the world was entering an online platform, a large number of companies were now moving towards digital marketing strategies such as the promotion of their products using online platforms like social media, availing the services of food bloggers, optimising their brand with search engine optimisation and using online services to provide their products and deliver them to homes, either free of cost or charging a very small amount.

An interviewee, participant G, aged 38 years, and a male manager, responded that:

“Market entrance factors like target audience, market compatibility purchasing power of the customers e.g., if the target audience includes limited niche or broad audience and if overhead cost will be covered or not. These factors have crucial roles in opening a new franchising business in a developing country. However, in my perspective, only these factors are not sufficient as services including tangible and intangible factors are equally important. Significantly, marketing strategy and in the contemporary world of business, digital marketing strategy is more important as compared to traditional marketing strategy. A lot of customers want to avail online services, especially when life has become too fast and everyone wants to receive their products either at their home door-step or at the entrance of an office. Although, the physical environment of the franchising business is unlikely to be avoided because there are various customers who still want to visit business units, still the ratio is less than a few years ago”.

As the franchising landscape, especially in the context of the fast food industry, is exclusively competitive, these business units are required to formulate tactics that could help their potential customers and encourage them to visit the franchising outlets. Eventually, digital marketing strategies are created by business organizations to attract new customers and expand their customer base. Nonetheless, it is critical for businesses to be aware of the leading digital marketing strategies available to them and to select the one that is best for them. Digital marketing has a broad spectrum of opportunities and offers products and services across the globe. However, Camillo et al. (2008) wonder whether it is a new website or a direct digital marketing strategy that promotes franchising units.

This analysis, however, confirms previous studies that product attributes, prices, quality, employee competence, management activities, brand names, brand attributes, and business concepts are variables that promote franchising units. In addition to these variables, the present study also confirms, based on the practical experience of sample respondents, that digital marketing strategies and customer service have crucial value and facilitate customers towards the specific franchising unit. Customer service is now deemed one of the essential factors that may boost franchise sales promptly or even decline them if not provided with an adequate strategy. In this fast-paced business landscape, where every business strives to have successful operations in the market, digital marketing strategy cannot be overlooked. Being aware of these strategies and influential factors helps franchising units in the fast food sector attain various benefits and augment their sales revenues. However, each franchising unit requires a unique strategy that could help with consistent sales and an improved brand name in the market.

4.4 Focus Group Analysis for the Role of COVID-19 in Fast Food Franchising in Pakistan

In addition to collecting primary data through individual interviews with fast food franchisees and managers and obtaining information from customers through questionnaires, a focus group discussion was held during COVID-19 to understand customer perceptions of fast food franchises and to what extent fast food franchises have been successful in terms of customer health and safety. Since there was a pandemic crisis and a lockdown situation, and since it was also unlikely to conduct focus group discussion in the field, online sessions were arranged through "Zoom software", and all the customers were selected using purposive sampling and snowball sampling methods. In total, 15 customers were selected to discuss the matter of COVID-19 and the extent it affected their perceptions and attitudes towards fast food franchises and identify the key success factors that may help fast food franchises enhance their

performance and productivity in the market. The time duration for the entire focus group was 80 minutes and started from 5:30 p.m. in the evening to 6:50 p.m. on Saturday (Date: November 14, 2020). The focus group discussion started with the following question: "What are your views on customers interacting with fast food franchises during COVID-19?"

The above question began the focus group discussion and preceded the whole discussion with varying viewpoints collected from different respondents to the study. To keep the anonymity of each participant, numbers were given to each participant, which started from 001 to 015. Participant 001 began the discussion as:

“One of the core reasons why the pandemic has been so damaging for the fast food franchises is that it attacked at the fundamental traits of each franchise. Despite the fact that technology had been increased in the past few years, it did not seem essentially a way to remove human interaction. We cannot neglect human interactions in the food sector. Although, when I evaluate the recent activities of the majority of fast food restaurants, I realise that they are trying to avoid people at all costs. The majority of franchises have used “front counter shields” to offer barriers between workers and clients, even that I am unable to tell if the cashier is smiling at me or not”.

The participant ID 005 added in this discussion as:

“Since the increase of COVID, fast food restaurants in Pakistan are really thriving for offering best customer services and consider health and safety as the key parts of their strategies.. Even though they are following strict SOPs, still I can see their connection with their customers on a daily basis. Such as, a few days back I went to collect my meal from a fast food chain from a drive through area and found that they have recently added a customer survey with the aim to

find out customer's perceptions towards them. There was a mailbox with a separate file that had pages to write a review and place them in the mailbox. I also liked the way they kept a hand sanitizer with the mailbox. When I went to collect my meal, I was hardly able to see their waiter or service provider as they were having a glass shield to safeguard their customers. Their hands were also covered with gloves. This element assured me that I was fully protected”.

One participant with ID, 009 raised question:

“Am I always concerned about how different people interact with quick service of fast food franchises, in this unrivalled pandemic environment?”

The above question further led to discussions and a few more participants added their experiences and viewpoints as participant 002 who said:

“I always regard those fast food restaurants that facilitate digital or text message ordering. Actually, I need to remain safe and healthy but at the same time I want to eat and enjoy fast food items. More restaurants have been very effective in the previous days when there was a wave of corona virus. Their improved convenience in ordering and safety in digital services led me to continue purchasing their fast food items”

Another respondent, ID 006 added in the given discussion by sharing his perception as:

“I am much concerned about me being exposed to corona virus, which is why, I will try my best to avoid going to any restaurant during this challenging time. However, as participant 002 said, fast food franchises are making steps towards the enhancement of their environment and convenience and making ways towards digital business. I believe that I will return to quick

service fast food franchises for the variety of reasons. First, I am assured that the relevant fast food is offering safe and healthy food, free from any contamination and harmful effects as I have heard that corona virus stays on the surface for a few days. Second, brand reputation of a particular fast food has an integral role in my perspective and I believe that as franchises are claiming to be healthy and safe places for customers then I would definitely want to avail their services more even before I used to visit there prior to quarantine. My reason is straight forward: Franchises convenience, business concept and reputation are worth in weight during crisis”.

The above discussion was further brought forward as participant ID 012 said:

“In this pandemic crisis, people are seeking ways to become normal again and familiarize themselves with those places that entertain them. Eventually, ambience and comfort offered across various franchises have important roles. In my case, I try to go to the place that I trust and I believe that they offer safe and affordable items with excellent safety measures. A pandemic crisis due to corona is not a ripe environment for enjoying adventurous dining”

Respondent ID 011 added in the discussion as:

“The pandemic crisis happened so quickly. I have a friend who is working across KFC outlets in Pakistan. He shared with me his experience that they were ordered to install hand sanitizers as soon as the pandemic elevated and they were ordered to entertain only take away and delivery orders”

Participant 014 replied to this thus:

“I visited a majority of franchises because I am a fast food lover. During my visit I found that all such franchises were informed with new standards and had varying operating procedures

like the majority of them ceased their dining services and only take away was provided. Still, old customers were entertained with extra caution and they were provided with special health and hygiene measures if they wanted to eat and enjoy the environment in the fast food outlet”.

In view of the above focus group discussion, all Pakistani franchising segments seemed to allow take-away and home deliveries with an intense focus given on the health and safety of employees, customers, and audiences. Although the closure of dine-in services and only home deliveries made it arduous for both customers and franchisees to earn profits, the given focus group discussion revealed that those franchises that were able to maintain their SOPs and the health and safety of their customers still managed to succeed in this pandemic crisis, and customers continued going to such franchise outlets.

Chapter 4b: Quantitative Analysis

The previous chapter collected and analysed data using qualitative analysis and in-depth interviews. However, this chapter of the thesis elaborates on the results attained through quantitative research methods and structured questionnaires using the five point Likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree).

4.5 The Response Rate

Overall, the response rate of the determined sample size of 385 was 100%. The sample size was raised by five units to guarantee that nonresponse difficulties did not affect the initial sample size, and a total of 390 samples were gathered to examine customer propensity towards fast food franchises and how different factors influence their perspective towards a given firm. The actual sample size was 390, and with a non-response base and probability of missing data, the actual size was determined as 389. Hence, the overall response rate was 99.7%, including

non-responses. One response was considered either missed or due to incomplete information and was, therefore, not included in the study. The non-response can be classified as those questionnaires which are given to the participants but not given back by them. Table 1 shows the response rate of the customers for the given study.

Table 8 Case-processing summary

Summary of Case Processing

	N	%
Valid	389	99.7
Cases Excluded ^a	1	.3
Total	390	100.0

a. Using all variables in the procedure, a listwise deletion is performed.

4.6 Reliability Tests

This section offers the reliability tests for the items used in the questionnaire. A convenience sample of 390 respondents was used to collect the data from the customers of the franchised fast food outlets, which were recognized as the source of collecting data for this study. The construct for calculating the reliability and validity of items used in the current study is tested through Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach in 1995 mentioned that if someone is looking to test the reliability of scales used in a study, the benchmark is 0.7. If the value attained for an individual item and for all the items used in the questionnaire has a minimum value of 0.7 and a maximum value of 0.9, then it is considered the most reliable and valid item. In other words, applying the same concept to the current study, it is implied that if the reported Cronbach alpha is higher or equal to 0.7, it means that the statements measuring the customer inclination towards fast food

franchises are well understood by the participants of the study and are highly reliable to use to collect the data.

This section shows the reliability and validity tests of the variables used in the study. The results show that the constructs were reliable and that the entire questionnaire was highly reliable for the analysis. The reliability tests for Cronbach alpha are shown in Table 9.

Table 9 Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.805	.870	18

The above calculated value of the reliability test shows that Cronbach's alpha is 0.80, which is higher than 0.7 and lower than 0.90. Hence, based on this value, the items used to measure the customer inclination are highly reliable and offer significant results for this study.

Table 9 shows reliability tests for the individual constructs used in the current study. From the given table, it is indicated that the Cronbach alpha for each item is also greater than 0.70, which shows that they fulfill the criteria of Cronbach for reliability tests and are likely to offer the most reliable results for each variable.

Table 10 Item total statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Gender	33.41	64.598	.523	.	.795
Age	32.92	61.504	.697	.	.784
Position	32.28	54.770	.434	.	.801
Nam FastFood	32.49	53.493	.607	.	.779
Visit Frequency	31.97	53.491	.861	.	.760
Convenience	33.45	68.109	.030	.	.813
Price	32.82	58.834	.497	.	.788
Product Features	32.75	70.088	-.213	.	.814
Employee Comptence	32.72	65.948	.121	.	.813
Atmosphere	33.08	58.826	.794	.	.775
Brand Image	33.40	62.462	.803	.	.786
Success	33.08	59.604	.557	.	.785
Visit Reason/Convenience	33.38	62.242	.828	.	.785
Visit Reason/Price	32.43	68.411	-.067	.	.840
Visit Reason/Product	33.03	64.244	.687	.	.792
Visit Reason/Emp.Com	33.45	63.145	.730	.	.788
Visit Reason/Atmosph	33.04	64.093	.698	.	.792
Visit Reason/Brand Img	32.12	66.189	.065	.	.821

Table 10 above shows the item statistics for their mean values and standard deviations. Item statistics are utilized to evaluate the productivity of individual test items, based on the condition that the entire quality of the test derives from the quality of their items. The study used mean as the average customer response to the item and it is computed by adding the number of points earned by the customers on the item and then dividing them with the total number of respondents. Likewise, standard deviation is the measure of dispersion of student scores on that particular item. That is, it shows how the particular item is spread out and how spread the responses were. The standard deviation is the most important when contrasting items and which have exceeding one correct substitute and when the scale scoring is utilized. For this purpose, this study uses standard deviation for the purpose of evaluating customer response towards fast food franchises. Table 11 shows that standard deviations are not highly spread from the mean value and are near to the mean, which shows that most of the data is clustered about the mean value.

Table 11 Item statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Gender	1.40	.491	389
Age	1.89	.645	389
Position	2.53	1.739	389
NamFastFood	2.32	1.493	389
Visit Frequency	2.84	1.128	389
Convenience	1.37	.715	389
Price	1.99	1.155	389
Product Features	2.06	.346	389
Employee Competence	2.09	1.014	389
Atmosphere	1.74	.783	389
Brand Image	1.42	.494	389
Success	1.73	.977	389
Visit Reason/Convenience	1.43	.496	389
Visit Reason/Price	2.38	1.487	389
Visit Reason/Product	1.78	.414	389
Visit Reason/Emp.Com	1.37	.482	389
Visit Reason/Atmosph	1.77	.421	389
Visit Reason/BrandImg	2.69	1.223	389

4.7 Demographic Statistics

The findings of the current study reveal that the dominant gender for the current study is male with 59.5% and female with 40.5%. It shows that in the current study the proportion of male is higher than the females. Table 12 shows that the current study accounts 232 males and 158 females.

Table 12 Gender frequency analysis

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	232	59.5	59.5	59.5
Valid Female	158	40.5	40.5	100.0
Total	390	100.0	100.0	

Other findings on demographics show that the age of the respondents are between 25 to 35 years with 57.4% of the total sample size. It means that customers with this age group have more frequent visits as compared to other age groups. However, this age group is followed with 15 years to 25 years and then only 62 participants of the study are between 35 years to 45 years who are mostly employers, self-employed and employees. On the other hand, it is correct that a large population of people are of the age of younger customers' age ranging between 25 years to 35 years visit fast food franchises.

Table 13 Age Frequency analysis

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 15-25	104	26.7	26.7	26.7
25-35	224	57.4	57.4	84.1
35-45	62	15.9	15.9	100.0
Total	390	100.0	100.0	

Figure 16 Graph showing the gender of respondents

Figure 17 Graph showing the Ages of respondents

The following table shows the findings of the study concerning the "name of the fast food frequently visited by customers." The findings show that McDonald's is the top preference of each customer, with a higher frequency of visits. Burger King is the least frequented restaurant by customers, trailing only KFC, Hardees, and Subway. This also indicates that McDonalds is highly preferred in Pakistan due to its key success factors linked to customer satisfaction. However, the next parts of the study will reveal the reason for the higher frequency of visits to McDonald's as compared to other fast food franchises.

Table 14 Name of the Fast Food Frequently Visited by Customers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid McDonalds	168	43.1	43.1	43.1
KFC	86	22.1	22.1	65.1
Hardees	39	10.0	10.0	75.1
Burger King	34	8.7	8.7	83.8
Subway	63	16.2	16.2	100.0
Total	390	100.0	100.0	

Figure 18 Graph Showing Names of Pakistan's Fast Foods

The demographic attribute, "visit frequency," shows that a large proportion of the sample taken visits fast food franchises on a weekly basis. Around 50%, or 195 respondents, of the study showed that they visited fast food franchises on a weekly basis. 31% disclosed that they visited on a monthly basis. 6.9% revealed that they visited fast food centers of their choice twice a week and once every six months. However, only 5% shared that they visited on a daily basis. This indicates that a majority of respondents visit fast food franchises of their choice on a weekly basis.

Table 15 Frequency to visit the fast food franchise

Visit Frequency

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	20	5.1	5.1	5.1
Weekly	195	50.0	50.0	55.1
Twice a week	27	6.9	6.9	62.1
Valid Monthly	121	31.0	31.0	93.1
Once in six months	27	6.9	6.9	100.0
Total	390	100.0	100.0	

Figure 19 Graph Showing Frequency of Visits to Pakistan’s fast Foods

Figure 19 illustrates the frequency of visits to Pakistan’s fast Foods. Indicating the position of customers visiting fast food franchises, the study reveals that 51.5% of the respondents or 201 out of 389 respondents were company employees who used to visit fast food franchise of their choice to make themselves fresh or to have lunch breaks. On the other hand, 21% of the study respondents showed that they were students who liked to visit fast food franchises with their friends. The study revealed that 12% of them were employers, 4.6 self-employed, 1.5% investors, 1.3% government officials and 4.6% were housework or parenting females.

Table 16 Positions of the customers

Position

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Student	82	21.0	21.1	21.1
Company employee	201	51.5	51.7	72.8
Employer	47	12.1	12.1	84.8
Self-employed	18	4.6	4.6	89.5
Investor	6	1.5	1.5	91.0
Valid Government official	5	1.3	1.3	92.3
Office and admin Job	12	3.1	3.1	95.4
Housework/parenti ng	18	4.6	4.6	100.0
Total	389	99.7	100.0	
Missing System	1	.3		
Total	390	100.0		

Figure 20 Graph Showing positions of Customers who Visit Pakistan’s fast Foods

4.8 Descriptive Statistics

The study had the success of the fast food franchises and six independent variables showing the key success factors of the fast food franchises. All these six variables are attained from the literature review and their roles shown in the success of fast food franchises in the study. This section offers the descriptive statistics of the study and its variables. The descriptive results of the study are show-cased in Table 4.10 below and show the number of items, mean, maximum, minimum and standard deviation of each variable.

Table 17 Table showing the Descriptive statistics of the mean score of each variable with maximum and minimum values for each variable

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender	390	1	2	1.41	.492
Age	390	1	3	1.89	.644
Position	389	1	8	2.53	1.739
NamFastFood	390	1	5	2.33	1.494
Visit Frequency	390	1	5	2.85	1.128
Convenience	390	1	4	1.36	.714
Price	390	1	4	2.00	1.158
Product Features	390	2	4	2.06	.346
Employee Competence	390	1	4	2.09	1.014
Atmosphere	390	1	3	1.74	.782
Brand Image	390	1	2	1.42	.494
Success	390	1	4	1.73	.976
Visit Reason/Convenience	390	1	2	1.43	.496
Visit Reason/Price	390	1	4	2.38	1.487
Visit Reason/Product	390	1	2	1.78	.413
Visit Reason/Emp.Com	390	1	2	1.37	.483
Visit Reason/Atmosph	390	1	2	1.77	.420
Visit Reason/BrandImg	390	1	4	2.70	1.223
Valid N (listwise)	389				

The findings in Table 17 This shows the mean score of each variable, with maximum and minimum values for each variable. For instance, the mean value for the independent variable, convenience, is 1.36 and the standard deviation is 0.714, which shows that the value is close to the mean and is not too much spread from the mean value. Likewise, the result of price as a variable shows that the mean value is 2.0, and it has a maximum value of 4 and a minimum value of 1, with a standard deviation of 1.15. This shows that the value of standard deviation is not exceedingly spread from the mean value of price and is a good sign. The response price is spread within the standard deviation of prices, and this shows that there was a narrow response and is a reflection that the respondents had consensus for this particular variable. The study by Saunders et al. (2007) shows that when the value of standard deviation is less than 1, it shows that there is consensus, as in the given descriptive statistics table, where we can see it for the variables of convenience, product features, atmosphere, and brand image. However, all these values for standard deviation are not far below 1, which shows that the majority of the study participants had similar viewpoints and there was not much deviation from the mean value.

The study also sought to create consensus for the independent variables if the participants of the study had consensus and had a similar viewpoint. The standard deviation for price and employee competence is greater than 1 and is near to the mean value of 2.0 and 2.09, respectively, which means that there is a consensus between the responses of the respondents. On the other hand, the results for convenience, product features, atmosphere, and brand image are lower than 1, which indicates that this study lacks consensus among the responses collected. However, the values show that the standard deviation is not spread further than the mean value. This indicates that all the participants in the study had consensus with each other.

4.9 Testing of Hypothesis-Correlation Testing

Hypothesis 1: Product features have significant and positive relationship with the success of fast food franchises.

According to the findings, there is a positive and significant relationship between product features and the success of fast food franchises, which is significant at the 0.05 percent level. The study, therefore, rejects the null hypothesis, which states that there is an insignificant relationship between product features and the success of franchising and accepts the alternative hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the product features and the success of fast food franchises. This means that if the fast food franchises improve their product features, their probability of success will be improved, and vice versa.

Table 18 Correlation between success and product features

Correlation between success and product features			
		Success	Product Features
Success	Pearson	1	.134**
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.008
	N	390	390
Product Features	Pearson	.134**	1
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	
	N	390	390

** . At the 0.01 level, correlation is significant (2-tailed).

Hypothesis 2: Convenience is an important key success factor of the fast food franchises

In order to determine the correlation between convenience and success, it is indicated from the statistical value in Table 19 that the correlation is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The value is 0.165, which is lower than the p value 0.01 and implies that we accept alternative hypothesis by rejecting null hypothesis. Hence, it is indicated that convenience in the fast food is the key success factor in fast food franchises in Pakistan from the customer’s perspective.

Table 19 Convenience and Success Correlation

Correlations

		Convenience	Success
Convenience	Pearson Correlation	1	.165**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	390	390
Success	Pearson Correlation	.165**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	390	390

** . At the 0.01 level, the correlation is significant (2 tailed).

Hypothesis 3: Pricing is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.

Pearson correlation test is used to find the relationship between pricing and the success of the fast food franchises. The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between price and success of the fast food franchises working in Pakistan at 0.01 level of significance. The null hypothesis is, therefore, rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted confirming that pricing has an important role in determining the success of the fast food franchises.

Table 20 Prices and Success Correlation

Correlations

		Success	Price
Success	Pearson Correlation	1	.540**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	390	390
Price	Pearson Correlation	.540**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	390	390

** . At the 0.01 level, the correlation is significant (2-tailed).

Hypothesis 4: Employee competence is the key success factor for the fast food franchises in Pakistan

The statistical results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between employee competence and the success of the fast food franchises in Pakistan at the 0.01 level of significance of 95% confidence interval. In other words, the findings show that $p < 0.05$ and reflects that if employee competence is increased, and improved, the probability of franchising success rate is also increased. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, that there is a positive and significant association between staff competency and the success of fast food franchises, is accepted.

Table 21 The correlation between success and the competence of employee(s)

Correlations

		Success	Employee Competence
Success	Pearson Correlation	1	.737**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	390	390
Employee Competence	Pearson Correlation	.737**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	390	390

** . At the 0.01 level, correlation is significant (2-tailed).

Hypothesis 5: Atmosphere is a key success factor in fast food franchises in Pakistan

Atmosphere has an important role in the success of the fast food franchises. The findings of the current study confirms the previous studies that atmosphere is positively linked with the success of the fast food franchises and the attained value is of $p < 0.05 = 0.446$. The value is significant at p level and is positively linked with the success of the fast food franchises. The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 22 Correlation between success and atmosphere

Correlations

		Success	Atmosphere
Success	Pearson Correlation	1	.446**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	390	390
Atmosphere	Pearson Correlation	.446**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	390	390

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis 6: Brand image is a key success factor in determining the success of the fast food franchises in Pakistan

From the calculated value of brand image at $p < 0.05$ is 0.596. This value is less than the value of p and is positively linked with the success of the fast food franchises. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table 23 Correlation between success and brand image

Correlations

		Success	Brand Image
Success	Pearson Correlation	1	.596**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	390	390
Brand Image	Pearson Correlation	.596**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	390	390

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 24 Table showing the Coordinates of Variables and their values

Correlations		Success	Convenience	Price	ProductFeatures	EmployeeComptence	Atmosphere	BrandImage
Success	Pearson Correlation	1	.165**	.540**	.130*	.737**	.446**	.596**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.000	.010	.000	.000	.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	88.269	21.846	116.000	8.308	68.308	64.654	54.577
	Covariance	.227	.056	.298	-.021	.176	.166	.140
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390
Convenience	Pearson Correlation	.165**	1	.491**	-.091	.000	-.067	-.301**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.000	.073	.999	.188	.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	21.846	198.297	158.000	-8.738	-.005	14.497	41.349
	Covariance	.056	.510	.406	-.022	.000	.037	-.106
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390
Price	Pearson Correlation	.540**	.491**	1	.154**	.488**	.437**	.306**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.002	.000	.000	.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	116.000	158.000	522.000	-24.000	-110.000	154.000	68.000
	Covariance	.298	.406	1.342	-.062	.283	.396	.175
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390
ProductFeatures	Pearson Correlation	.130*	-.091	-.154**	1	.168**	-.168**	-.151**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	.073	.002		.001	.001	.003
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	8.308	-8.738	-24.000	46.523	11.323	-17.662	-10.031
	Covariance	-.021	-.022	-.062	.120	.029	-.045	-.026
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390

EmployeeComptence	Pearson Correlation	.737**	.000	-.488**	.168**	1	-.852**	.897**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.999	.000	.001		.000	.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	-68.308	-.005	-110.000	11.323	97.190	129.595	-86.097
	Covariance	.176	.000	-.283	.029	.250	-.333	.221
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390
Atmosphere	Pearson Correlation	.446**	.067	.437**	-.168**	-.852**	1	.826**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.188	.000	.001	.000		.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	64.654	-14.497	154.000	-17.662	-129.595	237.797	124.049
	Covariance	.166	-.037	.396	-.045	-.333	.611	.319
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390
BrandImage	Pearson Correlation	.596**	-.301**	.306**	-.151**	-.897**	.826**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.003	.000	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	54.577	-41.349	68.000	-10.031	-86.097	124.049	94.874
	Covariance	.140	-.106	.175	-.026	-.221	.319	.244
	N	390	390	390	390	390	390	390

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 25 Table showing the grand Summary of the results of the hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Correlation	Result/Status
Convenience is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.	0.165	√ Accepted
Pricing is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.	0.540	√ Accepted
Product features is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.	0.134	√ Accepted
Employee competence is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.	0.737	√ Accepted
Atmosphere is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.	0.446	√ Accepted
Brand image is the key success factor of the fast food franchises.	0.596	√ Accepted

4.10 Regression Analysis

The impact of convenience, product features, pricing, atmosphere, employee competence, and brand image on the success of fast food franchises is analysed using regression analysis.

Overall, the results show that success is dependent on these predictor variables i.e., **convenience, product features, pricing, atmosphere, employee competence, and brand image**. The model summary Table shows the value of R, adjusted R square and standard error of the estimate. The R square shows that 71.6% of the success in fast food franchises is due to all these predictor variables: **convenience, product features, pricing, atmosphere, employee competence, and brand image**.

Table 26 Regression analysis

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.846 ^a	.716	.712	.256	.716	161.074	6	383	.000	.147

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image, Product Features, Price, Convenience, Atmosphere, Employee Competence

b. Dependent Variable: Success

In Table 27 below, the unstandardised coefficient B shows the intercept and the coefficient of each predictor variable. The significant p value shows the measure of probability that the distinction in results is executed by chance. The aforementioned model shows that the overall independent values have significant impacts on the entire success of the fast food franchises in which $p=0.000$ and is lower than 0.05.

Table 27 ANOVA

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	63.217	6	10.536	161.074	.000 ^b
	Residual	25.053	383	.065		
	Total	88.269	389			

a. Dependent Variable: Success

b. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image, Product Features, Price, Convenience, Atmosphere, Employee Competence

Table 28 Showing the Success of the Dependable Variable Success.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
	1	(Constant)	3.377			.279		12.102
	Convenience	.012	.028	.019	.436	.000	-.043	.068
	Price	.107	.016	.260	6.815	.000	.076	.138
	Product Features	.003	.038	.002	-.083	.000	-.079	.072
	Employee Competence	1.073	.081	1.126	-13.225	.000	-1.232	-.913
	Atmosphere	.429	.033	.704	-12.879	.000	-.495	-.364
	Brand Image	.091	.084	.094	1.086	.000	-.074	.256

a. Dependent Variable: Success

4.11 The Impact of Demographic Variables on Customers

The analysis for the impact of demographic variable, gender is evaluated on the frequency of visit to fast food outlets in Pakistan. The findings show that male have the more frequency of visits on weekly basis as compared to females in Pakistan. This is due to the reason that either they take their families or hang out with their friends after a long week for work. The cross tabulation analysis is carried out to test if there is any impact of gender on the frequency of visits. The results show that 20 males as compared to zero female visits daily, 167 males as compared to 28 female visit on weekly basis. However, only 18 males showed that they visit

on monthly basis as compared to 103 females. Overall, it shows that the demographic attribute, Gender, has an important role in determining the frequency of visits to the fast food outlets in Pakistan.

Table 29 Cross tabulation for gender and frequency of visits

Gender * Visit Frequency Crosstabulation

Count

		Visit Frequency					Total
		Daily	Weekly	Twice a week	Monthly	Once in six months	
Gender	Male	20	167	0	18	27	232
	Female	0	28	27	103	0	158
Total		20	195	27	121	27	390

Figure 21 Graph showing frequency of Gender Visits

Another important attribute age is also evaluated on the frequency of visits and showed that ages ranging between 25-35 years have more frequency of visits to the fast food franchises as compared to people with ages ranging from 35-45 years. However, people with ages ranging from 15 to 25 years also have more frequent visits to the fast food franchises in Pakistan.

Table 30 Cross tabulation for age and frequency of visit

Age * Visit Frequency Crosstabulation

Count

		Visit Frequency					Total
		Daily	Weekly	Twice a week	Monthly	Once in six months	
Age	15-25	20	84	0	0	0	104
	25-35	0	86	27	111	0	224
	35-45	0	25	0	10	27	62
Total		20	195	27	121	27	390

Figure 22 Graph showing frequency of Age-Group Visits

4.12 Conclusion

In this chapter, both qualitative and quantitative analyses have been carried out. In order to determine the impact of each predictor variable on the success of fast food franchises, the reason of visiting fast food franchises was evaluated. From the analysis, it is clear that with regard to convenience, customers revealed that 56.7% of the customers strongly agreed that they visit a fast food franchise due to convenience. Similarly, with regard to pricing attribute, the respondent revealed that it was one of the strong variables determining their reasons of visiting a particular fast food franchise. 209 out of 389 respondents strongly agreed that they visited a particular fast food franchise due to price factor; however, 175 disagreed on the statement that price persuaded them to visit a particular fast food outlet. Other attributes atmosphere, employee competence, brand image and product features are also determined as important predictors for influencing customer decision-making in visiting a particular fast food franchise.

Chapter 5- Findings and Discussion

5.0 Overview

This chapter aims to evaluate the findings of the research through comparing the data or information gathered from qualitative as well as quantitative methods with the literary works already reviewed. The idea is to gauge the effectiveness of the outcomes of this research and identify whether it will be able to contribute for the future research.

In the previous chapter, an in-depth analysis of the data and information gathered from the qualitative as well as the quantitative approaches have been discussed. For the qualitative approach, in-depth interviews and FGD's were conducted with the franchisees and or managers of fast-food chains in Pakistan in order to gain first-hand information in relation to the franchise's performance and to identify the main success factors in franchising operations within the industry.

On the other hand, quantitative data was collected by administering a survey with the fast-food customers who were visiting the fast-food restaurants. The researcher would pass on the survey to them while they wait for their orders. The questionnaire was self-administered and used a five-point Likert scale ranging 1 to 5 (1 strongly disagree, 2, disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree, 5 strongly agree). Both the methods were fully in line with the proposed hypothesis for this particular research and ensured that it achieved the research objectives by the end of it.

This chapter further explains and discusses the study's findings, highlighting the status and importance of the Pakistani franchise industry in terms of key determinants for success.

The following findings are derived from the study's findings. The findings are elaborated under hypothesised statements and objectives.

H1= Product features have significant and positive relationship with the success of fast food franchises

The hypothesis is accepted as there is a positive and significant relationship between product features and success of fast food franchises at $p=0.134$, which is significant at 0.01 % level.

H2= Convenience is an important key success factor of the fast food franchises

The hypothesis is accepted as there is a positive and significant relationship between convenience and success of fast food franchises at $p=0.165$, which is significant at 0.01 % level.

H3= Pricing is the key success factor of the fast food franchises

The hypothesis is accepted as there is a positive and significant relationship between price and success of the fast food franchises at $p=0.540$ which is significant at 0.01 % & level.

H4= Employee competence is the key success factor for the fast food franchises in Pakistan

The hypothesis is accepted as there is a positive and significant relationship between employee competence and success of the fast food franchises at $p=0.737$ which is significant at 0.01 % level.

H5= Atmosphere is a key success factor in fast food franchises in Pakistan

The hypothesis is accepted as there is a positive and significant relationship between atmosphere and success of the fast food franchises at $p=0.446$ which is significant at 0.01 % level.

H6= Brand image is a key success factor in determining the success of the fast food franchises in Pakistan

The hypothesis is accepted as there is a positive and significant relationship between brand image and success of the fast food franchises at $p=0.596$ which is significant at 0.01 % level.

The above hypothesis results show that all of the variables proposed in the study have a positive impact on determining the success of the fast food industry in Pakistan, and the null hypothesis is fully accepted.

5.1 Finding Through Qualitative Approach

The data analysis of the interviews was conducted with the management staff and the franchisees currently placed at large international fast-food chains in Pakistan. It was found out that brand image and the brand concept are two of the most significant aspects that make a fast-food chain successful in the region. For each of the fast-food chains, the respondents had different opinions to share but the cumulative effects of the findings recommended that the brand image with respect to product quality, product attributes and its overall pricing strategies tend to shape up the opinions of the customers about the fast-food restaurant altogether. Customers tend to prefer the brand they have adequate knowledge about, the business concept

for any restaurant chain is the overall impression the customers have about its resourcing capabilities, management capabilities and the fundamental qualities that make it gain an edge over the rest of the competition in the marketplace.

In modern times, the customers are exposed to a variety of options as they can get a wide range of prices to choose from, the different product attributes and the different processes that makes up a restaurant business different from the others in the marketplace. Business concept is heavily reliant upon the experiences of the customers and that is largely dependent upon the products or services they may be getting at the end of any transaction altogether. If the customers are able to associate with the brand it is due to the underlying business concept of the fast-food chain. An interviewee had clearly emphasized that it is due to the business concept that they were able to gain a competitive edge in the market.

By just receiving a “Halal” license and getting exclusive supply of its chicken and other ingredients, the interviewee seems to believe that it provided a fundamental advantage over the rest of the international fast-food chains operating in Pakistan. Pakistan is an Islamic state and it is fairly common that majority of the consumers may have some issues with international food chains with it being “Halal” or not and therefore, it is a need for the business to provide just what the customers demand to gain success in the long-run. As Roberts-Lombard (2009) had emphasized that if any restaurant business fails to offer “what” the customers really want from them, it will be swept away by the competition within the industry. Interviewees also have pointed out that the customers tend to prefer international fast-food chains in comparison with the local chains, based upon the impression they have built in their minds about the unique business concept they have to provide. For brand information, the conceptualization in the minds of the consumers is another essential elements since it constitutes how the individual attaches brand recognition and rates its brand performance altogether.

The business concept ensures that the customer is able to return to the same brand based on their previous experience with the brand as well as its products throughout. Brand concept is in a way interrelated with brand awareness that influences positive impacts in developing a strong and rather more stringent relations with the customers in their preferences of fast food (Sashi & Karuppur, 2002).

Thus, in this scenario, the following hypothesis is accepted as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4 of the thesis.:

From the customer's perspective, the business concept is the most important success factor in determining the success of fast-food restaurants.

A similar situation that is in a major way correlated with brand concept is that of brand awareness. Customers who are satisfied with an organization's "value added services," according to Esteves (2004), are able to link themselves to the brand, resulting in brand equity and brand awareness. This particular association with the brand can be in terms of association with the brand concept or with its products or its product attributes or simply the brand name itself. For instance, McDonalds is a big brand in the fast-food chain worldwide; people do not need to create an association with the chain in each individual location they see it; it is one single impression about the brand that either makes them like it or dislike it. Similarly, for one to go to McDonalds they will visit it with similar feelings in Pakistan and do the same in the U.S.A. or elsewhere that they spot its=the company's franchise.

As argued by Qu et al (2018) brand awareness comprises of the different brand attributes that makes the physical composition of any particular product. For a fast-food chain, the unique ingredients that make the food so delicious and rather different from the other competitors in the market is what makes its brand recall stronger for the consumers. For some customers, the unique taste and the ingredients would mean more but for some it will be non-physical attributes like that of price or its packaging or just the visual appearance of the product.

All these elements collectively account for the brand differentiation in the marketplace and enables the consumers to be able to opt for the one fast food franchise they prefer the most. Brand awareness also includes the ability of a particular brand or organization to be able to provide consistent quality products and services to gain its customers' loyalty in the long-run. All this eventually accounts for gaining an edge in the streams of revenues and the overall expenditures will also be reduced.

Thus, the following hypothesis is also accepted as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4.:

Brand awareness, brand image, brand attributes and promotion and revenue growth have positive relation with each other in the fast food franchised outlets.

There are still certain elements that did not really matter for the Pakistani consumers in general like the atmosphere of the restaurant. Research suggests that people tend to prefer fast food restaurants since it's a quick meal that they can just get on the go, the atmosphere of the fast-food chains does not really seem to matter in the majority of cases. Customers generally prefer "Take away" approach where customers collect their orders and leave the premises of the restaurant (Noor, et al, 2018). But still, that does not totally overlook the cleanliness of the outlets or its general physical appearance, the colour coding and the simple idea of branding the fast food franchise is what gains the attention of the customers. In Pakistan, KFC, McDonalds and Pizza Hut are all known for the attractive atmosphere of their restaurants, the hygiene and cleanliness regime at their outlets is kept like a benchmark and mostly the branding tactic that enables the customers to set one brand apart from the other. People tend to associate with these brands due to their unique branding and the perceptions they have in the minds of the consumers.. Research suggests that if the restaurant is successfully able to maintain these elements, they can significantly contribute to earning the brand loyalty of the customers to that specific brand in the long-term (Nakao et al., 2019). As Ottenbacher et al., (2009) has pointed it out, the customers do not prefer those fast food restaurants that are comparatively maintained in a poor manners and the cleanliness and hygiene is overlooked at their outlets..

The standardization in the atmosphere only enables the business to have a constant image in the marketplace and its overall brand image also stays same throughout in the minds of the consumers. As they say, people recall McDonalds wherever they see two gold arches flashing; that is the kind of brand recall every single fast food restaurant needs to build in the long-term. For future researchers, it is recommended to look for more options on the atmosphere of the fast food franchises and be able to stress more on the detailed specifics of the environment of the restaurants. It is quite a big deal in the servicing industry to establish a healthy environment for the customers to return back to you over and over again. This is what ultimately accounts for the success of any franchise in the fast food business.

However, for this particular research, the following hypothesis is rejected as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4. of the thesis:

From the customer's perspective, the atmosphere is the most important component in determining the success of a fast food restaurant.

In addition, the null hypothesis has been accepted.

According to the statistical study in Chapter 4 of the thesis, *atmosphere is not the most important aspect in determining the success of a fast food restaurant from the customer's perspective*.

Another success factor that has been discussed with the interviewees was that of an attractive product mix that basically results in the profitability of fast-food restaurants specifically.

In one study carried out in the UK region, McDonalds, which is an internationally famous fast-food chain and known for its hamburgers, was enforced by this target market to serve “new healthful alternatives” of pasta salad, fruit bags and corn-on-the cob alongside traditional burger and chicken food. Since the primary motive of McDonalds was to gain a significant position in the UK market, it had to revamp its product mix in order to gain mass appeal within this region (Sarstedt and Mooi, 2014).

The interviewees have collectively emphasized that majority of the customers repeat their purchase decisions in relation to fast food chain preferences when they feel that the quality attributes within a particular product mix are far superior and are unlikely to be found in the domestic fast-food chains altogether.

Thus, even in this scenario, the following hypothesis is accepted as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4. of the thesis:

Product mix is a key success factor for the fast-food restaurant from the customer perspective.

Another element that evidently provides for a restaurant's business success in any region is that of employee competence. As identified by Monge et al (2017) and Mohd Sidik (2014), employee competence is one of the care aspects in fast food businesses that contributes for its success in the future. This employee competence is achieved through extensive training of the labour force on the lines of establishing strong ties with the customers and be able to attract as much business as possible.. Customers rely on employee competence in the event that an issue arises or they have a complaint about the service; it is the employee's competence that ensures that the customers are satisfied with the products and services once more. The employee is the one middle person between the fast-food system and the customer that helps in the building of stronger and longer relations together.

Thus, the following hypothesis is also accepted as proven in Chapter 4 of the thesis:

From the perspective of the customer, employee competence is the most important success factor in determining the success of fast-food restaurants.

So far, it can be seen that the fast-food chains operating in Pakistan need to be fully equipped in terms of highly competent employees, excellent business concept and a unique product mix that is able to attract the target customers and keep them engaged with the brand for the long-term. The fast-food business in Pakistan is really large, with multiple international fast-food chains and local chains as well. Evidently, the international fast-food chains have an edge over the local fast-food chains as they have superior business concepts and the employee competence is far superior to the locals in Pakistan. If the local fast-food chains need in order to get a competitive advantage in the market, they need to invest more on the business concept and the training of its employees. The international fast-food chains have some set international standards that their employees are required to stick to it in every manner whereas the local fast-food chains operating in Pakistan have less regulations to operate within the local markets. In order to compete with the likes of KFC, McDonalds and Pizza Hut, the local fast-food joints must adopt some stringent regulatory framework in order to gain a stronger brand presence within the marketplace.

As another interviewee has highlighted that for him the most important aspect about a fast food restaurant is that of managerial experience. The knowledge and the experience of the manager helps the business in tapping into the domestic markets more effectively. There have been so many examples in Pakistan itself that the businesses which lacked managerial experience were not able to survive in the market for long. Managerial experience is still not the most essential aspect for majority of the interviewees in this research. It can be reviewed more in detail in future research studies with some reference to how managerial experiences differ from international fast food chains compared to local fast food chains in Pakistan.

The following hypothesis could, therefore, not be accepted for this research as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4 of the thesis.

From the customer's perspective, managerial expertise is the most important aspect in determining the success of a fast food establishment

And instead of research, the null hypothesis is accepted, as shown in the statistical analysis in Chapter 4 of the thesis:

From the perspective of the client, managerial expertise is not the most important aspect in determining the success of a fast food restaurant

The most important element that potentially accounts for the success or failure of fast-food restaurants is that of price. In modern times, wherever customers have access to easy information, they can easily get price comparisons with the rest of the competition in the industry and make informed choices as per the pricing they seem to prefer. Even if the customers do not have the exact figures, due to the rapid use of the Internet and other smart communication technologies, the customers can still easily get an estimate on which they price fast food chains and as to which ones are the cheaper ones. According to Monge et al. (2017), the perceived price is demonstrated as one of the most essential attributes that affects the consumers' purchase decision as well as helping in determining the reason for considering any specific restaurant.

As proposed by Mueller & Kleiner (2004), if the customers are satisfied with the attributes of the product, its cleanliness, its quality and they agree to spend more on what they perceive as the quality content. This means that they are actually paying for the quality they get for the food more than anything else in the entire deal. This is exactly what the interviewees have stressed on as well, for Pakistani customers, the product and the superior service is what they will pay the high prices for at these fast-food chains.

Thus, the following hypothesis is also accepted as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4 of the thesis:

Price is the key success factor for determining the success of fast-food restaurant from the customer perspective.

The interviewees were not just asked about the success factors that were to be tested for the hypothesis purpose of this research. The interviewees were all experienced franchisees who had some significant command over their relevant field's unique dynamics altogether. As one interviewee pointed out that profitability for any franchise business is boosted through its effective marketing strategies.

Another essential aspect that was highlighted by the interviewees was the significance of customer purchasing power that was also quite an essential element for the sales growth of the

franchise business collectively. This can be identified by gaining a fuller understanding of consumer behaviour that helps in determining their ability or mere intent to purchase any product or avail any new service. This can further be considered a crucial element for the success of operating activities in the different business units. Evidently, the relation of the franchisee and the customers is two sided where the customers are involved in reacting towards the business tactics and the franchises responding to the ever-evolving consumer trends in the specific marketplace.

As Nyadzayo et al (2016) suggested that the physical presence of a restaurant is an essential factor that can affect its success or failure that is one aspect to look at it but it is also important for restaurants to give adequate consideration to their online presence as well. . The accessibility and visibility of a restaurant are elements which are related to convenience and location but it is not only limited to that; now these restaurants need to be equally involved in the online market to gain more prominence in the eyes of their customers in terms of convenience.

In different studies, it has been pointed that the reason behind the density within the fast-food chains in any corner of the world is due to the convenience it provides to not just the customers but also to the business owners (Fpumo and Moriera, 2020; Muller, 2015). It is quickly prepared and has relatively streamlined recipes that include monotonous tasks, like preparing a burger can easily get timed if it is done over and over again, or the frying of chicken or fries can be easily put on timer and once it is done it can be served to the customers. The processes involving within a fast-food restaurant are comparatively straight forward and do not require much effort once the workers are in sync to repeat it again and again.

Convenience is not restricted to the location or the accessibility of a fast-food restaurant; it also includes the way the customers are being served by these fast-food restaurants. Studies suggest that technological advances and the changing customer needs have contributed to the use of disposable serving, eating and packaging items. This has improved the convenience of using restaurant products for the consumers (Zhang, 2015). This idea of disposable packaging is appealing to the customers who are looking for quick bite options and have other errands or important tasks to do on the side. We are living in a fast-paced world where everyone is continuously on the run and literally people do not have time to spend hours at a restaurant to grab a meal and sit to eat; and therefore, that is where the main motive of fast-food chains comes to play.

Fast food chains are developed with this mere objective of providing wholesome fresh and hot meals to the customers while they are on the go. More than about the food taste and the quality of the products being served at these fast-food chains, the prompt service and the fresh food served within a span of 10-15 minutes is what makes it so preferable amongst the other choices irrespective of the age groups. Researchers have pointed out that convenience is one key aspect that is the most influential factor when it comes to customers' interests in visiting food outlets. This only further implies that convenience is a main contributing factor in making a fast-food restaurant success or failure.

Nevertheless, the participants that were interviewed for this particular research had nothing to specifically mention about whether the location or the particular ease factor that is experienced by fast food factors is actually a success factor for their business. The interviewee did know that the pricing of the menu items needed to be carefully planned out in order to attract the attention of the customers. Since there are so many players present in the marketplace, it is of utmost significance that the fast-food chains are able to defend their pricings in order to appeal to the mass markets.

Convenience is predominantly a factor that is considered in studies as a foundation of success for any restaurant and mostly for fast food restaurants. Customers tend to come to fast food chains for the convenience it provides in terms of service, price and quality altogether with minimal time consumed on the eating part as well. Evidently, Mohd Sidik (2014) linked convenience with the location, hours of operational activities and the speed of delivering service; however, it may vary across the food restaurants. It is, therefore, recommended that even the fast-food chains that are operating in Pakistan need to invest more on making their services as speedy as possible in order to gain the prominent attention from their consumers in the long-term.

Location is again a vital element in determining convenience for the consumers; therefore, the fast-food restaurants must put a lot of thinking into the picking the ideal locations for the setting of their businesses. However, there is still not much mention by the participants during the interviews on the convenience that their fast-food restaurant may be providing to them in the long-term.

Hence, the following hypothesis denies the argument regarding location conveniences as proven in the statistical analysis in chapter 4 of the thesis:

From the customer's perspective, convenience is the most important aspect in determining the success of a fast-food establishment.

And, as shown in the statistical analysis in Chapter 4 of the thesis, the null hypothesis is accepted:

Convenience is not the most important element in determining the success of a fast-food restaurant from the customer's perspective.

From the past studies it can be seen that usually, convenience can act as a major competitive edge factor in fast food services market because in such segment, customers want to choose their products from a hanging menu and want to receive the order as soon as they make order and or make payments at the point of sale.

This study just provides some foundation on this aspect and the few researchers can take this study forward and explore the convenience aspect that might have been overlooked during this research. Convenience is evidently a significant aspect about fast food restaurants and for customers it is a highlighting point as well. the Future researchers can explore this aspect from the consumer's point of view and do not inquire about anything from the franchisees about their opinions on this particular factor as to whether it is a success factor or not. When any customer approaches a fast-food restaurant, the speedy delivery, the prompt service, "easy on the pocket" aspect and food available on the go are the key aspects that one really sees.

Customer services are generally at the heart of the majority of the franchise business, as mentioned by several authors in the literary works reviewed. The consumers tend to give much regard to those companies that potentially value their customers and ensure that they are providing them with the best customer services. It is assumed that these companies' top priorities are to avail the best services, purchases and the best products at the best prices collectively. It is a known fact that customer services are likely to elevate the expenses of the major business sectors, but just specifically to the restaurant businesses, the customers are willing to spend an extra 18% or more on the added services they may be getting at these restaurants (Asemi & Jazi, 2010). This percentage only indicates that the customers regard the services provided at these restaurants with utmost importance and this is one aspect that the franchisees cannot overlook under any circumstances.

Also, future researchers can shed some light upon the importance of the atmosphere and the ambiance in a fast-food restaurant. Past studies suggest that customers do not spend much of their time in the restaurant; therefore, the atmosphere of the restaurant seems less important in the prospect of fast-food franchising. Even the majority of the fast food franchises are based on “Take away” approaches where customers collect their orders and leave the premises of the restaurant.

Usually, when the customers make choices, the atmosphere seems to have least importance in the fast food chains. However, cleanliness of the outlet, its physical appearance, colours and branding organization will be those elements that primarily attract the customer’s attention towards the restaurant (Noor et al., 2018). This also counts under the convenience aspect that consumers usually opt for, they do not look at the atmosphere, all they want is a quick service and this is also one of the reasons as to why in the fast food restaurants consumers get the “drive thru” option as well. If the customer is in a rush and wants to grab some food in a hurry while, they are travelling or have to be at a meeting or an appointment, drive-thru is the option to go for. Even though, the atmosphere may have some influence, it is not necessary that it will not be considered by the customer altogether. There are researchers that have put significant emphasis upon the added influence that physical stimuli puts on the customers. Evidently, many marketing scholars have recognized that if the customers have increased stimuli for the physical environment of the restaurant, their purchasing intentions are significantly influenced and in return, the sales revenue of the outlet (O’Gorman, 2009).

5.2 Findings Through Quantitative Approach

The previous section discussed qualitative analysis on the data collected through in-depth interviews carried out on franchisers. This section discusses the quantitative data collected through survey questionnaires that were handed out to a total sample size of 390 respondents. The sampling technique used is convenient sampling and the overall response rate is 99.7% by ensuring the non-response rate and the responses with incomplete information. The instrument was tested for reliability. The instrument for calculating the validity and reliability of items used in the study is tested through Cronbach alpha. The test had shown positive outcomes and showed a reliability of 0.805 or 80.5% that shows the instrument was highly reliable for running the survey. The items in the questionnaires all measure the respondents’ inclination towards significant outcomes in the study.

The frequency charts helped in identifying the demographic division of the sample. The majority of the respondents are Males (59.5%) belonging to the age group of 25 to 35 years (57.4%). The findings show that McDonalds (43.1%) is the most preferred franchise by the customers due to the key success factors associated with the brand. Then comes KFC (22%), Hardees (10%), Subway (16.2%) and Burger King (8.7%).

The frequency Tables also helped in determining the frequency of visits of a potential customer to their preferred franchise. A large percentage of the respondents (50%) showed that they usually preferred going to their favorite restaurants on a weekly basis. The majority of the respondents also belonged to the working sector and were company employees (51.5%). This implied that the people who preferred going to fast food restaurants usually preferred to go out for a quick bite during their lunch breaks or a quick break to grab a bite that was convenient for them.

Fast food is considered to be a meal that is quickly prepared and people can enjoy it on the run. The findings of these demographics suggest that mostly males who go out for work, prefer fast food over other cuisines due to the convenience and ease it provides to them through its quick preparation and easy access altogether. Research suggests that the majority of the fast food franchises are based on “Take away” or making use of the “Drive thru” approach where customers collect their orders, leave the premises of the restaurant and enjoy the meal on the go. If the customers are in a rush, want to grab food in a hurry, they are travelling or have to be at a meeting or have to join back work or an appointment, drive-thru and take away are the options to go for.

Convenience is predominantly a factor that is considered in studies as a foundation of success for any restaurant and mostly for fast food restaurants. Customers tend to come to fast food chains for the convenience it provides in terms of service, price and quality together with the minimal time consumed while eating as well (Mohd Sidik, 2014).

The effect of the six independent variables on the success of fast food franchises was tested using descriptive statistical analysis in this study. The descriptive statistics including the variables of convenience, product features and atmosphere and brand image were less than 1 that showed there was a consensus, reflecting towards all participants having similar

viewpoints with respect to these variables and have not had much deviation. Evidently, product features played a significant role in determining the success rate of a fast food restaurant. There is a positive relationship between the product features and success of fast food franchise with a significant level of 0.05%. This is exactly what a respondent also recommended in the interview that, in Pakistan, the majority of customers anticipate franchises are comparatively expensive and costly in the local markets. However, if the franchise is able to give them exceptional experience through high quality product features and offer them that product mix that effectively targets the preferences of customers, they can make significant profits and lead towards record revenue. This means that if the fast food franchises improve their product features, their probabilities of success will be improved and vice versa.

Convenience is another significant factor for determining the success of fast food franchises in Pakistan. The correlation between convenience and success is significant at 0.01 level of significance. The accessibility and visibility of a restaurant are elements which are related to each convenience and location. Zhang (2015) has noted that convenience is determined as the most influential factor when it comes to the customer's interest in visiting food outlets. This shows that convenience is a contributing factor in making a food restaurant a success or failure. Convenience means the restaurant facilitates its customers through its quick services.

The central location can mean a lot to the customer and can play a significant role in attracting them to a given trade area. It is considered that every retail location is likely to have its own unique attributes with respect to the demand it gets which is based on the store outlets present in that location by ensuring that the offerings are in line with the requirements of the market as well (Jaravaza & Chitando, 2013).

Pricing is another key factor determining the success of a fast food restaurant. The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between price and success of the fast food franchises working in Pakistan at 0.01 level of significance. Researchers have pointed out that the fast food chain owners have to be very careful in establishing strong grounds for the pricing models of their businesses as it is given utmost importance in shaping up the buying behaviors in the customers altogether. As proposed by Mueller & Kleiner (2004), if the customers are satisfied with the features of the product, its cleanliness, its quality and they agree to spend more on what they perceive as quality content, this means that they are actually paying for the quality they get for the food more than anything else in the entire package. Even if the prices

are high, the customer will be more than happy to pay the price for it and therefore scholars have stressed on putting adequate thinking into planning for pricing.(Fpumo and Moriera, 2020).

Another significant variable that has been tested for determining its overall effect on the success of the franchise is that of employee competence. There is a positive and significant relationship between employee competence and success of fast food franchises in Pakistan at 0.01 level of significance. This reflects upon the significant need for hiring highly competent employees at the fast food restaurants to ensure the long term success of the business. The competition is getting fierce in the industry and it has put significant pressure on the fast food businesses specifically on employing competent and high expertise employees. A key success factor identified through the studies by Monge et al (2017) and Mohd Sidik (2014) is employees' competence. This key factor can be derived from training the labor force in addition to establishing personal relationships with customers and a variety of other tasks that may be considered crucial for driving the success of a potential fast food business. The food enterprise is a labor intensive industry and the linkage between customers and personnel is important and for that employee competence plays a significant role in determining its overall success in the long-run.

Atmosphere is another crucial element that plays an important role in the success of the fast food franchises. Atmosphere is positively linked with the success of the fast food franchises and the attained value is of $p < 0.05 = 0.446$ that refers to the positive relation between the two. The cleanliness of the outlet, its physical appearance, color coordination and branding organization will be those elements that primarily attract the customer's attention towards the restaurant. If the restaurant is successfully able to maintain these elements, they can significantly contribute to earning the brand loyalty of the customers to that specific outlet. Atmosphere may mean different things to different individuals but in the case of fast food franchises, it refers to the collective environment that the business is willing to provide to its customers. Research has shown mixed views on the significance of atmosphere but mostly it has shown that atmosphere mostly works as stimuli in generating revenues for the business.

Researchers like Monge et al., (2017) claim that the impact of atmosphere specifically in the service industry has a great influence because services are produced and consumed at the same time; therefore, this part of the restaurant constitutes an important factor in the sustainability of the restaurant business. Noor et al (2018) noted that if the restaurant makes adequate

measures for “atmospheric planning”, it can make a huge difference between the long-term business failure and success.

Lastly brand image is considered the most significant and crucial factor in determining the success of the fast food restaurants. This factor also has a significant positive relationship itself and the success of fast food businesses. When tested on the Pearson Correlation scale, it was found out that employee competence and Brand Image have the highest correlation out of all the other elements at 73.7% and 59.6% respectively.

To sum it up, all the variables do have some significant positive relationship with the success of a fast food franchise business with Employee Competence and Brand Image having a more significant positive relation than the rest of the variables. The weakest correlation can be seen in variables of Product Features and Convenience with 13% and 16.5% respectively. Mohd Sidik (2014) linked convenience with the location, hours of operational activities and the speed of delivering service, however, it may vary across the food restaurants. Nevertheless, convenience is observed as the influential factor for making a purchase decision but still it cannot be singled out as the most significant factor in determining the success of the restaurant. Even in the case of product features, it is not necessary to effectively contribute to the long term success of the fast food restaurant.

As argued by Mueller and Kleiner (2004), if the business wants to establish competitive advantage, this can be done by developing key success factors. This is exactly what this research aims at: to evaluate, the key success factors responsible for running a fast food restaurant in Pakistan. Pakistan is an Islamic nation and a country is based in the Middle East where the market norms and values are largely different in comparison with the West. For international franchises like McDonalds, KFC and Burger King Etc., they are required to adopt certain standards to operate in an effective manner within the region.

As the interviews suggested and the surveys conducted on the particular sample of population, there were some factors that contributed more towards the success of the fast food franchises than the rest. As Roberts-Lombard (2009) suggests, if any restaurant business fails to offer “what” the customers really want from them, it will be swept away by the competition within the industry. The survey findings propose that the employee competence and the brand image have a stronger relation with the success of the business than the rest of the factors. Brand image can merely mean the brand’s impression in the minds of the customers that enables them

to go to the fast-food restaurant again and again. It is only created once in the consumers' minds and the marketers are recommended to plan on developing the brand image carefully and strategically in the marketplace. Similarly, employee competence is another significant element that is developed through extensive training and learning of the staff and people employed by the fast-food restaurants. The more competent the staff is, they tend to comfort and fulfil the needs of the customers in an effective manner. The idea is to ensure that the customers are satisfied and their needs are fulfilled in every manner. This is the power of a powerful business that the customer's blindly rely upon the products and services being offered to them by a franchise that is as competent as the customers assume it to be.

5.3 Answer to the Research Question

Following data analysis, the answer to the research question was discovered. Although all the six variables showed a positive relationship and the hypothesis were well accepted in the research but the correlational analysis showed that Employee competence, Brand Image, Price and Atmosphere have a stronger relation in determining the success of the fast-food franchises and Product features and Convenience have relatively a weaker relation. This research is extremely beneficial to franchisees and other fast food business owners in Pakistan who are struggling with their businesses. It will enable international franchising brands to adopt their business practises in line with the variables and their significance to the business in order to achieve success.

The below table 31 indicates the comparative analysis of the success factors through existing literature vs the new finding through research questions and objective of this study.

This below comparative analysis will facilitate the decision making process to the local and international franchises companies, and to analyse and evaluate Pakistan fast food franchise industry by realising the ranking of the important factors.

Table 31 Comparison of literature hypothesised and research findings

	Ranked by literature hypothesis	Ranked by Research findings
Employee Competence	3	1
Brand Image	6	2

Pricing	4	3
Atmosphere	5	4
Convenience	2	5
Product Mix	1	6

Employee competence is a major concern for both the consumer and the franchisee. It was also discovered in theory, demonstrating the significance of this factor. The franchisee bases the business's long-term viability on the availability of competent employees who can provide excellent customer service while also running the franchised business smoothly.

As these all research objectives are aligned with research questions. Therefore the below findings through data analysis are discussed to show their link with the study objectives.

5.4 Conclusions on the Objectives for the Research

5.4.1 Objective 1: To find out the key success factors of the food franchising system in Pakistan.

The survey findings helped in gaining a deeper understanding about the variables that have a more significant and positive impact on the success of fast-food businesses in comparison with the rest of the variables. Although all the six variables showed a positive relationship and the hypothesis were well accepted in the research but the correlational analysis showed that Employee competence, Brand Image, Price and Atmosphere have a stronger relation in determining the success of the fast-food franchises and Product features and Convenience have relatively a weaker relation. Thus objective 1 have been achieved,

5.4.2 Objective 2: To find out the importance of these key success factors in Pakistan's franchising system.

It is common for all customers coming to a fast-food franchise that they may be valuing some characteristics of the fast-food franchise more than the others and it may be the opposite for

the next customer coming in. It is all based upon the perception of the customers as to which particular variable gets them attracted towards a fast-food franchise altogether. Brand image plays a significant role in creating a significant brand impression in the minds of the customers that enables them to go to the fast-food restaurant again and again. It is only created once in the consumers' minds and this is why marketers are recommended to plan on developing the brand image carefully and strategically in the marketplace to gain a competitive edge. This underlies the importance of key success factors in Pakistan's franchising system. Thus Objective 2 is achieved.

Fast food business is an extremely competitive market with respect to Pakistan, there are local as well as international players in the industry that makes it more and more demanding from the customer's perspective. There are a variety of options available to the customers and if any one fast food business is unable to gain the attention of the consumers or keep them satisfied for a longer period, the business will fail drastically in terms of revenues and eventually will be swept away by other potential competitors.

5.4.3 Objective 3: The impact of these success factors in Pakistan's franchising system.

This research is extremely helpful for the franchisees and the different fast food business owners who are struggling in Pakistan with respect to their business. The different variables that have been tested are in relation to gauging their contribution towards determining the success of the fast-food business in the long-term. Marketers can plan marketing initiatives and the entire business concept by keeping these variables and their significance to the business portfolio in mind altogether. This clearly depicts the impact of these success factors in Pakistan's franchising system. Thus, objective 3 is achieved.

5.4 The Reaction of Pakistan Franchising Stakeholder to COVID-19

This study previously discussed the revenue generated by the franchising sector in Pakistan and supports the key argument by Qu et al (2018) that the Pakistani franchising sector is responsible for offering a number of direct jobs to people in the country. But the recession caused by COVID-19 would definitely have a negative influence on the economy of Pakistan in regard to employment and loss of revenue.

The Government of Pakistan took various measures to mitigate the risk of this pandemic crisis and contributed their best activities on the fast food franchising sector. For instance, it developed advocacy initiatives with the state-level authorities and with banks, financial institutions and put in their efforts on webinar and online discussions with franchisees, international franchisors and other interlinked players. From April 10 till April 17, 2020, three webinars and round table discussions were carried out. The documentation analysis shows that such webinars and discussion included a total of 18 franchisors, 20 franchisees and managers and 6 consultants. The entire discussion focused on the approaches carried out by franchisors and franchisees during pandemic crisis and evaluated their ways of handling food service, delivery services, ambience, health and hygiene and strategies for partnering with businesses during pandemic challenges.

In the next sections, we tend to review the key ideas discussed about the following five areas: primary measures taken by them, discussion with suppliers and landlords, adopting relevant business model and the relationship between franchisor and franchisee and franchisee with customers. Some important findings are extracted from the data provided in relevant documents uploaded on official site of Pakistan federation of franchises.

5.4.1 The Primary Measures were Emergency Care and Safety

Initially, when the wave of corona virus spread; the franchisors and franchisees shut their doors for customers at the end of March 2020. Primarily, the initial measures were taken to revise their budgets and they also dealt with their employees. The fundamental concern was, to find ways and reserve their cash flow. This was done by decreasing their cost structure, and by keeping a major part of their profit through other channels.

The franchisees eliminated their unnecessary costs. They reduced their consulting services, communication services, their repair costs and maintenance. Multiple organisations decided to

lay off their contracts with their contractual employees but permanent employees were facilitated to take their vacation and work remotely from their homes. However, fast food franchises cannot be entirely shifted to remote workplaces because the work involves cooking and the making of food and then deliver them to customers; thus, isolation and social distancing measures were also introduced to those who were vulnerable to the corona virus. Once franchises initiated isolation measures to those who were infected or social distancing to the remaining employees, the temporary suspension of employment contracts were reduced and also workers were recalled working for less hours than usual.

In the meantime, franchisees began to avail the credit lines and funded the salaries of their employees in Pakistan. As the prospect of the Pakistan government stimulating measures, private banks acted as middle agencies between public banks and organisations and initiated their credit lines to their customers. Despite all, there were various firms that did not experience smooth processes and reported trouble in attaining their credit lines as there was a huge distinction between the civic and private banks and the way each bank managed their credit line process. This is a general viewpoint about initial strategies that were needed to be revised and monitored by relevant franchisees and managers, persistently. There was one franchisee who during the semi-interview section stated that we were living in the contemporary moment and due to COVID-19, there was a huge uncertainty about our decisions because paths are not clear to anyone during the pandemic. However, it still seems that these primary initiatives were helpful in alleviating the impact of the coronavirus from the general public.

5.4.2 The relationship between all the relevant parties is increasingly turning close

Discussions with different suppliers and commercial real estate landlords were equally important to assure the financial room for both the franchisors and the franchisees. Such discussions are complex because all the relevant parties are trying to decrease their costs and keep a major part of their income and revenue. The suppliers of franchising facilities are also badly affected by the pandemic crisis. Usually, the shopping malls are reliant on their rents and fees. Even to the extent that, some people who own street stores are also the sole earners for their families and for them rent from such franchise outlets was their primary source. As mentioned by one of the customers during the focus group discussions, they had their relatives who own franchising and for them, rent from the franchise units were primary sources of income.

In the given situation, the challenge that discussion with suppliers and landlords would end in a loss-to-lose situation, stakeholders in Pakistan shared similar visions with each other and showed considerable flexibility for each other's demands. The focus group discussion shows that franchisees were seeking ways of negotiating with all their suppliers and service providers and it seemed beneficial for them because of the scale and it was good to discuss as part of the network than to discuss the things individually with each other.

There are various shopping malls in Pakistan that allowed food chains to remain open and deliver their services to their customers at their homes. Even, there were some shopping malls that allowed their franchise outlets to either delay their payments or to cancel their rent payments for the time period that did not show any revenue or profits. Some suppliers worked their ways to postpone their payments or to temporary suspend their payments. However, this study shows that in the pandemic crisis of COVID-19, many suppliers and landlords did not forward any alternatives to franchisees for the long term, which is why they were concerned about the ways to negotiate with their suppliers and landlords and govern their businesses post COVID-19. The franchisee of one of the fast food outlets "McDonalds" during an interview stated that they were seeking ways for more transparent discussions with their suppliers and their criteria was flexible that will definitely bring back their revenue.

From this study, it is evident that the majority of the suggested measures by the government of Pakistan to the franchisees included the postponement of rent till the end of the year 2020. The majority were exempted from their deductions for tax purposes and also their fee for royalty was also exempted for the year 2020, which was a good sign for all franchisees as this time relaxation would help them re-establish their business.

5.4.3 It was important, but it is unavoidable

In the given context of the pandemic crisis, franchisors and franchisees started implementing flexibility in their business models and decreased the impact of the crisis. Various developments were seen as important in the medium to long term and are now considered as integral to this whole process of franchising. The most notable change is the way how franchisees have adopted technology because this pandemic crisis has steered pertinent trends related to customer's behaviour and organizational structure, having been affected by every part of the business. Technologies that were previously regarded as experimental processes

were now in the form of online shopping and digitalization seemed like most important business development process that could save businesses from the existing crisis.

In some of the fast food franchises, delivery to home is seen as the first time business services and now delivery is regarded as the one that will definitely continue in the upcoming years. Those franchises that did not invest in technology are now focusing on this model of digitalization and home delivery with the implementation of various technologies like big data and robotics. Other business models are also recently initiated like “dark-kitchen model”, where franchisees make their meals ready and are then delivered to their customers. According to the franchisees of the given study (findings of the study), they have a plan to initiate dark-kitchen that will help them function only meals for home deliveries and eventually will reduce their cost structure.

5.4.4 Creating Connection between Franchisors and Franchisee

The arrangement of the franchising model fosters the exchange of information and ideas that will help them decrease the adverse effects of this pandemic crisis. The teamwork between the franchisors and the franchisees enable them to respond more quickly and make prompt decisions with immense predictability. The franchisor provides financial and managerial support for their franchisees and in the same manner franchisees facilitates their franchisors to recognize threats and challenges in the given context. The findings of this study shows that the franchising sector in Pakistan is adequately dealing with the current crisis and are working in collaboration with each other with more flexible and adaptable rules and concepts. So far, there is a positive and healthy connection between franchisors and franchisees during this pandemic crisis as redesigning business models would enable each of these parties to negotiate safety measures and understand consumer behaviour.

5.5 Conclusion

The majority of the franchisees are making investments on their communication processes that facilitates their connections with their stakeholders and they can overcome the negative impacts of pandemic crisis. Overall, the consequences of pandemic crisis on fast food franchises is devastating as it will affect consumer behaviour; however, building long-term relations with digital business models and repositioning their brands with focus on the marketing agenda and sustainability measures would lead them towards long term success.

The findings of this study revealed that customers are considerably concerned about their primary requirements like health and safety measures, safe delivery of food to their homes and healthy food that is free from any harmful germs. As mentioned by one of the customers in the given study that they were facing considerable challenges and they needed healthy food that prioritised their safety. Although, the given pandemic crisis shows that around 80% of the consumers are buying only essential food items (Fpumo and Moriera, 2020), those franchises that offer health and safety measures to their customers are still progressing. In addition, consumers seem increasingly concerned with environmental sustainability and social issues that require franchises to restructure their business and understand their customer preferences.

Chapter 6- Conclusion, Contribution and Recommendations

6.0 Introduction

This chapter provides the conclusion to the thesis. It discusses the conclusions made on the all the three objectives of the research. The contributions made to knowledge literature and practice have all been discussed in the chapter. The thesis makes eight (8) main recommendations and expresses the need for future research in the subject and topic area.

6.1 Conclusion

This study investigated the franchising business model in the food industry in Pakistan. The study was able to develop and also analyze different theoretical models of predictors that helped in determining the impact of key factors that are responsible for enhancing the quality of the franchisor-franchisees relationship and eventually account for the success of the business in the long-term.

The research questions of the research were focused on the evaluation of the factors related to franchisee that affect their franchise performances in Pakistan and thoroughly discussed the critical success factors of international food franchising according to the existing literature (Muller, 2015; Fpumo and Moriera, 2020). This contributed to existing literature and filled in gaps that were missing in the literature relating to franchising in Pakistani's fast food industry.

The findings of the research are based upon the data collected through interviews of franchisees and by carrying out surveys on the customers of the international fast food restaurants based in Pakistan. For each of the fast-food chains, the franchisees had different opinions to share but the cumulative effects of the findings recommend that the brand image with respect to the product quality, product attributes and its overall pricing strategies tend to shape up the opinions of the customers about the fast-food restaurant altogether.

The conclusion can also be generally made that customers tend to prefer the brand they have adequate knowledge of the business concept for any restaurant chain is the overall impression the customers have about its resourcing capabilities, management capabilities and the fundamental qualities that makes it gain an edge over the rest of the competition in the marketplace.

It can also be concluded that the mere impression of the particular franchise contributed majorly to the shaping up of the perceptions in the minds of its consumers altogether. Business concept has been highlighted as one significant success factor in establishing greater brand awareness and the increased likelihood of the consumers to get attracted to any particular fast-food restaurant in Pakistan.

If the consumers have any kind of doubts in their minds they would never be interested in coming to your restaurant. For instance, as an interviewee suggested, it was due to the business concept that they were able to gain a competitive edge in a market as competitive as that of Pakistan's fast-food market. By just receiving a "Halal" license and getting exclusive supply of its chicken and other ingredients, the interviewee seems to believe that it gave a fundamental advantage over the rest of the international fast-food chains operating in Pakistan.

It can be seen now that this mattered to the people of Pakistan and it is rather mandatory for any international franchise to first get a Halal license to the successful running of its business in this market. Also, according to the respondents it was more important for the consumers when there was an international fast-food franchise altogether as they immediately attached greater value attributes with the products and services being offered by the brand in comparison with the local fast-food restaurants. This is the power of a business concept; the customer's blindly rely upon the products and services being offered to them when it came from an international franchise. Once an impression is made in the minds of the customers, it is for a lifetime and this is the very reason why first impressions are so important for businesses.

6.2 Knowledge Contribution

This research has contributed to knowledge through the shedding of light on how franchising is carried out in the fast food chain industry in Pakistan. There is ample empirical literature

and information on the franchising of the fast-food industries in the Western countries such as Europe and the Americas. However, information and data on those of Pakistan have been scanty, if non-existent. This research has provided enough data on the operations of franchising in the fast-food industry of Pakistan thereby contributing to literature and well and practice of franchising in less developed countries.

It serves as a research foundation for international and local franchises interested in capitalising on the growing opportunities in the Pakistani restaurant market and other similar regional markets. The study identifies the franchising challenges that must be addressed in this specific market. In practise, franchised restaurants, particularly global chains, appear to meet the criteria for entering a market. These criteria may be linked to the critical success factors of entering a specific market. The criteria, however, have not been found in published academic studies.

It has identified critical success factors for restaurants in Pakistan. According to research, CSFs can be influenced by geographical locations and environmental conditions, among other things (Rockart & Christine, 1981). Because of Pakistan's unique geographical location, sociopolitical, and environmental conditions, the CSFs identified in this region may not be identical to those found in other regions. Neither would they be as relevant.

The study adds to the literature by triangulating research methods in an attempt to be more comprehensive in examining CSF from the customer's point of view. We couldn't find any published academic studies that looked at critical success factors for franchised restaurants from the customers' perspective.

This research contributes a lot in guiding fast food businesses to reap maximum profits for their businesses in the future.

6.3 Significance of the Study

The above study has contributed a lot of knowledge on how to operate a successful fast food chain franchise in Pakistan. Through analysis of data collected, areas of improvement as well as recommendations have clearly sufficed, advancing the need for this study. The success of any franchise operation, besides fast food, may be gladly boosted by this study.

This study will be a stepping stone for future research and will enable not only local businesses but international franchising brands to adopt their business practises in line with the variables and their significance to the business in order to achieve success. As explained in Table 31 the factors listed provide an insight to factors they must consider in order to be successful in the Pakistani fast food franchise industry.

The study also touched upon the impact of Covid in the fast food franchise industry in Pakistan which will serve as a basis for future research.

6.4 Implications of the theory and practice of the franchising industry

The franchising industry injects into the national GDP billions of dollars in products and services, payroll, and the creation of employment opportunities, hence benefiting the local economy.

Furthermore, franchising drives further growth in the local economy by offering competition to local firms. Competition, when properly capitalised on, means an incentive to scale up operations and improve service delivery in order to remain afloat.

For franchisors, government policies are extremely important. The importance of government policies to franchisors derives from the fact that the majority of franchisors are foreign nationals who are concerned about the host country's legal ramifications. Franchisees, on the other hand, maintain a local presence and are only concerned with local rules such as licencing requirements. Local licencing laws, on the other hand, apply to all firms, not just franchisees.

For a restaurant franchise system to work in Pakistan, the franchisor must carefully pick franchisees, develop a strong connection with them, give instructions and support, and most importantly, make the franchise agreement flexible to meet the needs of the franchisee.

6.5 Recommendations

For any fast food franchise or any restaurant business in general, the primary focus of the business should be to attract a loyal customer base towards the business for the long term. Temporary success is not the goal and the fast food business industry is extremely competitive, not just in Pakistan but also everywhere in the world. It is of the utmost significance for the business that it is able to attract reasonable revenues for a long time, and that is only possible through establishing a loyal customer base.

The research makes the following recommendations:

1. Loyal customers are like your own individual marketers who will even spread positive word of mouth for the long-term survival of your business. Specific to the fast food business, people actually rely on positive word of mouth and the reviews that come across through social media and other modes of communication. Before going to a restaurant, we always look out for reviews about the business and how the other customers potentially rate their food and service altogether.
2. Fast food franchises should have complete clarity in their minds about their market positions in the industry. The competition is rapidly intensifying, and it is the need of the moment for fast food businesses to have a strategic plan at hand to drive up their business sales and create a strong business image altogether.
3. As highlighted in this study, the business concept plays a crucial role in fast food franchises. Some researchers have stated that the business concept must be clear to its customers, and that this is even more important than the quality of the food service. It is thought that having a well-defined business plan helps restaurants all over get more customers.
4. Businesses need to be more creative when it comes to business concepts if they wish to maintain a strong place within the industry.
5. It was concluded that employee competence is critical to the success of fast food businesses. It is, therefore, recommended that the fast food franchises invest heavily in the training and development of their staff and employees in such a way that they are able to effectively attract some positive revenues for the business by being able to engage with some customers in the long-term.

6. Evidently, the food industry is a labour-intensive industry, and the linkage between customers and personnel is important, meaning that employee competence plays a significant role in determining its overall success in the long run.
7. Most importantly, the business should be able to establish a competitive edge in the marketplace, and this can be done by developing key success factors. Key success factors play a crucial role in establishing a strong and significant position for the business in the long term.
8. Fast food businesses should be able to plan strategically if they wish to drive up their sales in a market as competitive as that of the fast food industry. It is only a matter of correct strategic positioning that the business should be able to flourish within the industry by attracting handsome sales through creating a loyal customer base within the industry.

6.6 Need for Further Research

In this modern, competitive and complex world of business, studies conducted in the past are easily superseded and replaced by more modern and hi-tech research. Consequently, research conducted cannot be deemed remain relevant and influential forever as new ones are poised to bring new ideas, facts and data that are huge improvements of them. This study, therefore, expresses the need for future research to be conducted in this particular area of business, This would engender continuity to the subject area and help to bring out new and better ways of doing franchising in the fast food industries, not only in Pakistan, but around the globe.

References

- Agnelo, R. M. & Vladimir, A. N., 2007. *Hospitality Today: An Introduction*. Lansing, Michigan: Education Institute of the American Hotel and Lodging Association
- Aliouche, E. H., & Schlenrich, U. A. 2011. Towards a Strategic Model of Global Franchise Expansion. *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 87., Iss. 3., pp. 345–365.
- Alon, I. 2004. Global franchising and development in emerging and transitioning markets. *Journal of Macro Marketing*, 24, 156-167.
- Alon, I. 2006. *Service Franchising: A Global Perspective*. New York, USA: Springer.
- Alon, I., 2006. Key success factors of franchising systems in the retailing sector.
- Alon, I., Lerner, M., & Shoham, A. 2016. Cross-national cultural values and nascent entrepreneurship: Factual versus normative values. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, 16(3), 321–340.
- Ambastha, A. & Momaya, K. 2004. Competitiveness of Firms: Review of Theory, Frameworks, and Models, *Singapore Management Review*, 26 (1), 45.
- Amberg, M., Fischl, F. & Wiener, M., 2005. Background of Critical Success Factor Research. Nurnberg: Friedrich-Alexander-Universitat.
- Anderson, E. W. & Shugan, S. M., 1991. Repositioning for Changing Preferences: The Case of Meat versus Poultry. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 18(No. 2), pp. 219-232
- Asbill, R. M., & Goldman, S. M. 2001. *Fundamentals of International Franchising*. USA: ABA Publishing
- Asemi, A., & Jazi, M. D. 2010. A comparative study of critical success factors (CSFs) in implementation of ERP in developed and developing countries. *International Journal*, 2(5), 99–110
- Aslam, M. 2011. *Pakistan Economy in Retrospects, 1947-2010*. Ferozsons (Pvt.) Ltd. Lahore, Pakistan.
- Atkins, P. & Bowler, I., 2001. *Food in Society: Economy, Culture and Geography*. London:Arnold.
- Autio, E., Pathak, S., & Wennberg, K. 2013. Consequences of cultural practices for entrepreneurial behaviours. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 44, 334–362.

- Bachmann, J., Engelen, A., & Schwens, C. 2016. Toward a better understanding of the association between strategic planning and entrepreneurial orientation—The moderating role of national culture. *Journal of International Management*, 22(4), 297–315.
- Bahauddin, A.R., Wei, L.S. and Mantihal, S., 2020. Food Sensory Factors and Restaurant Images on Customer Satisfaction: A Comparison of Franchise and Local Fast-Food Restaurant. *Asian Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 1(4), pp.62-71.
- Barthelemy, J. 2008. Opportunism, knowledge, and the performance of franchise chains. *Strategic Management Journal*, 29, 1451-1463
- Belk, R.W. ed., 2007. *Handbook of qualitative research methods in marketing*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Bell, E., Bryman, A. and Harley, B., 2018. *Business research methods*. Oxford university press.
- Bordonaba-Juste, M., & Polo-Redondo, Y. 2004. Relationships in franchised distribution system: the case of the Spanish market. *International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, Vol. 14., Iss. 1., pp. 101–127.
- Box, T. & Miller, W. (2011). Small Firm Competitive Strategy, *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 10 (2), 55-59.
- Brands, H. and Gavin, F.J. eds., 2020. *COVID-19 and world order: The future of conflict, competition, and cooperation*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Bretas, V.P.G. and Alon, I., 2020. The impact of COVID-19 on franchising in emerging markets: An example from Brazil. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 39(6), pp.6-16.
- Bujisic, M., Hutchinson, J., & Parsa, H. G. 2014. The Effects of Restaurant Quality Attributes on Customer
- Camillo, A. A., Connolly, D. J., & Kim, W. G. 2008. Success and failure in Northern California: Critical success factors for independent restaurants. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 49(4), 364-380.
- Chia, X.R., Kee, D.M.H., Khor, S.T., Chin, K.Y., Lok, T.X., Almutairi, H.A., Quttainah, M.A., Balakrishnan, H. and Kulkarni, S., 2020. Contributing Factors to Organizational

Success: A Case Study of McDonald's. *International journal of Tourism and hospitality in Asia Pasific*, 3(2), pp.38-47.

Chiou, J., Hsieh, C., & Yang, C. 2004. The effect of franchisors' communication, service assistance, and competitive advantage on franchisees' intentions to remain in the franchise system. *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 42., Iss. 1., pp. 19–36

Chun, S.H. and Nyam-Ochir, A., 2020. The Effects of Fast Food Restaurant Attributes on Customer Satisfaction, Revisit Intention, and Recommendation Using DINESERV Scale. *Sustainability*, 12(18), p.7435.

COCHET, O., DORMANN, J. & EHRMANN, T. 2008a. Capitalizing on franchisee autonomy: Relational forms of governance as controls in idiosyncratic franchise dyads. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 46, 50-72.

COMBS, J. G., KETCHEN, D. J. & HOOVER, V. L. 2004a. A strategic groups approach to the franchising-performance relationship. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 19, 877-897.

COMBS, J. G., MICHAEL, S. C. & CASTROGIOVANNI, G. J. 2004c. Franchising: A review and avenues to greater theoretical diversity. *Journal of Management*, 30, 907-931.

Combs, J.G., Michael, S.C. & Castrogiovanni, G.J., 2004, 'Franchising: A review and avenues to greater theoretical diversity', *Journal of Management* 30(6), 907–931.

Cooper, D. R. & Schindler, P. S., 2008. *Business Research Methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill

Covin, J. G., & Lumpkin, G. T. 2011. Entrepreneurial orientation theory and research: Reflections on a needed construct. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(5), 855–872.

Covin, J. G., & Miller, D. 2014. International entrepreneurial orientation: Conceptual considerations, research themes, measurement issues, and future research directions. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 38(1), 11–44.

Covin, J. G., & Wales, W. J. 2012. The measurement of entrepreneurial orientation. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 36(4), 677–702.

Dada, L., & Watson, A. 2013a. Entrepreneurial orientation and the franchise system: Organizational antecedents and performance outcomes. *European Journal of Marketing*, 47(5/6), 790–812.

Dada, L., & Watson, A. 2013b. The effect of entrepreneurial orientation on the franchise relationship. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(8), 955–977.

Dada, L., Watson, A., & Kirby, D. 2012. Toward a model of franchisee entrepreneurship. *International Small Business Journal*, 30(5), 559–583.

Daudpota, F. 2013. Limitation on Repatriation of Royalties out of Pakistan - An Imprudent and Unlawful Measure that Hinders Development of Franchise Markets. *International Franchising*, Vol. 17., No. 1., pp. 20-21.

Dillon, W. R., Madden, T. J. & Firtle, N. H., 1990. *Marketing Research in a Marketing Environment*. 2nd ed. Boston, MA: Times Mirror/ Mosby College Publishing.

Doherty, A.M., 2007. The internalization of retailing. Factors influencing the choice of franchising as a market entry strategy. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Volume 18(2), pp. 184-205

Doherty, A.M., 2007. The internalization of retailing. Factors influencing the choice of franchising as a market entry strategy. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Volume 18(2), pp. 184-205

Dube, B., Mara, C. and Ntimane, V., 2020. Perceptions of franchise stakeholders on trust in franchising relationships. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 9(1), pp.1-12.

Dung, T.T.T., 2020, November. COVID-19 pandemic impact on Franchise industry and Franchise dispute resolution. In *Research Technologies of Pandemic Coronavirus Impact (RTCOV 2020)* (pp. 239-244). Atlantis Press.

Ebben, J. & Johnson, A. 2005. Efficiency, Flexibility, or Both? Evidence Linking Strategy to Performance in Small Firms. *Strategic Management Journal*, 26: 1249-1259.

Eser, Z. 2012. Inter-organizational trust in franchise relationships and the performance outcomes: The case of fast-food restaurant in Turkey. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality*, 24, 774-790

Eser, Z. 2012. Inter-organizational trust in franchise relationships and the performance outcomes The case of fast-food restaurants in Turkey. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24, 774-790.

Esteves, J. 2004. *Definition and analysis of critical success factors for ERP implementation projects*. Barcelona, Spain: Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya

FELÍCIO, J. A., DUARTE, M., CALDEIRINHA, V. & RODRIGUES, R. 2014b. Franchisee-based brand equity and performance. *The Service Industries Journal*, 34, 757-771.

Forte, R., & Carvalho, J. 2013. Internationalisation through franchising: the Parfois case
Fpumo, W. and Moriera, B., 2020. Risk Management in the Middle of a Sustainable Covid-19 Pandemic. *Journal Dimensie Management and Public Sector*, 1(1), pp.17-19.

FRAZER, L. & WINZAR, H. 2005. Exits and expectations: why disappointed franchisees leave. *Journal of Business Research*, 58, 1534-1542.

Frazer, L., and Winzar, H., 2003. Causes of franchisee failure: an analysis of franchisor and franchisee perspectives. Proceedings of the World Marketing Congress. Perth, West Australia.

Gikonyo, L., Berndt, A., & Wadawi, J. 2015. Critical Success Factors for Franchised Restaurants Entering the Kenyan Market: Franchisors' Perspective. *SAGE Open*, 5(4), 1-8.

GILLIS, W. E., COMBS, J. G. & KETCHEN, D. J. 2014. Using Resource-Based Theory to Help Explain Plural Form Franchising. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 38, 449-472.

Gitia, W.G., 2017. *The Influence of Competitive Advantage Strategies on Performance of International Fast Food Franchises in Nairobi, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).

GROVOAIA, N. & WINDSPERGER, J. 2013. Real Options, Intangible Resources and Performance of Franchise Networks. *Managerial & Decision Economics*, 34, 183-194

Goulding, C., 2002. *Grounded theory: a practical guide for management, business and market researchers*, Sage Publications Ltd, London.

Griffith, K.L., 2019. An Empirical Study of Fast-Food Franchising Contracts: Towards a New Intermediary Theory of Joint Employment. *Wash. L. Rev.*, 94, p.171.

Hair, J.F., 2015. *Essentials of business research methods*. ME Sharpe.

Hair, J.F., Celsi, M., Ortinau, D.J. and Bush, R.P., 2008. *Essentials of marketing research*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill/Higher Education.

Hietschold, N., Reinhardt, R., & Gurtner, S. 2014. Measuring critical success factors of TQM implementation successfully—a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Production Research*, 52(21), 6254-6272.

Hitt et al, 2002. *Strategic Entrepreneurship, Creating a New Mindset*. Malden, MA: Blackwell Publishing

Hoffman, R. C. & Preble, J. F., 2004. Global Franchising Current Status and Future Challenges. *The Journal of Services marketing*, 18(No. 2), pp. 101-113.

Hoffman, R. C., & Preble, J. F. 2004. Global franchising: Current status and future challenges. *The Journal of Services Marketing*, 18, 101-113

Hua, N. & Dalbor, M.C., 2013, 'Evidence of franchising on outperformance in the restaurant industry: A long term analysis and perspective', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* 25(5), 723–739

Jaravaza, D.C. & Chitando, P., 2013, 'The role of store location in influencing customers' store choice', *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences* 4(3), 302–307

Johannesson, J., 2010. The Dynamics of East African Market. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 2(1).

Kacker, M., Dant, R.P., Emerson, J. & Coughlan, A.T., 2013, 'How firm strategies impact size of partner-based retail networks: Evidence from franchising', *Journal of Small Business Management* 4(2), 21–37.

Kandampully, J., 2006. The new customer-centered business model for the Hospitality Industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Volume 18(3), pp. 173- 187.

Khan, S., Hussain, S.M. and Yaqoob, F., 2013. Determinants of customer satisfaction in fast food industry a study of fast food restaurants Peshawar Pakistan. *Studia commercialia Bratislavensia*, 6(21), pp.56-65.

- Kremez, Z., Frazer, L., & Thaichon, P. 2019. The effects of e-commerce on franchising: Practical implications and models. *Australasian Marketing Journal (AMJ)*
- Lashley, C. & Morrison, A., 2000. *Franchising Hospitality Services*. Oxford: ButterworthHeinemann
- Lee, K., Khan, M.A. and Ko, J.Y., 2008. Outback Steakhouse in Korea: A success story. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 49(1), pp.62-72.
- Lim, J., and Frazer, L., 2004. Matching franchisor-franchisee roles and competencies. Proceedings of the International Society of Franchising 18th Annual Conference. Las Vegas, Nevada.
- Ling, C.H., and Mansori, S. 2018. The effects of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: Evidence from Malaysia Engineering Industry. *International Journal of Industrial Marketing*, 3(1), 20-35.
- Luangsuvimol, T. & Kleiner, B. H., 2004. Effective Franchise Management. *Management Research News*, 27(No.4/5), pp. 63-71.
- Mabesele, L.A., 2009. *The role of performance measures in the fast food franchisee industry to sustain positive growth: Cape Metropole-South Africa* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Mackay, N., Spies, H., Williams, C., Jansen Van Rensburg, L.J. & Petzer, D.J., 2013, 'The influence of service brand equity on the strength of brand relationships in the fast food industry', *Southern African Business Review* 17(2), 67–92.
- MADANOGLU, M., LEE, K. & CASTROGIOVANNI, G. J. 2011. Franchising and firm financial performance among U.S. restaurants. *Journal of Retailing*, 87, 406-417.
- MANEV, I. M., GYOSHEV, B. S. & MANOLOVA, T. S. 2005. The role of human and social capital and entrepreneurial orientation for small business performance in a transitional economy. *International journal of entrepreneurship and innovation management*, 5, 298-318.
- MARNBURG, E., LARSEN, S. & OGAARD, T. 2004. Uncovering aspects of franchisees' incentives: an explorative investigation. *Food Service Technology*, 4, 117-128.

- Melnyk, V., van Osselaer, S.M.J., and Bijmolt, T.H.A. 2009. Are women more loyal customers than men? Gender differences in loyalty to firms and individual service providers. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(4) 82–96.
- Mendelsohn, E., 2004. *The Guide to Franchising*. 7th ed. London: Thomson Learning.
- Michael, S. C., & Combs, J. G. 2008. Entrepreneurial Failure: The Case of Franchisees. *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 46., Iss. 1., pp. 73–90.
- Mohd Sidik, S.N. 2014. *How Loyal Are You? Factors Influencing Consumer Brand Loyalty*. Sintok: University Utara Malaysia
- Monge, E.C, Sanz, I.P, and Zavala, P.H. 2017. *Economic Sustainability in Franchising: A model to Predict Franchisor Success or Failure*. Spain: University of Burgos
- Mueller, J. & Kleiner, B., 2004. Determining Exempt and non-Exempt Status in the Fast Food Industry. *Management Research News*, 27(No. 10), pp. 51-57.
- Müller, H. J. 2015. The Internationalization of the Service Franchising Operations: Decision Making During Internationalization Process: A View in International Consulting / Training Business. *Pinnacle Business Management*, Vol. 3., Iss. 2., pp. 758-770.
- Nakao, A.N., Carneiro-da-Cunha, J.A., Patah, L.A. and Nassif, V.M.J., 2019. Performance of services and products in a fast food franchise chain: reflections about the home delivery model. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 19(1), pp.85-99.
- Nassaji, H. 2015. Qualitative and descriptive research: Data type versus data analysis. *Language Teaching Research*, 19(2), 129-132.
- Nijmeijer, K. J., Fabbrocotti, I. N., & Huijsman, R. 2014. Making Franchising Work: A Framework Based on a Systematic Review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 16., pp. 62–83
- Nijmeijer, K.J., Fabbrocotti, I.N. & Huijsman, R., 2013, ‘Making franchising work: A framework based on a systematic review’, *International Journal of Management Review* 16(1), 62–83.
- Noor, Y.M, Lu, M.H, Nasharuddin, F.M, Kong, M.H, and Aziz, N. 2018. The factor Influencing Customer Preference towards International Food and Beverage Franchise in Malaysia. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 31(12), 25-33

Nyadzayo, M. W., Matanda, M. J., and Ewing, M. T. 2016. Franchisee-based brand equity: The role of brand relationship quality and brand citizenship behavior. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 52, 163–174.

O’Gorman, K., 2009. Origins of the commercial hospitality industry: from fanciful to factual. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. Volume 21 (No. 7) pp. 777-790.

Ottensbacher, M., Harrington, R. and Parsa, H., 2009. Defining the hospitality discipline: a discussion of pedagogical and research implications. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*. Volume 33 (No 3), pp. 263-83.

Paik, Y. and Choi, D.Y., 2007. Control, autonomy and collaboration in the fast food industry: A comparative study between domestic and international franchising. *International Small Business Journal*, 25(5), pp.539-562.

Pizam, A. & Shani, A. 2009. The nature of the hospitality industry: present and future managers’ perspectives. *An International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*, Volume. 20 (No. 1), pp. 134-50.

Porter, M. 1985. *Competitive Advantage, Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*, New York, NY: The Free Press

Qu, M., Frazer, L., Weaven, S. and Arli, D., 2018. Critical factors for successful franchise expansion into China. Australia and New Zealand International Business Academy Conference.

Quinn, B. & Alexander, N., 2002. International Retail Franchising: A Conceptual Framework. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 30(No. 5), pp. 264-276.

Rahatullah, M.K. 2014. Role of Trust and Commitment in Building Successful Franchise Business Relationships. *Journal of Knowledge, Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 2(1), 90-107

Ramírez-Hurtado, José M., Francisco J. Rondán-Cataluña, Flor M. Guerrero-Casas, and relationships affect franchisees’ satisfaction? The importance of fairness,

Risner, M.E., 2001. *Successful fast-food franchising in Brazil and the role of culture: four cases* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Florida).

- Roberts-Lombard, M., 2009, 'Customer retention strategies of fast-food outlets in South Africa: A focus on Kentucky Fried Chicken (KFC), 'Nando's and Steers', *Journal of African Business* 10(2), 235–249
- Saeed, K.A., 2013. *The economy of Pakistan*, Karachi: Oxford Univ. Press.
- Samsudin, F., Wahab, S.A, Latiff, A.S, and Osman, S.I. 2018. Strategic Direction and Sustainable Development in Franchising Organizations: A Conceptual Study. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 11(4), 89-98.
- Sarstedt, M., and Mooi, E. 2014. *A concise Guide to Market Research*. Australia: University of Melbourne.
- Sashi, C. M. & Karuppur, D. P., 2002. Franchising in Global Markets: Towards a Conceptual Framework. *International Marketing Review*, 17(No. 5), pp. 499-524.
- SBP 2018. *Annual Report 2017-19 State of the Economy*. Available online: www.data.worldbank.org [Accessed 24 March 2020]
- Schlosser, E., 2001. *Fast Food Nation*. St Ies: The Penguin Press.
- Scott, S. and Spell, C., 1998. Factors for new franchise success. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 39(3), p.43.
- Sedera, D., Gable, G. & Chan, T., 2004. *Measuring Enterprise Systems Success: the importance of a Multiple Stakeholder Perspective*. Turku, European Conference in Information Systems (ECIS, 2004).
- Shapiro, A., 2005. How including prior knowledge as a subject variable may change outcomes of learning. *Research. American Educational Research Journal*, Volume 41(No. 1), pp. 159-189
- Sharma, A. & Christie, I.T., 2010. Performance assessment using value-chain analysis in Mozambique. *International Journal Of Contemporary Hospitality Management Volume*, Volume 22(No. 2-3) , pp. 282-299.
- Shrestha, N., Shad, M.Y., Ulvi, O., Khan, M.H., Karamehic-Muratovic, A., Nguyen, U.S.D., Baghbanzadeh, M., Wardrup, R., Aghamohammadi, N., Cervantes, D. and Nahiduzzaman, K.M., 2020. The impact of COVID-19 on globalization. *One Health*, p.100180.

- Siddiqui, D. A. and Ahmed, Q. M. (2019). The Causal Relationship Between Institutions and Economic Growth: An Empirical Investigation for Pakistan Economy. *International Economics and Business*, 5(1), 1-19
- Singh, A., and Masaku, M. 2014. Sampling Techniques & Determination of Sample Size in Applied Statistics Research: An Overview. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and management*, 2(11), 1-22.
- So, K.K.F., King, C., Sparks, B.A. & Wang, Y., 2013, 'The influence of customer brand identification on hotel brand evaluation and loyalty development', *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 34(1), 31–41.
- Sowunmi, F., Omigie, C., and Daniel, D. (2014). Consumers' perception on Ofada Rice in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(16), 78-85.
- STANWORTH, J., STANWORTH, C., WATSON, A., PURDY, D. & HEALEAS, S. 2004. Franchising as a small business growth strategy - A resource-based view of organizational development. *International Small Business Journal*, 22, 539-559.
- Trkman, P. 2010. The critical success factors of business process management. *International journal of information management*, 30(2), 125-134.
- Uddin, M., Chowdhury, A., Zafar, S., Shafique, S., & Liu, J. 2018. Institutional determinants of inward FDI: Evidence from Pakistan. *International Business Review*.
- Vahdati, H., and Nejad, S. H. 2016. Brand Personality toward Customer Purchase Intention: The Intermediate Role of Electronic Word-of-Mouth and Brand Equity. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 21(2), 1-26.
- Vignali, C. 2001. McDonalds: Think global act local, the marketing mix. *British Food Journal*, 103, 97-111.
- Vignali, C., 2001. McDonalds: Think Global Act Local, the Marketing Mix. *British Food Journal*, 103(No. 2), pp. 97-111.
- Watson, A., Dada, O. (Lola), Wright, O., & Perrigot, R. 2017. *Entrepreneurial Orientation Rhetoric in Franchise Organizations: The Impact of National Culture*. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 104225871773851.

Winer, R.S. 2004. *Marketing Management*, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall Publishing Company

Wingrove, C.A. and Urban, B., 2017. Franchised fast food brands: An empirical study of factors influencing growth. *Acta Commercii*, 17(1), pp.1-8.

Zaidi, S. A. 2005. *Issues in Pakistan's Economy*. Oxford University Press Karachi, Pakistan.

Zhang, Y. 2015. The Impact of Brand Image on Consumer Behavior: A Literature Review. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 3(1), 58-62.

Montagu, D., 2002. Franchising of health services in low-income countries. *Health Policy and Planning*, 17(2), pp.121-130.

Berry, L., Bolton, R., Bridges, C., Meyer, J., Parasuraman, A. and Seiders, K. (2010) Opportunities for Innovation in the Delivery of Interactive Retail Services. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*. Vol.24 (2), pp.155-167.

Grünhagen, M., Dant, R. and Zhu, M. (2012) Emerging Consumer Perspectives on American Franchise Offerings: Variety Seeking Behavior in China*. *Journal of Small Business Management*. Vol.50 (4), pp.596-620.

Nyadzayo, M., Matanda, M. and Rajaguru, R. (2018) The determinants of franchise brand loyalty in B2B markets: An emerging market perspective. *Journal of Business Research*. Vol.86, pp.435-445.

Shin, C., Hwang, G., Lee, H. and Cho, S. (2015) The Impact of Korean Franchise Coffee Shop Service Quality and Atmosphere on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *The East Asian Journal of Business Management*. Vol.5 (4), pp.47-57.

Perrigot, R., Oxibar, B. and Déjean, F. (2013) Corporate Social Disclosure in the Franchising Sector: Insights from French Franchisors' Websites. *Journal of Small Business Management*. Vol.53 (2), pp.321-339.

Bawany, Y. (2022) fatburger – Insanity at its best! [Online]. Insanity at its best!. Available: <https://yousufbawany.com/tag/fatburger/> [Accessed 6 Apr 2022].

Pizza Hut Centaurus Mall, Islamabad Branch - Phone Number, Branch Code & Address. (2022) [Online]. Branches.pk. Available: <https://branches.pk/branch-detail/Pizza-Hut-Centaurus-Mall-Islamabad-Branch> [Accessed 6 Apr 2022].

Covid-19: KFC tells customers to hold off on the 'Finger Lickin' for now. (2022) [Online]. Profit by Pakistan Today. Available:

<https://profit.pakistantoday.com.pk/2020/08/25/covid-19-kfc-tells-customers-to-hold-off-on-the-finger-lickin-for-now/> [Accessed 4 Apr 2022].

APPENDIXES

APPENDIX 1

RESEARCH INFORMATION

Research Title:

To identify the Key Determinants for Successful Performance in Franchising: A study of the Pakistan's Fast Food Industry

INTERVIEW / PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Research Investigator:	Farhan Sharif	Participant Name:	
Participant Email:		Participant Contact Number:	
Date of Interview:		Notes Taken By:	
Interview Start Time:		Interview End Time:	

The interview will take up to forty minutes. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to stop the interview or withdraw from the research at any time. Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of the above research project. Ethical procedures for academic research undertaken from UK institutions require that interviewees explicitly agree to being interviewed and how the information contained in their interview will be used.

Participant Consent Form

Programme of Study: Doctorate of Business Administration

Title: To identify the Key Determinants for Successful Performance in Franchising: A study of the Pakistan's Fast Food Industry

Name of Researcher: Farhan Sharif

I confirm that I have read and understood the purpose of the study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline.

I understand that my responses will be kept strictly confidential. I understand that my name will not be linked with the research materials, and will not be identified or identifiable in the report or reports that result from the research unless I have given authorisation.

I agree for this interview to be tape-recorded. I understand that the audio recording made of this interview will be used only for analysis and that extracts from the interview, from which I would not be personally identified, may be used in any conference presentation, report or journal article developed as a result of the research. I understand that no other use will be made of the recording without my written permission, and that no one outside the research team will be allowed access to the original recording.

I agree that my anonymised data will be kept for future research purposes such as publications related to this study after the completion of the study.

I agree to be contacted in the future by the principal investigator.

I agree to take part in this interview and the above study.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Principal Investigator

Date

Signature

Copy (ies): The original copy of the signed and dated consent form should be placed in the main project file which must be kept in a secure location.

APPENDIX 2

Survey Questions:

Introduction

Dear participant,

Thank you for participating in The research survey. We appreciate your response.

- I am the student of..... The purpose of the study is to determine the key success factors of fast food franchises operating in Pakistan. In particular, this questionnaire addresses customer evaluation of Pakistan fast food franchises and finds out if brand Image, Product features, Convenience, the competence of employee, Pricing, Atmosphere/ambience, have any impact of customer choice of selecting a particular franchise.

Part 1: Demographic of Research

1. Please indicate your gender.

- Female
- Male

2. Please select the category of your age.

- 15 years to 25 years
- 25 years to 35 years
- 35 years to 45 years
- 45years to 55 years

3. Please indicate your position

- Student
- Company employee
- Employer
- Self employed
- Investor
- Government official
- Office and administrative job
- House work/parenting
- Others

4. Please indicate the name of Fast food franchise, you frequently visit

- McDonald's
- KFC
- Hardees
- Burger King
- Subway
- Others.....

5. How often do you visit this fast food franchise?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Twice a week
- Monthly
- Once in six months
- Other.....

Part 2: How would you rate the following aspects for the same (above mentioned) fast food franchise. Please mark with in the correct box. You cannot mark tick in more than one boxes.

Strongly agree	1
Agree	2
I do not know, neutral	3
Disagree	4
Strongly disagree	5

1. The following statements address your opinion towards “Convenience” of the fast food

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
They do not keep customers waiting for a longer time compared to other fast foods					
The location of the fast food is convenient					
The speed of service meets my expectations					
They have adequate parking space					

2. The following statements address your opinion towards “pricing” of the fast food

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
They offer food at lower prices compared to other fast foods					
The food and services offered are very good value for my money					
The food and services offered are very good bargain considering the prices					
The food prices are stable they do not change abruptly					
They inform the customers about the change of prices in good time before they change					

3. The following statements address your opinion towards “product features” of the fast food

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The menu has a large variety of choices					
The products are always the same quality					
The products are always the same quantity					
The menu is flexible to my tastes and combinations					
They often have new and exciting products on the menu					
The food hygiene standards are according to my expectations					

4. The following statements address your opinion towards “employee competence” of the fast food

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The employees are warm and welcoming					
The employees have the knowledge to answer my questions					
The employees provide prompt service					
The employees understand my specific needs					

The employees give me individual attention					
The employees are never too busy to respond to customer requests					

5. The following statements address your opinion towards “atmosphere” of the fast food

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The environment in this fast food is relaxing					
The music in this fast food is well selected					
The décor in this fast food is attractive					
The spacing between tables is adequate					
The chairs in the fast food are comfortable					
The physical facilities of are visually attractive					

6. The following statements address your opinion towards “brand image” of the fast food

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I prefer the selected fast food franchise over other franchises due to its satisfactory features					
I am certain that the value added services of my selected franchise is better than the market rivalries					
I think that this franchise has a strong brand name in the market					
This franchise performs as it promises					
This franchise is effective to my needs as compared to other brands					
This franchise helps me to better fit in my society and I am perceived well by others					

7. Success of this fast food franchise

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I like this fast food franchise					
I will continue coming to this franchise					
I would recommend this restaurant to my friends					
The fast food delivers what it promises					

8. I would continue coming to this franchise if the following features are present

Statements	Strongly agree	agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Convenience					
Pricing factors					
Product features					
Employee competence					
Atmosphere					
Brand Image					

Fast-Food Venues and Locals

APPENDIX 3

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of fast food. Please contact the author for further information.

APPENDIX 4

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of fast food. Please contact the author for further information.

APPENDIX 5

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of fast food. Please contact the author for further information.

APPENDIX 6

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of fast food. Please contact the author for further information.

APPENDIX 7

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is a photograph of fast food. Please contact the author for further information.